

**Assessing the role of Education as a tool for Nigeria's Sustainable
Economic Growth**

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to the memory of those who lost their lives during the #EndSARS protest in Nigeria. 20/10/2020 – we won't forget.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACMGS	Archdeacon Crowther Memorial Girls' School
ASUU	Academic Staff Union of Universities
BCMSS	Bishop Crowther Memorial Secondary School
CMS	Church Missionary Society
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DBA	Doctorate in Business Administration
E1, E2	Employer
ESD	Education for Sustainable Development
FRN	Federal Republic of Nigeria
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ILO	International Labour Organisation
JAMB	Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M1, M2, M3	Management
N	Naira
NCE	National Certificate of Education
NECO	National Examinations Council
NEEDS	National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy
NESG	Nigerian Economic Summit Group
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPE	National Policy on Education
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PTA	Parent-Teacher Association
QE	Quality Education
R&D	Research and Development
S1, S2, S3, S4, S5	Student
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEEDS	State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy
SEG	Sustainable Economic Growth

SSC	Senior School Certificate
T1, T2, T3, T4, T5	Teacher
UBE	Universal Basic Education
UBEC	Universal Basic Education Commission
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
UN	United Nations
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organisation
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
TRCN	Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria
WAEC	West African Examinations Council
WOF	Word of Faith School
WTO	World Trade Organisation

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ABSTRACT

This exploratory research used endogenous economic growth theories to illustrate education as an investment in human capital formation and contribution to Nigeria's economic growth. The purpose of this research was to answer the question – How well do education providers in Nigeria align provision with the SDG of quality and access to education? QE requires a functional curriculum and teachers with the right knowledge and skills to undergo relevant training in line with education standards and labour market requirements. Corporate governance strategies in schools influence profit levels using monitoring and supervision to improve performance. This research exposed the problem of poor education in Nigeria evident in lack of basic skills, unemployable graduates, erratic government policies, unqualified teachers, insufficient funding and facilities, and poor school management policies. The researcher developed an empirical model that shows the link between education, human capital, and SEG. The research methodology gave a breakdown of the foundation, pre-field, field, and reporting phases which explained the philosophy, protocol, data collection methods and analysis using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. Mixed methods approach was used to have a holistic understanding of school management policies for SEG in Nigeria. The research participants showed interesting views and the results were triangulated from quantitative and qualitative methods. Data findings revealed that Nigeria is in great need of a sustained economic growth and has the potential to achieve this with proper investments in schools. This will enhance QE as a whole-school approach which is needed to ensure human capital availability and SEG in Nigeria. The study revealed different methods used to grade students' outcomes like examinations and research groups, and teachers' regular training which are important to be updated with current trends and requirements in the labour market. Contributions to knowledge and practice in schools are seen in management practices that

enhance QE in schools and as a way forward for Nigeria's transition from the old to the 'new economy'. The researcher also noted some lessons from the Finnish education system which can be tailored to fit the Nigerian context. It was recommended that the empirical model be tested using a descriptive investigation for more in-depth study of the subject and derive conclusions for the research.

Keywords: SEG, labour market, school management practices, QE, mixed methods, Nigeria

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

'The ultimate resource in economic development is people. It is people, not capital or raw materials that develop an economy' (Peter Drucker)

1.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter provides a background to the study, purpose, and structure of the thesis. The chapter also discusses the problem facing education in Nigeria and the link between quality education and sustainable economic growth based on UN reports. Having an experience and connection to the education sector in Nigeria, the later chapters of this thesis present an objective view of the education of the youth and its effect on Nigeria's sustainable economic growth.

1.2 Novelty and Originality of the Research

This research is a doctoral thesis written to answer important questions, fill gaps in knowledge and practice, and for the researcher's professional development for the award of a DBA. The research gives full detail of the purpose of the study, research methods, interpretation and implications of the primary and secondary data findings. An original research paper must not only summarise already known information but also produce new knowledge and theories (Guetzkow et al. 2004). It could be based on previous research; however, to be considered original, the research must present a new angle to the findings and new perspectives. Novelty in this research produces new knowledge based on observations, new approaches to solving existing problems, and experiments. The first stage of this research is an introduction to the context. According to Cooper (2015), the introduction shows the known (a clear, concise, and easy-to-understand overview of the research

for a general audience), the unknown (what gap the research intends to fill), and an emphasis on the research question and objectives.

Originality of research focuses on using an original approach, an original theory, and studying an original topic. On the other hand, social scientists view originality considering the personal attributes of the researcher especially his/her moral character, authenticity and integrity (Guetzkow et al. 2004). This research thesis is built on objectivity and is free from bias. The researcher got full ethical approval from the University and consent from the research participants before conducting the study. During the field phase, the researcher acted as the participant-observer and took the 'enquiry from the outside' approach. Shared reality with the participants served as a source of new information and fresh perspective to further understand the research context. The researcher explains this in more detail in CHAPTER FIVE. Originality of this research is based on the research topic, the theory used, research methods used, data on which it is based, and the results of the research. Another category of research originality according to Guetzkow et al. (2004) is the innovative character of the questions and arguments formulated. In this case, the research questions are not designed from previous research. Rather, the questions are based on the researcher's experiences and real-life understanding of the context.

As opposed to research works by Ahmed (2015) that showcase university education as the main driver for SEG; this research uses selected secondary schools in Port Harcourt Nigeria to argue that secondary education provides the basis to develop broader skills for lifelong learning and problem solving in students (World Bank, 2007) compared to the university education that teaches only specific content and skills. The researcher seeks to fill the research gap in this study and argues that with secondary education only, an individual is still able to contribute to human capital accumulation even without a university degree.

The researcher has worked with the management board of the schools. During this time, some lapses were discovered in the schools and the education sector generally. A major challenge noticed was the difficulty of the schools to generate funds because of low tuition fees and the target market. The researcher was also present during some recruitment exercises and noticed the wide gap in the skills the schools needed and teachers' skills. Some teachers only resort to the teaching profession because of unemployment and so there is no motivation to work. Government policies are not tailored to the needs of the education sector. Although we are urging people to go to school, there is no effort to provide opportunities for these people when they graduate to contribute to Nigeria's economic life. With a strong passion for education, the researcher believes that a stable economic environment can inspire every individual to learn skills needed to be locally and globally relevant in the labour market.

1.3 Background to the Study

The development of any society is linked to inclusive education at the secondary level and serves as the best tool to realize desirable changes. In more detail, Bajaj and Chiu (2009) state that education is not just an end in itself but a mechanism for change in practices, qualities, information, and ways of life required to accomplish sustainability and stability among and within nations. These changes are seen in developing society's financial, human and sociological resources. As stated by The Commonwealth Education Hub (2015, p.1), the fourth goal of the Sustainable Development Goals is to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all'. Young people are top on the list for sustainability initiatives and declarations. Etuk et al. (2012) and Anupriya and Salim (2014) define inclusive education as the

right of every child to acquire new skills and values for the effective functioning of society irrespective of his or her differences.

According to Kaur (2015), the global concern and focus are on the young people and it is seen in the principles of Agenda 21, World Development Report by the World Bank (2006/2007), and the UN SDGs. Young people have become major partners in creating a more sustainable world and effective education for sustainable development programmes. Kaur (2015) goes further to note that ESD programmes focus on enhancing and activating the participation of young people in community actions leading to sustainable development; promoting a healthy lifestyle, social tolerance, and non-violence among young people; promoting gender-sensitive education; and empowering young people to participate in society and national development. This is summarised in a statement by UNESCO (2015, p.7), 'Education can, and must, contribute to a new vision of sustainable global development'.

An important step towards global citizenship is in encouraging youth participation in civil society, economic and political life. This participation of young people influences their development and contribution to society (Kaur, 2015). Drawing from the SDG 8 – which is to 'promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all' (UNESCO, 2017) – young people serve as a medium to achieve sustainable economic growth in their countries (Rieckmann et al., 2017). However, Onano (2015) stresses that policy makers, governments, political and business leaders, and international organisations lack what it takes to address issues that influence young people. Young people need to be the focus of the sustainable development agenda of their countries by ensuring that there is consistent access to quality education, employment, and strategic engagement in politics and governance (Onano, 2015; Kaur, 2015).

In the 1950s and 1960s, the government of the western region of Nigeria paid great attention to providing education as a pathway to economic growth. The citizens of the region on their part embraced and enjoyed benevolent education because of the leadership of their premier at the time – Chief Obafemi Awolowo. The government of the region also made education free and because of this, many people had access to quality education and free books in schools irrespective of social class (Afejuku, 2017). The result of this huge investment in education is seen in the high number of professors and teachers from the region¹. Because they were so highly educated, they affected other sectors of the national economy.

In today's world, it is clear that education is an investment in human resource development and it contributes significantly to economic development in the long run (Salgur, 2013). The purpose of education resides not only in providing the curricula and school subjects to the students but functions mainly in preparing them to live as responsible members of society. If a nation is unable to provide better education to its workforce, then it cannot achieve sustainable economic growth (Ozturk, 2001). The relationship between education and economic growth came from the concept that people feel that more schooling brings about a better educated human capital which leads to an increase in labour productivity (Salgur, 2013). The reason for this school of thought is that individuals who have a higher level of education are more literate and can be trained to be competent in future jobs. Besides, when people are better educated especially on basic skills, they can learn more quickly and adapt themselves more rapidly to complicated jobs and tasks. Several countries have come to the conclusion that inadequate education among the human capital in the production process is the main problem which threatens the economic growth of any country (EFA Global Monitoring Report 2011).

¹Obialo, M. (2020) *Top 10 Best Educated States in Nigeria - Nigerian Guide*. Nigerian Guide. Available at: <https://nigerianguide.com/ng/top-10-best-educated-states-in-nigeria/> (Accessed: 15 September 2021).

According to Armeanu et al. (2018), sustainable economic growth explains the economic development within a country that attempts to satisfy the needs of humans without jeopardizing the resources which will be needed by future generations. Kaur (2015) indicates that sustainable development is a pressing requirement of the 21st century and ensures that the urgent necessities of everyone is met and encompasses opportunities to attain a better life thereby ensuring a developed and secured environment (Ndubusi-Okolo et al., 2016).

Dauda (2010) emphasizes that the level of socio-economic development in nations is not reliant only on natural resources and physical capital but mainly on the quality and quantity of human capital. Human capital displays an intrinsic talent which Namasivayam and Denizci (2006) and Becker (2002) refer to as the accumulation of knowledge, education, work competence, skill, health, and psychometric evaluations. This can only be achieved through a high level of education and training. Human beings can learn, adapt, innovate and create; therefore, Harbison (1973) is of the view that consistent acquiring of knowledge, skills, and experiences are needed by the human capital to produce economic value for sustainable national development. Ogunleye et al. (2017) note that countries with significantly developed human capital enjoy several benefits such as reduced poverty, increased employment opportunities, and sustainable economic growth rate. On the other hand, it is no doubt that Nigeria and most other African countries have not achieved any of the SDGs (Dansabo, 2018). This is because, according to Eze (2017), Nigeria lacks qualified people to develop and implement alternative technologies due to a poor education system, brain drain, conflicts, and unrealistic government policies (Babalola, 2018).

The Education For All (EFA) agenda states that every child, youth, and adult must benefit from educational opportunities which should meet their basic learning needs. Thus, Boyi (2013) says that education must be attained to a high standard to achieve sustainable national development of

any state or society. Fafunwa (1974), on the other hand, argues that the knowledge given to the younger generation which enables them to develop positive attitudes is an evidence of quality education in any society. Amaele (2011) also sees education as the all-embracing development of an individual by using adequate techniques and methods according to his or her ability and area of interest so that he or she is up-to-date and knowledgeable to increase the development of society. Education trains the minds of the people of society making them relevant, useful, and able to contribute to the labour market and in turn national development. Babalola (2003) has based his argument on the reason behind educational investment in human capital, which implies that the new generations must be given important contents of the education that has been accumulated by the previous generations; that existing knowledge should be taught to the new generations to develop new products, processes, and methods; and that creative skills should be imbibed in people to develop new ideas, products, and methods. To back up this argument, Adedeji and Bamidele (2003) have developed three elements of education, which are:

- **Access to education** by citizens enhances human capital development and provides access to a large number of the people in society, which is needed for a sustained economic growth.
- **Content of education** is determined by the educational curriculum used in institutions through schooling and training. Education exposes human capital to various ideas, knowledge, skills, and attitudes that cut across all spheres of life.
- **The openness of education to meet the demand of the labour market** explains that students must be adaptive to the demands of public and private employment. However, Boateng (2002) argues that education services do not meet demands of the labour market.

Education policies are not related to labour market requirements nor individual student interests.

To achieve the elements of education, educationists are striving to catch up with globalization to equip students to be relevant globally. Centuries before now and sadly still in Nigeria presently, the 3Rs existed portraying Reading, Writing and Arithmetic, which produced graduates who were near useless and incapable of coping with the changing demands of the labour market (Egbefo, 2012). The curriculum of this education system was strange to the Nigerian environment; it was devoid of vocational and technical subjects that encourage self-reliance, technological development, and national efficiency. Fortunately, on the other hand, the 4Cs have been developed by the Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21, 2015b) and consist of Communication, Critical Thinking, Collaboration, and Creativity. This is aimed at making education relevant, equipping students to be innovative, enhancing their communication, and building skills in collaboration with others to create jobs for better economic growth (Harshbarger, 2016).

1.4 Describing the Problem

The 17 SDGs, especially SDG 4 of providing education, were a step to overhaul the failure of the Millennium Development Goals to be achieved specifically in most African countries. The UN (2017) acknowledged that the world failed to meet the MDGs of achieving universal education in 2015. Estimates by UNESCO (2015) show that 122 million youths globally are illiterate, 59 million children were out of school, 1 in 5 of these children had dropped out, and 2 in 5 had never entered a classroom. The UN recognises that this gap must be closed. The UN SDGs Agenda is timely and laudable, however attaining these goals in Nigeria might not be a reality if there are no sufficient public investments and improvement in governance (Adegbami and Adesanmi, 2018).

Even though Nigeria is called a developing nation; in real terms, the nation has not started any development process compared to other nations that got independence in the 1960s.

The purpose of education in Nigeria has remained undefined. Funding of Nigeria's education sector has not gone anywhere close to UNESCO's (2015) recommendation of 26% budgetary allocation. In fact, the highest the Nigerian government has come close to in terms of budgetary allocation to the education sector is 10.7% in 2015². This explains why there is weak accountability and governance structures in the education sector. Nigeria has institutions and the legal framework for corporate governance strategies in organisations but lacks the human capital to enforce these policies and monitor compliance (Adekoya, 2011; Osemeke and Adgebite, 2016). Also, most school board directors comprise of people with different professions who have diverse interpretations of how corporate governance is practiced which affects the school performance (Ozili, 2021).

A report by NESG (2018) states that the conflicting regulatory laws and lack of a clear vision for the Nigerian education sector reflect in corporate governance failures in schools (Adekoya, 2011), unfavourable business environments (Letza, 2017), and the high number of graduates at different levels who cannot compete globally regardless of their high levels talent and effort. In 2018, the Nigerian education sector was valued at USD7.5million, employing 2.7 million people, accounting for just 3.5% of Nigeria's total employment, contributing a meagre 2.1% to the nation's GDP and very poorly -1% to GDP growth (NESG, 2018). Part of this challenge is the shortage of well-trained and qualified teachers as well as infrastructure. Nigeria has barely 570,000 teachers to cater for over 23 million students enrolled in schools.

² Olufemi, A. (2020) 'Buhari's 2021 budget share for education is Nigeria's lowest in 10 years', *Premium Times*, 4 October. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/422829-buharis-2021-budget-share-for-education-is-nigerias-lowest-in-10-years.html> (Accessed: 18 August 2021).

For the SDGs to be achieved and sustained, Rieckmann et al. (2017) agree that it is the responsibility of the Federal Government to set up policies and laws to take ownership and establish national frameworks, policies, and measures for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda and ensure strict adherence by all concerned. It is also the responsibility of the Government to lead reforms of Teacher-Training Colleges and Institutes followed by complete reforms in the education sector. Good governance sets and acts on policies that yield the desired positive results irrespective of whether the governed disagree with the results. Government policies on education in Nigeria are often integrated into the national development plans and are developed from all sectors of the Nigerian economy. According to Babalola (2018), these policies were developed after Nigeria's independence in 1960 and some of them include the National Development Plans (1962-1986); the National Perspective and Rolling Plans (1990-2009); the Nigerian Vision 20, 2020 (2010-2020); the NEEDS and SEEDS with the 10 Year Education Sector Strategic Plan (2005-2015); the Jonathan's Administration's National Transformation Agenda (2010-2015); and the Five Point Change Agenda of the Buhari's administration (2015-2020). These policies show that Nigeria commits to legal, policy, and methodological frameworks. However, Osunwusi (2020) insists that some of these frameworks exhibit more glamour in terms of documentation rather than in their practicability. For example, Chapter II of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999, as amended, deals with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy which imposes obligations on the State in terms of educational, cultural, political, foreign policy, socio-economic, and environmental objectives. Section 18 of the 1999 Constitution instructs the State to direct its policy to: provide equal and adequate educational opportunities at all levels; advance science and technology; eradicate illiteracy; and provide free, compulsory adult literacy programmes, universal primary and university education.

A look at the Finnish system of education shows that even though there are predominantly government-owned schools with very few private schools; these private schools are still largely funded by the government. OECD (2013) reports that 97.6% funding of Finnish private schools are provided by the government. Unfortunately, the Nigerian government does not support private schools especially in terms of funding and infrastructural facilities³. The students in Nigerian schools presently will become graduates in future, thereby contributing their skills and talents to meet the demands of the labour market regardless of whether their education was in government-owned or private schools. It is the same society these students will contribute to when they become graduates. In his presentation, Afejuku (2017, para.14) said:

‘Our big men in government are too narrow-minded, too self-centred ...to think of positive and big education dreams of our country. Or how should we interpret our President’s total lack of reference to education...? His deliberate silence on the current state of education in modern Nigeria spoke loud volumes.’

According to Babalola (2018, p.3), the Nigerian government continues to experience ‘policy somersault’ which is manifested in corruption, lack of sufficient human capital, inconsistent policies, unrealistic promises, and misplacement of priorities. It is believed that for policies to achieve the desired results, they need to be consistent over time (World Bank, 2017). These government policies are not feasible considering the short period spent in office thereby making it difficult for the leaders to properly review their outcomes within the different sectors. The unstable economic and political conditions in Nigeria make it difficult to reach sustainable agreements. The government claims to be committed to providing progressive education, but it treats teachers with

³ Afejuku, T. (2017) ‘Thoughts on funding private education in modern Nigeria’, *The Guardian*, 19 October. Available at: <https://guardian.ng/issue/thoughts-on-funding-private-education-in-modern-nigeria/> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

disrespect. The government appoints low quality people into institutions and these uneducated people are not able to set good examples and policies for the national life (Afejuku, 2017).

A major issue that has plagued the Nigerian education sector is the shortage of teachers. Research has shown that there is an inconsistency between the demand for teachers and the supply of teachers (Ibidapo-Obe, 2007). Teachers are the backbone of the education system; therefore, professional education requires careful planning and execution. Amadi (2012) states that some teachers have not met the minimum requirement set by the National Policy on Education because of lack of incentives, lack of motivation, and brain drain. Dike (2002) also notes that the continued fall in the standard of education in Nigeria is caused by the shortage of teachers needed in schools. Sadly, most teachers do not even possess the minimum certificate, which is the NCE. This accounts for the poor performance of students in external examinations (Odeleye, 2012). To achieve a sustained economic growth, it is important to ensure that people with the right knowledge and skills are in political leadership and that there is enough time for those in power to implement policies and credibly deliver on promises made to citizens beyond the political cycle (Babalola, 2018).

1.5 Scope and Significance of Enquiry

Sustainable economic growth is channelled towards nation-building. According to Carmeli and Schaubroeck (2005), nation-building is derived from the accumulation of human capital and it entails higher income, better education, less poverty, freedom, and more equitable opportunities. Human development is a change model that focuses on creating an atmosphere in which people can develop their full potentials, lead productive and creative lives, and become the real wealth of nations (Mbachu and Dorgu, 2014). The quality and quantity of human capital are mainly achieved through education to build the skills and competencies needed for the workforce (Obanya, 2009).

Education is seen as an investment against poverty; therefore, human capacity is only developed when the school curriculum is functional and responsive.

This research will be based on formal education and will use employers, teachers, students, curriculum, managers, school environment in secondary schools as the foundation. Edet and Beyin (2018) give three definitions of the context of education. The first being defined as acquiring knowledge, skills, and attitudes from daily life experiences; another description of education refer to it as the acquisition of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experiences from institutions of learning; and yet another defining education as an organised learning activity between individuals. This explains that the programme, teacher, and student must be within a learning environment. Edet and Beyin (2018) further explain that the formal education is highly organised, rigid, and uses specific criteria to be admitted into the system. Education in Nigeria is only done through the government or its recognized and accredited agencies, where examinations are carried out, and certificates issued at the end of the learning programme. Another justification for this study is that formal education at the secondary level is broader compared to university education because while university education focuses on specific skills and training for the labour market; secondary education builds basic skills in the students for more advanced skills and lifelong learning (Kashefpakdel et al. 2018) so that even if these students do not get a university education they will still be able to fit into the labour market.

Lastly, the researcher justifies this study because secondary education has little or no research or funding support from the government. Out of the Nigerian government's budgetary allocation to the education sector, 90% of this goes to university education and just 10% to basic education (Ahmed, 2015). The researcher, therefore, argues for a more balanced budgetary allocation to all facets of the education sector.

This study will be significant to the students, teachers, school management, government and its agencies, and the general society. The students will benefit from this study because it will reveal to the government and various educational institutions on the type and nature of curriculum that should be adopted and implemented to prepare the students with the desired knowledge and skill to fit properly into society. The study will serve as a guide to teachers and other educational instructors to adopt the right methodology during the process of teaching and learning. The study will provide a policy framework for schools' management to provide the right management strategy and teaching and learning environment for teachers and students. The study will provide a legal and policy framework to the government to effectively and efficiently fund the education sector as the foundation for a sustained economic growth. Lastly, the general society will benefit from this study as it will provide the basis for which a trained human capital is developed and integrated into society to achieve sustainable economic growth and development.

Table 1 Learning Objectives for the SDG 4 ‘Quality Education’

The table below gives cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural learning objectives for the SDG 4 – ‘quality education’. The significance of this table is referred to in subsequent sections of the study.

Cognitive learning	Socio-emotional learning	Behavioural learning
The learner understands the important role of education and lifelong learning opportunities for all (formal, informal, and non-formal learning) as the main drivers of sustainable development, for improving people’s lives, and in achieving the SDGs.	The learner is able to raise awareness of the importance of quality education for all, a humanistic and holistic approach to education, education for sustainable development, and related approaches.	The learner is able to contribute to facilitating and implementing quality education for all, education for sustainable development and related approaches at different levels.
The learner understands education as a public good, a global common good, a fundamental human right, and a basis for guaranteeing the realization of other rights.	The learner is able through participatory methods to motivate and empower others to demand and use educational opportunities.	The learner is able to promote gender equality in education.
The learner knows about inequality in access to and attainment of education, and about reasons for a lack of equitable access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities.	The learner is able to recognise the intrinsic value of education and to analyse and identify their own learning needs in their personal development.	The learner is able to openly demand and support the development of policies, promoting free, equitable, and quality education for all, ESD and related approaches as well as aiming at safe, accessible, and inclusive educational facilities.

The learner understands that education can help create a more sustainable, equitable, and peaceful world.	The learner is able to recognise the importance of their skills for improving their life, in particular for employment and entrepreneurship.	The learner is able to promote the empowerment of young people.
	The learner is able to engage personally with education for sustainable development.	The learner is able to use all opportunities for their education throughout their life and to apply the acquired knowledge in everyday situations to promote sustainable development.

Source: UNESCO (2017, p.18)

1.6 UN Reports on the link between SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 8 (Sustainable Economic Growth)

It is worthy to note that Nigeria resolved to declare January 24 every year as the ‘International Day of Education’ and this was adopted by the UN General Assembly⁴. The resolution acknowledges ‘the importance of education for achieving sustainable development... and that education plays a key role in building sustainable and resilient societies and contributes to the achievement of all of the other SDGs’ (Agency Report, 2018, para. 4 and 8). It also recognises that inclusive and equitable quality education at all levels increases the productivity of individuals and strengthens

⁴ Agency Report (2018) ‘UN adopts Nigeria’s resolution on education’, *Premium Times*, 4 December. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/298955-un-adopts-nigerias-resolution-on-education.html> (Accessed: 17 August 2021).

the potential for economic growth, develops the skills needed for decent work, and develops the professional skills needed for sustainable development.

Reports have emphasized the impact of education, particularly at the secondary level, on workers' productivity and productive capabilities (ILO, 2014) and higher earnings (UNESCO, 2014); the importance of education as a determinant of knowledge enhancement and entrepreneurship (World Bank, 2013) both in wage and non-wage sector – wages in the form of monetary compensation, and non-wages or non-monetary as seen in working conditions, facilities available at work, and the sociability of the hours. Foreign direct investment is positively associated with achievements in education (World Bank, 2015). Rising educational attainment shows that enrolment in secondary education lowers skill shortages (World Bank, 2007) as basic skills are developed at this level. Education of the youth increases their opportunities to be employable, stay healthy, and participate fully in society⁵. Reports from UNIDO (2013) also state that the education of youths emphasizes marketable skills and specialised high-level training to meet demands from firms.

The reports identify two main groups of challenges. The first concerns the gap between supply and demand for skills, with a growing gap between the skills acquired in education and the nature of jobs available (ILO, 2014). The second group of the challenge is on youths who leave school unprepared for work or cannot convert educational achievements into paid jobs (UNFPA, 2014). Many reports have advocated for higher investment in education to curb these challenges and stimulate innovation and economic growth (UNFPA, 2014). It recommended that there should be an investment to increase school enrolment among economically and socially deprived households, raise educational attainment to at least the lower-secondary level, and adopt education

⁵UNESCO (2014). 'Teaching and Learning: achieving quality for all; EFA global monitoring report, 2013-2014'. [ebook] Paris: UNESCO, pp.1-496. Available at: <<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000225660>> [Accessed 17 July 2021].

policies to improve low-performing schools by offering a quality learning experience (World Bank, 2015). Other reports suggest an emphasis on high-level, specialised training, with more formalised on-the-job training and vocational education, with closer interaction between educational institutions and the industry in the form of apprenticeships⁶. World Bank (2007) notes that the balance or sequence of education policies depend on the state of a country's education system, level of development, overall development priorities, and the priorities of its young people. Linking growth and jobs to education at the macroeconomic level, WTO (2014) reports that economic growth is a necessary condition for development – which is seen in countries with improved health, educational attainment, living standards, and poverty reduction.

Economic changes have pushed for improvement in educational approaches and content. Companies now demand soft skills and focus on the importance of work-based learning in addition to the formal education system (UNESCO, 2012; 2014). Economic downturns, on the other hand, affect the educational development of a child – especially when the parents lose their jobs. UNDP (2014) reports that long-term unemployment is a serious threat to a child's education. Market distortions are also caused by high unemployment and skills mismatch (ILO, 2014; World Bank, 2013).

Goal 8 of the SDGs is to promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all (UNESCO, 2017, p.6). This goal aims to sustain per capita economic growth in keeping with national circumstances and, in particular, at least 7% GDP growth per annum in the least developed countries; achieve higher levels of economic

⁶UNIDO (2013) *Industrial Development Report. Sustaining Employment Growth: The Role of Manufacturing and Structural Change*. Vienna: UNIDO.

productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including through a focus on high value-added and labour intensive sectors.

Table 2 Learning Objectives for the SDG 8 ‘Sustainable Economic Growth’

The table below gives cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural learning objectives for the SDG 8 – ‘sustainable economic growth’. The significance of this table is referred to in subsequent sections of the study.

Cognitive learning	Socio-emotional learning	Behavioural learning
The learner understands the concepts of inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work, including the advancement of gender parity and equality, and knows about alternative economic models and indicators.	The learner is able to discuss economic models and future visions of the economy and society critically and to communicate them in public spheres.	The learner is able to engage with new visions and models of a sustainable, inclusive economy and decent work.
The learner has knowledge about the distribution of formal employment rates per sector, informal employment, and unemployment in different world regions or nations, and which social groups are especially affected by unemployment.	The learner is able to collaborate with others to demand fair wages, equal pay for equal work, and labour rights from politicians and their employers.	The learner is able to facilitate improvements related to unfair wages, unequal pay for equal work, and bad working conditions.
The learner understands the relation between employment and economic growth and knows about other moderating factors	The learner is able to understand how one’s consumption affects the working conditions of others in the global economy.	The learner is able to develop and evaluate ideas for sustainability-driven innovation and entrepreneurship.

like a growing labour force or new technologies that substitute jobs.		
The learner understands how low and decreasing wages for the labour force and very high wages and profits of managers and owners or shareholders are leading to inequalities, poverty, and civil unrest.	The learner is able to identify their rights and clarify their needs and values related to work.	The learner is able to plan and implement entrepreneurial projects.
The learner understands how innovation, entrepreneurship, and job creation can contribute to decent work and a sustainability-driven economy and the decoupling of economic growth from the impacts of natural hazards and environmental degradation.	The learner is able to develop a vision and plans for their own economic life based on an analysis of their competencies and contexts.	The learner is able to develop criteria and make responsible consumption choices as a means to support fair working conditions and efforts to decouple production from the impact of natural hazards and environmental degradation.

Source: UNESCO (2017, p.26)

1.7 Research Objectives

This research will aim to explore the relationship between education and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The study will focus on middle/low income private secondary schools because they provide learning objectives for Sustainable Development Goals 4 and 8, they have the greatest untapped potential, the largest proportion of students, and therefore can make the biggest difference. In so doing, the study will seek:

- a. To explore how middle/low income private secondary schools in Nigeria obtain and use funding to influence sustainable economic growth;
- b. To explore and examine how management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools in Nigeria influence labour market demand;
- c. To explore how school management practices influence education quality and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria;
- d. To outline ways in which teaching and learning aids and methods can prepare learners to be drivers of sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

1.8 Research Questions

This research thesis will seek to answer the overarching question – How well do education providers in Nigeria align provision with the Sustainable Development Goal of quality and access to education? This holistic research question is further broken down into four sub-questions:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence sustainable economic growth in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of sustainable economic growth in Nigeria?

1.9 Outline of Thesis

The thesis contains nine chapters showing the introduction, the education system in Nigeria, review of related literature, conceptual framework, research methodology, presentation and analysis of results, discussion of research findings, contributions to practice, summary and conclusion.

Chapter 2: The System of Education in Nigeria

This chapter begins with a background knowledge of Nigeria using a map to illustrate the geographical area. It goes on to discuss the history of education, organisation, and challenges from the pre-colonial era to present day system of education. The chapter further outlines the journey of educational planning showing a list of the different government policies on education, their provisions and relevance.

Chapter 3: Review of Literature Review

The third chapter is literature review of the study. The chapter is divided into three parts. Part one gives a detailed discussion of the concept and role of education for SEG in Nigeria. Part two discusses sustainability, theories explaining the schools as a business venture, and school management practices for sustainability. Part three is more detailed as it narrows the research problem to the Nigerian context. Part three also gives a theoretical framework of the study using endogenous economic growth theory of Romer (1989b) and Lucas (1988).

Chapter 4: Conceptual Framework

Chapter 4 gives a discourse of the constructs used for this research. The antecedents are education and human capital. The indices used in this chapter are the research constructs – funding, government policies, teaching and learning aids and methods, labour market demand, and quality of education. The discussion of this constructs lead to the outcome which is sustainable economic growth. The chapter also shows the relationships between the research constructs used and also discusses the concept of entrepreneurship in more detail.

Chapter 5: Research Methodology

This chapter is in four parts – the foundation phase, pre-field phase, field phase, and the reporting phase. It begins with an elaborate exploration of the research design which shows the philosophical consideration, approach, techniques of data collection and analysis. It also gives a step-by-step approach on the time horizon, researcher's role in the data collection process, justification for the research method, and ethical consideration based on the University's guidelines.

Chapter 6: Presentation and Analysis of Results

This chapter presents and analyses the quantitative and qualitative data. The chapter is divided into two parts. Part one shows an analysis and presentation of the quantitative data gotten from questionnaires. The survey data shows responses of the teachers and management to the questionnaires. Descriptive statistics is used for the data analysis section and presents the findings using tables and graphs to give an understanding of the quantitative data. Part two shows an analysis and presentation of the qualitative data using the proposed themes (discussed in Chapter 5). The qualitative data is gotten from interviews, observations, and document review. Thematic

analysis is used to present the research findings using a coding template developed by the researcher and the recurring code extracts which are categorised into themes.

Chapter 7: Discussion of Research Findings

A model is developed by the researcher showing the link education and the outcome of SEG. The themes used in this chapter are quality of education, problems facing education, government policies, labour market demand, teaching and learning aids and activities, access to education, problems facing human capital availability, and management policies. This chapter shows how data from the surveys, interviews, focus groups, documents, and observations are triangulated to give a full understanding of the themes linking back to the literature.

Chapter 8: Contributions of Findings to Practice

This chapter is discussed in three parts. The first part highlights the way forward for Nigeria's transition from the old to the new economy. Part two discusses important lessons from the Finnish education system which can be adopted in Nigeria. The third part reviews methodological contributions of the findings to practice in Nigerian secondary schools.

Chapter 9: Summary and Conclusion

This chapter begins by giving an overview of the research questions stated in chapter one and how these questions have been answered based on the literature, results from the findings and their contributions to knowledge and practice. The chapter also summarises and gives a recap of the research study, exposes problems encountered during the course of the study and gives direction for future research work.

CHAPTER TWO

THE SYSTEM OF EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

2.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter delves into the system of education in Nigeria giving a background knowledge of the journey of educational planning in terms of educational policies and their provisions from pre-independence to present, and the historical perspective of education – the indigenous system, Islamic education, and the formal European-style education. The researcher goes on to discuss the organisation of the Nigerian education system up to the 9-3-4 system currently used by schools and the challenges facing the Nigerian education system.

2.2 Background of Nigeria

The current administrative system of government in Nigeria is divided into the Federal Capital Territory – Abuja and 36 states. Nigeria’s population is estimated to be over 200 million⁷, split mainly between Christians (47%) and Muslims (52%). The majority of Muslims are in the north of the country and Christians in the south. Nigeria comprises over 250 ethnic groups. However, Hausa and Fulani (29%), Yoruba (21%), Igbo (18%), Ijaw (10%), Kanuri (4%), Ibibio (3.5%) and Tiv (2.5%) are the largest and politically influential⁸.

⁷The World Bank (2022) *Nigeria – Population, total – World Bank Open Data*. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?locations=NG> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

⁸Mustapha, A. R. (2005) *Ethnic Structure, Inequality and Governance of the Public Sector in Nigeria*. Centre for Research on Inequality, Human Security and Ethnicity. CRISE Working Paper No. 18. Available at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/57a08c97ed915d3cfd0014aa/wp18.pdf> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

Nigeria's economy is the largest in Africa⁹ with Lagos being the commercial centre and leading technology hub. Having a youthful, rapidly growing population, Nigeria has the potential to become a global economic powerhouse. However, the nation's economy continues to underperform. Policy uncertainty, underinvestment in education have impeded productivity¹⁰.

Figure 1 Nigeria at a glance¹¹

The figure below shows the map of Nigeria.

⁹Economy size ranking as of 2019. World Bank Data Bank, 'GDP (current US\$)', Accessed: 10 October, 2021.

¹⁰World Bank, *Jumpstarting Inclusive Growth: Unlocking the Productive Potential of Nigeria's People and Resource Endowments*, Fall 2019.

¹¹ Source: CRS map with data from State Department and Esri. Fact information from CIA World Factbook and the International Monetary Fund (IMF); 2020 data unless otherwise indicated. GDP per capita is adjusted to international dollars based on purchasing power parity. Available at: <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/RL33964.pdf> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

Table 3 Facts about Nigeria¹²

The table below gives a breakdown of major facts about Nigeria.

Time Zone: Nigeria Standard Time, which is Greenwich Mean Time plus one hour	Capital: Abuja
Size: 923,768 sq. km More than twice the size of California	Infant Mortality Rate: 60 deaths/1,000 live births
Median Age / Life Expectancy: 18.6 years / 60 years	
Natural Resources: Natural gas, petroleum, tin, lead, zinc, coal, iron ore. Oil reserves constitute 36.2 billion barrels	Life Expectancy: 59.3 years
Population: 214 million; 2.5% growth rate	Prevalence of HIV: 1.5% (2018)
Languages: English (official), Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo (Igbo), Fulani, over 500 other local languages	GDP Per Capita / Growth Rate: \$1,168 / 2.2% (2019)
Religions: Muslim 54%, Roman Catholic 11%, other Christian 35%, other 1% (2018)	Key exports: petroleum and petroleum products 95%, cocoa, rubber (2012)
Literacy: 62% (71% male, 53% female) (2015)	External Debt: \$40.2 billion (2017)
Government budget: The central government of Nigeria had expenditures of US\$21.8 billion and revenues of US\$20.5 billion, resulting in a budget deficit of six percent. The tax authorities face the challenge of tax evasion. This is caused by complaints about corruption and the poor quality of services.	

Nigeria gained independence from Britain in 1960 and it is a Federal Republic operating a Presidential system of government with 36 states and a Federal Capital Territory in Abuja¹³. The Nigerian constitution provides for a separation of powers between the three branches of

¹² Source: CRS map with data from State Department and Esri. Fact information from CIA World Factbook and the International Monetary Fund (IMF); 2020 data unless otherwise indicated. GDP per capita is adjusted to international dollars based on purchasing power parity. Available at: <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/RL33964.pdf> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

¹³Congressional Research Service (2020) *Nigeria: Current Issues and U.S. Policy*. Available at: <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/RL33964.pdf> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

government: a strong executive, an elected legislature, and an independent judiciary. The political structure of Nigeria is similar to the United States; it has a bicameral legislature with 109 members in the House of Senate and 360 members in the House of Representatives (Blanchard and Husted, 2019)¹⁴. The President, Legislators, and Governors are directly elected by the citizens for a four-year tenure. The country was ruled by the military after independence before it transitioned to civilian rule in 1999¹⁵. Nigeria is known as the giant of Africa, not only because of its size but mainly because of its political and economic function on the continent. South Africa, which used to be Africa's largest economy has been overtaken by Nigeria as one of the world's major sources of crude oil (Kwanga, 2015). Globally, Nigeria has the fastest growing population and is expected to overtake the United States by 2050 with a population of 410 million (United Nations Economic and Social Affairs, 2017). Despite the nation being rich in oil reserves, it remains highly underdeveloped. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2017), limited infrastructural development and economic growth have become the effects of Nigeria's poor governance and corruption among the citizens. The population is among the world's poorest, and there is a highly unequal distribution of the nation's wealth (Beaumont and Abrak, 2018). The number of people living on less than \$1.90 per day has grown to about 87 million. This has made Nigeria the country with the largest population living in extreme poverty (Kharas et al., 2018).

Decades of Nigeria's economic mismanagement, instability, and corruption have hindered sustainable investment in education and other social services. In the rural parts of Nigeria,

¹⁴ Congressional Research Service (2020) *Nigeria: Current Issues and U.S. Policy*. Available at: <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/RL33964.pdf> (Accessed: 17 July 2021).

¹⁵ Implementation of the "federal character" remains uneven. See Leila Demarest, Arnim Langer, and Ukoha Ukiwo, "Nigeria's Federal Character Commission (FFC): a critical appraisal," *Oxford Development Studies* (2020).

language has created a problem concerning education. The medium of instruction used in the rural areas which is the indigenous language has made it difficult to access instructional materials in those languages. In 2018, Nigeria's adult literacy rate was 62.02% on average, with a higher rate for men (71.26%) than that of women (52.66%) (UNESCO, 2020). The country provides free, government-supported education, however certain ethnic groups and the handicapped are not properly taken care of. Because of the decaying educational institutions and ill-prepared graduates, the Nigeria National Planning Commission (2004) described the country's education as dysfunctional.

2.3 Historical Perspective of Education in Nigeria

Education in Nigeria has passed through two stages – the colonial and post-independence eras. Before the establishment of the colonial government, Islam was deep rooted in the religious belief and educational orientation of the people in the northern area and they had a uniform Qur'anic education policy (Ozigi and Ocho, 1981). On the other hand, the southern parts had their own traditional form of education based on the culture and tradition of each ethnic group (Taiwo, 1980). The curricula was informal and comprised developing the child's physical and intellectual skill, character, vocational training, sense of communal living, and appreciation of the community's cultural heritage (Fafunwa, 2004). Historically, education was mainly faith-based. It was a medium used by the Christian missionaries to convert the average Nigerian to Christianity by setting up schools and developing indigenous languages into writing. The aim of education as given by the Christian missionaries was to enable recipients to learn to read the Bible in English and the local language, gardening, agriculture, and train local school masters and clergymen (Imam, 2012). The curriculum at the time was mainly based on indoctrination and brainwashing, rather than an avenue for self-realization and intellectual growth. As of 1990, there were three distinct education systems

in Nigeria. These are the indigenous system, Quranic schools, and formal European-style education which includes public and private schools.

In the **indigenous system**, education was acquired in age-based schools in which mature men instructed groups of young boys in community responsibilities (Osuji, 2004) and children learned farming skills, duties of adulthood, and other tasks. Indigenous crafts like leatherwork and traditional medicine were acquired through an apprenticeship in which the trainee provided service to the teacher for some years after which they were fit to be on their own. This era did not need any regulation by the government unless training included the need for a license.

Islamic education was practiced in Quranic schools with religious learning based on the Arabic alphabet, grammar, syntax, arithmetic, logic, rhetoric, and theology. Children between the ages of three and five were taught some chapters of the Quran by a local religious teacher. Formal Muslim schools were established based on European standards and set up in all major Nigerian cities especially Kano strictly for children of the rich and devout who wanted their children to have the new and European learning but within a firmly religious context.

Formal European-style education was brought to Nigeria in the mid-nineteenth century and focused mainly on examinations. After the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern parts of Nigeria, there were 59 government and 91 mission primary schools in the South. In 1914, there were 1,100 primary school pupils in the North compared to 35,700 in the South. Lord Frederick Lugard (the first governor of the northern and southern colonies) set up a school inspectorate in 1916 to inspect buildings, discipline, adequacy of teaching staff, and rankings of the examination results. The system gave way to the three-tiered systems of primary, secondary, and higher education in 1950 (Udey, et al., 2009).

The **formal school system** entailed optional but free education at any level. The government switched to this American system of education in 1982 despite the British model of education which was in use. The formal education system is the 6-3-3-4 style, which is six years in primary school, three years in junior secondary school, three years in senior secondary school, and four years in higher education leading to a bachelor's degree in any field.

Primary education begins at age six and lasts for six years. The curriculum includes subjects like English, mathematics, social studies, agriculture, home economics. The curriculum was reviewed in 2008 to further include ICT, French, and civic education. English language is the official medium of instruction. Until 2004, students had to sit for the Primary School-Leaving Certificate examination as criteria to graduate. However, the examination has now been abolished making the Certificate only awarded based on continuous assessment.

Secondary education lasts for six years and is divided into two: three years in junior secondary school and three years in senior secondary school. The junior secondary school has two streams: pre-vocational and academic. Students are awarded the Junior Secondary School Certificate after completion of the junior stage. This certificate is necessary to move into the senior secondary school, technical college, or out of school vocational training centres. The senior secondary stage lasts for three years in which every learner takes eight subjects from the curriculum. The Senior School Certificate is issued by the West African Examination Council and/or the National Examination Council after completion of the senior secondary stage. The SSC is one of the requirements for undergraduate admission into a Nigerian university. Another requirement for entry into a Nigerian university is the Universities Matriculation Examination (UME). This

Certificate replaced the West African General Certificate of Education Ordinary and Advanced levels (GCE 'O' and 'A' levels) in 1989.

2.4 The Journey of Educational Planning in Nigeria

According to Akpan (2018), education is necessary for the social, economic, technological, and political transformation of the nation. For this transformation to take place in the nation, education needs to be properly planned by considering the needs of the citizenry, the social, economic and technological changes, and the impact of globalization on the growth and development of the country. Akpan (2018) also proves that educational planning involves formulating policies and coordinating programmes and activities that will lead to the accomplishment of the set educational goals and objectives. It also includes budgeting, financial planning, and human resource planning. Educational planning aims to make education more effective and efficient to respond to the needs and goals of the students and society (Adepoju, 2000; Akpan, 2000).

Educational planning in Nigeria began in the colonial era when the British government managed the nation's affairs (Fabunmi, 2005). Education then was founded by the missionaries who brought Christianity to Africa. By introducing the western style of education, the aim was to train students to act as interpreters and clerks for the missionaries. The education ordinances controlled and administered education in the colonial era before Nigeria became a sovereign state in 1960 (Akpan, 2018).

Table 4 The Journey of Education Planning in Nigeria

The table below gives a breakdown of the journey of education planning in Nigeria showing its provisions from the 1887 Education Ordinance era to the 2016-2019 strategic plan for education.

Journey of educational planning in Nigeria	What?	Provisions?
The 1887 Education Ordinance	The first education policy in Nigeria. Formed the basis for educational planning and development in Nigeria (Fabunmi, 2005).	The Central Board of Education; appointment of inspector of school education officers; empowerment of the governor to open and run schools; conditions for grants-in-aid were based on subjects taught and the degree of excellence in schools; classification of teachers' certificates; and powers given to the Board of Education to grant scholarships for secondary and technical education.
The Phelps-Stokes Commission Report	Established in 1920 by the American Baptized Foreign missionary society and funded by the Phelps-Stokes fund with the main aim of studying the needs and resources of Africa regarding the quantity and quality of education provided for the people (Akpan, 2018).	Primary education to last between six and eight years with a curriculum based on hygiene, agriculture, handicraft and a study of the local environment; secondary education to last for six years after which the graduates will be competent to search for paid jobs in various fields; vocational higher education which was to provide vocational courses aimed at producing

		higher vocational education.
The 1942 Education Plan	Initiated in 1942 and focused more on the provision of financial support, expansion, control, and administration of education (Osokoya, 2010).	To provide better service conditions for teachers employed by the mission to have better-trained staff; to provide financial assistance to mission and other voluntary educational bodies; and to control the expansion of education within financial limits.
The 1999 Education Plan: The UBE	Launched in 1999 but signed into law in 2004. The UBE Act 2004 included Early Child Care Development and Education (ECCDE), primary and junior secondary. The federal, state and local governments had the responsibility to finance the basic education, with the federal government contributing 2% of its consolidated fund (Akpan, 2000).	To enable the learner acquire the knowledge, skills, and attitude that will contribute to the development of the society; to provide free, compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian child of school-going age; eradicate poverty; and to bridge the gap of educational imbalance in the country through the nine-year education plan.
The 4-year Strategic Plan for the Development of the	Launched by the FRN in 2012, focused on resolving the challenges	Strengthening the institutional management of education; access and

Education Sector, 2011-2015	that affected the Nigerian education system from playing its role in national development by reviewing curricula of the nine-year basic education, NPE, and teachers' training (Akpan, 2018).	equity; standard and quality assurance; teacher education and development; technical and vocational education and training; and funding, partnership, and resource mobilization.
The 2016-2019 Strategic Plan for Education	Tagged "Education for Change" focused on strengthening the educational institutions and creating innovative strategies to remodel the education sector. This plan aimed at repositioning the education system in Nigeria to play a central role in the Federal Government's philosophy of change (Abdulsalam, 2016).	To provide life-long learning opportunities for all; to provide the needed direction to ensure inclusive and equitable education; to promote public-private partnership and collaboration with donors to fill funding gaps; to provide the type of education in Nigeria needed to meet the target of the SDGs; to provide functional education as a step out of youth unemployment; to recruit quality teachers in sufficient quantity; to ensure quality, there will be opportunities for re-training and development of existing teachers; to make the school environment more learner-friendly; and ensure effective collaboration and coordination of educational inputs and activities to build
		and sustain adequate human capital for national development.

2.5 Organisation of the Nigerian Education System

Education which is an instrument of change has been a product of evolution through series of historical developments in the Nigerian education policy. As a public enterprise, it has witnessed active participation and intervention by the government (FRN, 1981; Amaghionyeodiwe and Osinubi, 2006). The Nigerian National Policy on Education which was formulated in 1977 aimed at achieving socio-economic, political, cultural, scientific, and technological development. In 1985, the objectives of this policy were geared towards access to free primary education, self-realization, and national efficiency (Anyanwu et al., 1999; Moja, 2000). The management of education in Nigeria is based on this Federal system. This means that some powers concerning educational delivery are delegated to the state and local governments while the basic education policy regarding structure, curriculum, and the school year is centrally determined. Education is administered by the three branches of government: primary education is controlled by the local government; secondary schools are controlled by the state government except for the unity schools which are controlled by the federal government. The unity schools are those established and run by the Federal Government.

Due to the shrinking economy in Nigeria, the development and expansion of the education system have been stalled. The reform process of the education system has been slowed down as a result of a reduction in the allocated expenditure. The reform agenda was established in 1972 and is based on the work of the National Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) to encourage, promote and coordinate educational research programmes in Nigeria. Presently, the most crucial strategy for the sustainable development of education is the UBE Scheme which was launched in 1999. However, its bill was passed into law in 2004. It aims to provide free education

at the primary school level and at the first three years of secondary school, and also to provide functional literacy programmes for adult illiterates.

Another reform agenda was implemented by the government in the 1980s and 1990s. This reform altered the structure of the secondary school system. The secondary school education was closely related to the British system which had GCE 'O' levels and then two years of GCE 'A' level courses. However, this system has been eliminated and replaced with three years of junior secondary and three years of senior secondary schooling. Junior School Certificate and/or Senior School Certificate are awarded at the end of the school depending on the category (Ibe, 2010). This adjustment in the reform also affected the secondary school curriculum thereby laying more emphasis on environmental and population studies, and science and technology. Junior secondary schools now offer both academic and pre-vocational subjects.

In 2008, a further adjustment and reform was made in the curriculum. A nine-year curriculum (9-3-4) was introduced in the education system. This was not to completely scrap the 6-3-3-4 system but to establish a more integrated curriculum that will cover the first nine years of school education. It was established by the Ministry of Education to act as a bridge between primary and secondary education and also provide the learner with a comprehensive education that includes ICT, French, and civic education at the end of the basic education system.

2.6 Challenges of the Nigerian Education System

Education plays an invaluable role in developing individuals and society. Many countries including Nigeria, take education as an instrument for the promotion of national development and social change (NPE, 2004). The administration and management of 21st century education in

Nigeria has experienced impressive milestones compared to the one hundred years of British colonial administrative rule of the country. These milestones are in national education policies, primary education, secondary education, the UBE, and institutional frameworks for regulating education. However, the Nigerian education system and its productivity in the 21st century have suffered some setbacks because of poor management of the education policies (Udey et al., 2009). Although the three levels of government (Local, State, and Federal Government) are responsible for managing and administering the education system; there is still crises as seen in low morale of teachers, low budgets, and poor human capital quality.

Nigeria is predicted to be economically one of the leading countries in the world or at least in Africa and blessed with economic resources and human assets. However, the instability of the government and increasing number of people living in poverty have damaged the quality of the education system (Amzat, 2010). Poverty has crippled the process of education and deprived people from getting proper access to education in Nigeria. It is seen to have a great impact on education and a high number of students struggle to study without any support from the government or their parents (Filmer and Pritchett, 1999, 2001). Unfortunately, the Nigerian government is yet to fully realise the power of education in developing and providing excellent human capital for the nation (Amzat, 2010). Xoe (1997) notes that poverty limits educational achievement because students in poor countries experience less education and lower levels of school enrolment.

To tackle illiteracy and accelerate growth, the Nigerian government stresses its commitment to providing good education for its people. But, the education system is more focused on theoretical knowledge instead of technical, vocational, and entrepreneurial education (Otive, 2007). Sustainability of the Nigerian education system has weakened because of strikes and riots which

frequently end up in closing down schools for countless months (Amzat, 2010). The nation suffers youth unemployment because the education system does not provide opportunities for transition from school to work, particularly for the poor (Enamiroro, 2007). The Nigerian education system should be based on local initiatives, local knowledge, resources, and institutions that are needed to attain development in the economy (Aletor, 2009). However, there is limited research, insufficient funding of research activities, and poor collaboration among investors, schools, research institutions, teachers and other researchers that should solve national problems (Sanubi and Akpotu, 2015).

Education remains a weapon for social and economic development of any nation. However, lack of commitment by the Nigerian government and breakdown of the education sector is caused by decay and lack of infrastructure in Nigerian schools and a shrinking government funding on education (IseOlorunkanmi et al., 2021). This breakdown of the system has caused many students to migrate to other countries in search of better education quality. Yaro (2008) says that students who migrate to other countries are in need of a better enabling environment, opportunity for improved education facilities, better living conditions, and access to better quality. Even though migrating to other countries has become much more complex recently; many students who aspire for better education still choose to study in other developed countries as opposed to Nigeria (Sjursen, 2000; Adu, 2019).

2.7 Summary

This chapter gave a contextual knowledge and evolution of the education system in Nigeria. The government policies on education were highlighted showing their provisions. The chapter further explored the formal school system – primary education, secondary education, and higher education

and training, the transition from the 6-3-3-4 system to the 9-3-4 system of education and the challenges faced in the Nigerian education system. In subsequent chapters, these government policies guiding the education sector will be discussed in more details in relation to the research objectives.

CHAPTER THREE

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

3.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter is divided into three parts. Part one provides an overview of previous research works on the concept of education for sustainable economic growth and discusses the role of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. It also examines human capital availability which is the core element to achieving economic growth. Part two goes on to discuss the concept of sustainability and its theories – CSR, stakeholder theory, and corporate sustainability – citing the school as a business venture. School management practices for sustainability are also highlighted. In part three, the research is more detailed – going on to give attention to the nature of Nigeria’s economic growth using entrepreneurship education as the basis. Entrepreneurship education should be a core curriculum in Nigerian educational institutions. This chapter further discusses empirical views and reports on economic growth as a basis for Nigeria’s development policy. Lastly, part three discusses the endogenous growth theory of Romer (1989b) and Lucas (1988). This theory explains human capital investment through education as a key factor for sustained economic growth.

PART ONE

3.2 Introduction

Education has been proven to provide the necessary human resources to develop and transform the economy of a nation (Afolabi and Loto, 2012). The necessary manpower for economic growth and advancement can only be achieved through quality education in schools as the products result in teachers, medical personnel, political leaders, accountants, and a list of other professionals. Despite

the gross lack of quality education in Nigeria which affects the rate of sustainable economic growth, Crawford (2014) has noted that the government has continued to make laudable efforts in improving the quality of education in schools. This has been achieved through the implementation of certain laws relating to education by the Nigerian government which include the implementation of compulsory education through the establishment and implementation of UBE Act 2004, National Policy on Education, UNICEF, the introduction of the TRCN Act of 2008, increase in the number of students' enrolment into primary and secondary education, the inauguration of the Presidential Task Force on education in 2011 and the USAID (Babalola, 2018).

Various studies have shown that there is a correlation between the quality of education and economic growth (Faraq and Taylor, 2011; Kawamoto, 2007; Wang and Wong, 2011; Nastase and Hodoroaba, 2010). Education plays a significant role in improving the human capital and the overall sustainable economic growth of Nigeria. Education, through the process of teaching and learning, helps people to develop and improve their knowledge, skills, and values, thereby making informed decisions that will be beneficial to themselves and others both now and in the future.

As shown by Ilechukwu et al. (2014), the whole essence of ESD is integrating the principles, practices, and values of sustainable development into all aspects of the education and learning process. According to the authors, this goal has been broken down into four major objectives:

- Providing support to achieve SDGs in countries through education.
- Encouraging greater quality in the teaching and learning process of ESD.
- Providing new opportunities and tools in countries to uphold education reform efforts for ESD.
- Networking, collaborating, and facilitating unity among stakeholders to achieve education for Sustainable Development.

ESD as stated by Illechukwu et al. (2014) identifies four major feats that it hopes to achieve: First, to achieve sustainable economic growth, existing education should be revamped across all levels. Educational processes are hoped to improve the content of what is taught, the teaching method, and the self/professional development of the students and those who have the responsibility of implementing education. Also, sustainable economic growth ensures a transformation in people's attitudes and values which is achieved through the development and improvement of basic education. As stated by the Association of African Universities (2009), improvement in basic education includes the quality of teaching, learning and infrastructure, and the host community. Furthermore, education for sustainable economic growth requires a population that makes a conscious effort in being aware of and understand social and economic practices relating to sustainability. Lastly, the economy needs a literate workforce who are sufficiently trained for roles in their different sectors. Training differs from education because it relates to a specific job role.

3.3 Role of Education for Sustainable Economic Growth

Schools provide education which is a continuous process that happens throughout a person's life. Therefore, Illechukwu et al. (2014) believe that the formal, non-formal, and informal education sectors should collaborate to enlighten the younger generation, providing them with opportunities to value global cultural diversity and empowering them to develop the necessary applied and research skills to play their roles in society. While quality education at all levels is fundamental, there is now an emphasis on the importance of continuous training and instruction outside the classroom. In the ever-evolving global economy, knowledge has become the most treasured asset of the world (Chattaraj, 2017). This has created an increased need for re(education) and training throughout life. Presently, countries incorporate policies that guarantee learning throughout an

individual's life as a response to the varying nature of the contemporary labour market (Jakobi, 2012).

The UN's World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) (1987) reported that education plays a great role in creating awareness, social change in values, and attitudes towards environmental issues within the context of sustainable development (Sims and Falkenberg, 2013). Education is the core of sustainability. Therefore, the purpose of education is to boost behavioural changes that will lead to a sustainable future for generations in terms of environmental integrity, economic viability and a just society (UNESCO, 2015). As part of the curriculum, some educational programmes integrate skills, values, behaviours, and expertise to support economic growth in Nigeria. Enoh (2009) posits that civic education, which is a subject in the Nigerian curriculum, is a factor for sustainable development as it teaches responsible citizenship which is a holistic approach to Nigeria's economic development.

According to Bedawy (2014), education through casual, informal, non-formal, or formal strategies helps people to be aware of ongoing issues affecting sustainable development globally. Common issues affecting sustainable development include poverty alleviation, CSR, management, patterns of production and consumption, ethics and diversity, and democracy and governance. To tackle these challenges, UNESCO (2015) says that education encourages the place of global citizenship which goes beyond being an indigene (as often seen in Nigeria) to a commitment and collaboration by globally-minded individuals who are conscious of how their actions in their home countries affect the global community. According to Nwokocha and Balewa (2018), civic education as a subject encourages students to think critically in understanding the connections between local and global; builds motivation to engage and assume roles in resolving global challenges, and contributes to a just and sustainable world.

UNESCO (2001; 2003) argues that through education, proper decisions about the long-term future of the economy are made. Stakeholders must review programmes and management policies of schools and ensure their relevance to better address the issues and opportunities for sustainable economic growth. Relevance in education is seen as having socio-cultural and socio-economic dimensions concerning preparation for life in local and national contexts and participating in the benefits of globalization (Barrett, 2011). Socio-economic relevance explains students' readiness for sustainable livelihoods through education.

Education for sustainable economic growth functions to educate and train students by developing their skills and knowledge to contribute to the development of the economy (Bedawy, 2014). Through education, leaders emerge who are competent to manage the affairs of the public and private sectors. Beatty and Pritchett (2012) assume that many students graduate from formal education without knowledge of basic literacy and numeracy skills. Schooling does not necessarily produce learning or education. Filmer et al. (2006) note that quality education in schools is seen in the level of learning outcomes achieved by students. These scholars have criticized the emphasis placed on the traditional approach to quality based on school inputs like class size, infrastructure, and teacher qualifications rather than on actual student learning. Quality education positively affects a nation's economic advancement more than the individual's years of schooling (World Bank, 2011). Most countries are now becoming internationally competitive as they offer knowledge-intensive products and services, expand education, and emphasize the acquisition of skills and competencies (Verger et al., 2015). A holistic approach to education quality delivery is needed that not only recognizes the outputs but most importantly, the processes and contextual dimensions leading to educational results. A comprehensive framework was proposed by UNESCO (2005) that includes learner characteristics, context, outcome dimensions, and inputs.

This framework lays out the relationship between outcome dimensions and context, learner characteristics, and inputs. This has been developed in the latter part of this thesis.

Figure 2 Relationship between outcome dimensions and context, learner characteristics, and inputs

Source: UNESCO (2005, p.4)

Educational institutions have the responsibility to develop teaching and research methodologies (through properly trained and qualified teachers) to disseminate information easily to the students to improve their communication skills, critical thinking, and involvement in matters that relate to the social, economic, and managerial values of sustainable development. Professional

development rather than training opens pathways that capitalise and build on the knowledge and expertise within the body of the teaching profession. Professional development ranges from mutual interactions to mentoring relationships and university degrees. Professional associations bring subject specialist teachers together to extend teachers' knowledge and expertise. The living and working conditions of teachers are a vision for developing and disseminating quality education (Marphatia et al., 2007). It is feasible to develop and monitor teaching and research methodologies at the global level. This is done at the system level carried out through an inspectorate and other forms of school supervision and evaluation (Carlson, 2009). To achieve this, Barrett and Sorensen (2015) provide a quantitative input indicator that sets frameworks to determine the frequency of contacts a school has with its supervisors, and a qualitative input indicator that sets frameworks used to evaluate schools. The effectiveness of these school inspections to improve education quality delivery depends on clear communication of expected findings to the teachers.

PART TWO

3.4 Sustainability of the school as a business venture

For this section, the concept of sustainability will be explored, its theories based on the school as a business venture, its operations, and strategies for survival in a competitive environment. Attention has been focused on sustainability in recent years following the growing concerns in the business world, environmental and climate change, issues of poverty, and tensions arising from social inequalities. The sustainability of organisations is now an important area of research. This is because organisations are the productive resource of the economy. Sustainability now has a meaningful influence on organisational strategies and operations. This impact, according to Eccles et al. (2014), reveals that organisations are characterized by a governance structure, a long-term

approach to maximize profit, an active stakeholder management process, and a developed measurement and reporting system. Organisations play an essential role in facilitating sustainable development (Barkemeyer et al., 2014). Simply put, sustainability has been defined as development that meets the needs of the present without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainability has also been defined as an economic state in which people place demands on the environment without reducing the ability of future generations to access the same demands (Hawken, 1993). Sustainable development involves seeking economic prosperity, environmental quality, and social equity all at the same time (Elkington, 1999). These definitions promote the indefinite existence of human systems through three dimensions: economic, social, and environmental. Studies reveal that sustainability is beneficial to organisations, society, and the environment through tangible benefits like low-price overheads and risks in running a business, and intangible benefits like increased attractiveness to talent, brand reputation, and competitiveness (Bove and Bonini, 2014; Kron et al., 2013). The comprehensive objectives of sustainability are to protect and manage the ecosystem; change unsustainable patterns of production and consumption; and eliminating poverty (Elkington, 1999). According to the UN (2019), the world is currently faced with the biggest challenge of eliminating poverty; and it is a condition for sustainable development, particularly in developing countries.

Table 5 A framework for considering different approaches to Business Sustainability

Source: (Dyllick and Muff, 2017)

Material redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Table can be found: Dyllick, T. and Muff, K. (2017) 'What does sustainability for business really mean? And when is a business truly sustainable?', in Jeanrenaud, S. Gosling, J. and Jeanrenaud, J. (ed.) *Sustainable Business: A One Planet Approach*. Chichester, UK: Wiley.

The basic business process uses the ‘input – process – output’ model to deeply understand approaches for integrating sustainability into the school as a business venture. On the input side, different issues which businesses choose to consider and address are identified (what?) – providing quality, inclusive, and affordable education to the youth. On the process side, emphasis is placed on different organisational perspectives (how?) – the teaching and learning process and management structure set up to achieve this. On the output side, the focus is placed on different values the business creates or preserves (what for?) – achieving students learning outcomes, raising global-minded citizens, and contributing to the economic growth of society (Dyllick and Muff, 2017).

3.5 Theories of Business Sustainability

Three evolving theories of sustainability and organisations have been developed by Chang et al. (2017).

3.5.1 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Bowen (1953) notes that large organisations are important centres of power. This means that people are influenced by the actions of these organisations. He proposes that businesses are required to pursue set out policies, make decisions and follow desired actions towards the objectives and values of society. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (1999, p.3) describes CSR as ‘a corporate commitment to contribute to sustainable economic growth, local communities, employees, and the general society to improve their quality of life’. Investing in CSR further improves the competitiveness of a school as a business venture. The term ‘social responsibility of businesses’ has steadily progressed to ‘corporate social

responsibility'. Friedman (1962) argued that the real social responsibility of an organisation is to generate wealth for its stakeholders, and that Bowen's (1953) concept of social responsibility threatened the basis of a society. CSR, therefore, describes the voluntary, strategic, and proactive responsibilities of organisations – for economic gains and to influence society – to create long-term value. According to Carroll (1979), the nature of CSR in schools is divided into four categories: legal responsibility, economic responsibility, discretionary responsibility, and ethical responsibility. Economic issues are important aspects of the school's responsibilities which include risk management, human relations/employee productivity, brand equity, cost of capital, and government financial regulations. A lot of research has been conducted in the field of CSR to examine the effect of CSR on corporate economic performance (Moneva et al., 2007; Tan et al., 2015; Orlitzky et al., 2003). These researchers note that there is an obvious relationship between financial performance and corporate social performance. This is because when schools are responsible, they can benefit from their improved reputation in the public and the business community, thereby increasing the ability to attract capital.

A classification into three fields of action helps to structure the variety of CSR measures in organisations.

CSR in the school: CSR begins in the school. Structures and processes of the business operations in the school need to be put in place strategically to ensure sustainability. Programs to improve job satisfaction of teachers and targeted staff development programs/training are initiatives to help retain highly qualified teachers and ensure operational performance in the school (PriceWaterhouseCoopers, 2007). This concept contributes to making the school appealing and helps attract and retain teachers. Also, if schools encourage the opportunity to train apprentices

and maintain older workers, this will solve the social and economic challenge of labour market security and education.

CSR at the location of the school: The school is not an isolated entity; it assumes responsibility by strategically investing in the society in which it is located. Investing in local infrastructure, offering scholarship opportunities to students within the local society, permission for local communities to host events within the school at no cost, recruiting junior staff from local communities, and sponsoring other social or cultural projects relating to sustainable resource management have a positive effect on the loyalty of parents, teachers, and other shareholders (Chang et al., 2017). The schools can also combine resources with public authorities within the scope of “Public-Private Partnership” projects to achieve a common objective.

CSR on the market: CSR is increasingly geared towards solving social issues with entrepreneurial models. This allows the school to shape its CSR activities on a sustainable basis. These models – ‘creating shared value’, ‘social innovation’, and ‘inclusive business’ – offer opportunities to develop the market and at the same time solve socio-economic challenges.

The CSR activities of the school can never replace political responsibility, instead, it complements the political and civilian responsibilities. The most important function of the school consists in its economic success because it ensures that jobs are generated, students have access to quality education, taxes are paid and the foundation for the economic welfare of the people and the nation is laid. The government has the sole responsibility to enforce feasible and sustainable laws and regulations, implement fundamental economic and social standards, and offer public services.

3.5.2 Stakeholder Theory

According to Freeman (1984), stakeholder theory promotes an efficient, practical, ethical, and effective way to manage organisations in a highly multifaceted business environment. He argued

that for schools to be managed more effectively, they must understand their relationships with traditional groups like the suppliers, students, and teachers; and also the non-traditional groups like the government, academic bodies, and the public.

Table 6 Examples of the Schools' Stakeholders

The table below shows the different categories of stakeholders of the schools used in this study.

Material redacted due to copyright restrictions. Table can be found:
Lozano, R. Carpenter, A. and Hulsingh, D. (2015) 'A review of 'theories of the firm' and their contributions to Corporate sustainability', *Journal of Cleaner Production.*, 106, pp. 430-442. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.05.007

Illustration by Lozano et al. (2015)

Stakeholder theory is a practical theory because it is the responsibility of the school to manage its stakeholders. It is an efficient theory because stakeholders who are treated well respond positively in terms of sharing valuable information (all stakeholders), buying more products and/or services (students/parents), providing scholarship opportunities and other incentives (communities), providing better financial benefits (banks and other financial institutions), investing more (investors), or working hard and remaining loyal to the school (teachers). In the stakeholder theory,

the management of stakeholders involves attending to the interests of the stakeholders (Harrison, et al., 2010). However, from a practical perspective, it is difficult to determine the interests of the secondary stakeholders like the government, regulatory bodies, and the general public. Regulatory bodies in Nigeria come up with different policies that affect the schools' operations. For example, the Ministry of Education developed preventive measures to fight Covid-19 in schools with close monitoring and inspection to ensure that these measures were put in place like handwashing stations, face covering, maintaining social distancing, and self-isolation for infected persons. However, the government-owned schools were not strictly monitored by the government compared to private schools (Research Participant – M1).

Freeman (1984) describes a stakeholder as an individual or group of persons that affect or are affected by the activities or objectives of the organisation. The primary stakeholders have a direct effect and are more influenced by the actions of the school than the secondary stakeholders. A principle of the stakeholder approach states that the main purpose of an organisation is to maximize profits for its shareholders. This means that the fundamental obligation of the school is not only to offer educational services but to ensure its long-term survival (Hasnas, 1998). The survival of the school is affected by stakeholders like the teachers, government, students, parents, and the general public. Another principle of this theory by Linnenluecke and Griffiths (2013) is that the school plays a role in its immediate communities and should react to pressures and demands from stakeholders to achieve its strategic objectives.

Stakeholder theory relates to the theory of CSR because synergy is created when all stakeholders are treated well. In other words, the attitudes and behaviour of students are influenced by how the teachers and other staff are treated; and how the school behaves towards the communities in which it operates influences the attitudes of its suppliers and parents (Cording et al., 2014). Studies show

that if the school properly understands the demands of stakeholders; it can create more value for itself even in financial terms (Harrison et al., 2010; Henisz et al., 2014).

3.5.3 Corporate Sustainability

From a corporate perspective, the school is a business venture and part of its objectives is to make a profit and be sustainable. Sustainability incorporates social, economic, and environmental issues that have business implications. To achieve corporate sustainability, there must be a focus on stakeholder requirements. The International Institution of Sustainable Development (IISD) (2002) describes corporate sustainability as implementing strategies that meet the needs of the business and its stakeholders as well as protecting and sustaining the resources needed by future generations. Another definition of corporate sustainability given by Dyllick and Hockerts (2002) and Artiach et al. (2010) states it is a business investment strategy that uses business strategies to meet and balance the needs of both current and future primary or secondary stakeholders. These definitions all point out the relationship between the stakeholder theory and corporate sustainability; the importance of meeting stakeholders' demands; and balancing the economic and social dimensions of corporate performance. Corporate sustainability is operated through the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) (Elkington, 1999) which has three dimensions, that is, social, environmental, and financial. The bottom line is defined as profit in conventional accounting (Chang et al., 2017). The concept of TBL is also illustrated as 'triple P' by Asif et al. (2013) and Salzmann et al. (2005). According to these authors, "triple P" (planet, people, and profit) implies that schools can sustainably create more value and encounter fewer risks if it considers the environmental (planet), social (people), and financial issues (profit) as opposed to a school that focuses mainly on profit.

Figure 3 The concept of corporate sustainability

Material redacted due to copyright restrictions. Figure can be found: Asif, M., Searcy, C., Zutshi, A. and Fisscher, O. (2013) 'An integrated management systems approach to corporate sustainability', *Journal of Cleaner Production* 56, pp. 7-17. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.10.034

Source: Asif et al. (2013)

According to Asif et al. (2013), the figure emphasizes that 'Triple P' and 'TBL' are key concepts of sustainability. The figure also shows that a sustainability strategy is important for the business continuity of the school. Corporate sustainability seeks to meet key stakeholder requirements thereby providing the school with legitimacy and license to operate its business.

In addition to the TBL for sustainability in the business context, sustainable business models offer another approach to corporate sustainability. Business models are key issues in promoting corporate sustainability and it describes how schools increase their competitive advantage through their services. Sustainable business models are business models which absorb the TBL approach and consider the interests of the stakeholders (Chang et al., 2017). Through a sustainable business model, schools can embed sustainability into their business purpose, mission, and process to gain competitiveness. The school is constantly faced with challenges such as changing market

conditions like Covid-19 with its adverse effect on school operations, changes and uncertainties in government policies, coordination of operations to meet national and international standards, parents' demands, and an increased need for qualified teachers. Corporate sustainability, therefore, enables the school to use a flexible approach to identify these challenges and adapt useful business strategies to tackle them (Asif et al., 2013).

3.6 School Management Practices for Sustainability

Education in Nigeria is varying and now structured to meet certain goals like the Education for All (EFA, 2015). The requirements to meet these goals are centred on advancing teaching and learning by implementing effective school management policies. The school management team (Owner, Principal, Vice Principals, and HODs) have the responsibility to understand their roles in managing the school as a business venture and improving student outcomes. They represent the school's management structure and are responsible for implementing the Nigerian education policies. The changing Nigerian political and socio-economic environments affect the education system. Secondary education forms the basis for formulating national policies and leads to economic growth and development if implemented (Francis, 2012).

Corporate governance as a management practice is a major factor in ensuring the provision of quality education in the school. For this research, Kadir and Nimote (2019) describe corporate governance as a set of responsibilities and procedures carried out in the school by efficiently using resources, accountability, and collective decision-making to ensure that educational objectives are achieved. Corporate governance also concerns how the school composes policies, produces and disburses funds, develops curricula, and manages teachers and students (Khalique, 2010). Corporate governance is responsible for the school's effectiveness, quality, and accountability.

Research has been done by Kadir and Nimote (2019) using the system theory to investigate the relationship between good governance and management of secondary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study showed that effectively managing education is dependent on the school leader's responsibility in managing available resources and collective decision making (good governance) to fulfil educational objectives. Further research also shows that corporate governance strategies lead to school performance; relate to behaviour by encouraging the school management to influence profit levels for improved performance; and use school monitoring and supervision to improve performance (Kroll et al., 2007; Leuz et al., 2003; Ozili, 2021).

In 2018, the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG) was issued for public, private, and not-for-profit organisations and it comprises the relationship with shareholders, Board of Directors, transparency, definitions, audit, sustainability, and business conduct with ethics (Ozili, 2021). The Code¹⁶ is established to report unethical behaviour, pay attention to business sustainability issues, and promote transparency with investors and stakeholders. Aspects of school management practices for sustainable economic growth are discussed below:

3.6.1 Financial management

The school's success or failure in administering and providing quality education depends on effectively managing the financial resources that lead to sustainable economic growth (OECD, 2017; Bilkisu, 2018). Although a majority of schools' management teams are faced with the challenge of effectively managing school funds (Biro, 2017; Shkurina, 2018); they have an important role towards financial management skills in providing quality education for secondary

¹⁶The code is available at: <https://pwcnigeria.typepad.com/files/nigerian-code-of-corporate-governance-2018-1.pdf>

schools. This role is a result of the demand for high quality in the education system and the decision to meet the global demand for human capital to manage development programmes (Shkurina, 2018). The school needs financial resources for salary payments, school supplies, academic field trip costs, school buildings and facilities maintenance, modern teaching and learning methodologies, extra-curricular activities, and other school programmes. Therefore, this means that for the school to succeed, it must effectively manage its financial resources, which in turn, improves school and student performance for sustainable economic growth (Bilkisu, 2018).

The school management team is expected to possess financial skills to identify various sources of funds to finance the school's academic and extracurricular activities. This is the most important condition to implement the curriculum and deliver quality education methodologies (Okumbe, 2007). Apart from tuition fees, alternative sources of funds can be generated for school development through lending halls, vehicles, and playgrounds to surrounding communities (Amos and Koda, 2018). Additional funds are also generated through fund-raising activities by host communities and parents, corporate funds from banks, UNESCO grants, and USA-Aid (Paul, 2018; Chonjo, 2018). Through financial management skills, the school management can detect frauds and financial errors, recognise causes of gains or losses in school, and accurately state the financial position of the school. Funds generated from different sources should be audited to verify the efficiency of those charged with the financial responsibility (Nwafukwa and Sunday, 2015). The financial officer who serves as the internal auditor is responsible for checking the income and expenditure account, and verifying the school financial statements for the quality provision of education outcomes (Kumar, 2017). Regular monitoring and evaluation of the school's budget/reports create measures to address financial challenges ahead of time (Amos et al., 2021). Competence in monitoring and evaluating the school budget equips the management in

procurement practices like acquiring goods and services based on set financial guidelines. An important duty of the school management is to manage available (and in some cases scarce) school resources while prioritising the school's needs.

Chrisantous (2013) notes that school funds may be scarce due to delays in raising funds, fee avoidance, and a small number of students enrolled in the schools. Scarcity of the school funds due to the growing demands of providing quality education leads to low salaries and the inability to invest in essential teaching and learning aids and infrastructure (Partelow et al., 2018). The lack of professional accountants or bursars make it difficult for the school to prepare and compile accurate accounting records, identify financial errors, and collect fees due from parents which in turn affects financial management (Edmund and Lyamtane, 2018). A proper vision and mission serve as drivers for members to improve the school's financial plans and allocate school resources to achieve the identified mission and vision (Mosha, 2018; Amos et al., 2021). Actions are necessary to demonstrate ethical standards in financial management to achieve the goal of preparing human capital with relevant skills and knowledge to resolve challenges facing the Nigerian society for its sustained economic growth.

3.6.2 School Leadership

Research shows that school leadership is crucial in providing quality education and sustaining the school as a business venture (Leithwood et al., 2006; Robinson, 2007). The relationships, understanding, and interaction between the management team, students, and teachers provide opportunities for good leadership trends in the school (Darling-Hammond, 1999). Effective school leadership makes a significant improvement in students' learning outcomes and school sustainability (Leithwood et al., 2004). School leadership is also seen to increase student

performance, teacher effectiveness, and job satisfaction (Leithwood et al., 2006; Ovando, 1996). Individuals' career development and professional growth opportunities are the responsibility of the school leadership (York-Barr and Duke, 2004). However, in situations where the schools only use the top-down leadership approach and hierarchy – this stops teachers from interacting with each other and hinders effective administration (Ash and Persall, 2000). If the traditional top-down leadership approach only exists in the school, the teachers replicate this style when appointed as principals. Therefore, to replace the top-down leadership approach, the school should adopt a culture of collaboration, trust, and networking (Bryk and Schneider, 2003).

The role of the principal has become more multifaceted and challenging in the 21st century (Bush, 2013) because of the rising need to be accountable and produce student outcomes for countries to compete in the increasingly global economy. World Bank (2012, p.7) says that 'the leadership of today needs to ensure that future generations will be fully functional, literate and skilled members of society, lest they jeopardise the likelihood of achieving the nation's vision for 2030'. However, even the most experienced school leader will face the challenge of providing quality education with scarce resources. Therefore, it is important to appoint only the best professionals to occupy the position of principal and other leadership roles in the school. The recruitment and selection processes to appoint the school leadership determine the effectiveness of the school. Ibukon et al. (2011) note that processes to appoint the principal in Nigerian schools are more successful when experienced teachers are selected. However, appointing principals with only teaching qualifications means that the school leadership and management are left in the hands of unqualified personnel (Ibara, 2014). Teaching experience is not the only criteria for potential leaders in schools because the danger is seen in promoting a teacher from a position of competence to a position of incompetence (Arikewuyo and Olalekan, 2009). A survey of selected Nigerian schools by

Arikewuyo and Olalekan (2009) shows that school leadership training is needed in the functional areas of finance, personnel, and school-community relationships. Also, Ofoegbu et al. (2013, p.67) conclude that:

‘The Nigerian school of today is different and much more complex than that of some decades ago. There is very little semblance between the earlier schools and today’s in terms of population, infrastructure and technology, particularly communication technology . . . Leadership in schools is therefore very different and more difficult today than it was two or more decades ago . . . standards of teachers’ performance and students’ academic performance are very much below expectations.’

To tackle these challenges, school leaders need to be more prepared for their demanding roles by incorporating programmes like capacity building, workshops, supervision, study leave, in-service training, retraining, and skill upgrading courses (Osagie, 2012).

3.6.3 Managing Resources

According to Besong (2013), four signs are needed to measure the quality of the school. These are the quality and availability of teachers, quality and quantity of infrastructure, quality and number of students admitted, and quality and number of managerial personnel like inspectors and supervisors. The quality of these indicators determines the school leaders’ administrative efficiency. Scarce resources increase the challenge the school leader faces in providing quality education. However, Odufowokan (2011) and Obadara and Alaka (2010) note that the availability of resources, good facilities, and instructional materials have an impact on student outcomes and the sustainability of the school as a business venture. School inspection and supervision are very important to ensure that goals are met in terms of financial, managerial, quality, and student outcomes. However, the mandate for supervision can be difficult in cases where the schools lack

available resources. Most supervisors tend to focus on administrative control rather than on offering support (De Grauwe, 2007).

The teaching profession is important and determines the health of a nation's economy. Therefore, competent teachers are needed in a significant number to drive the mission and vision of the school to form the basis of the economy. Attracting and retaining high-quality teachers is an important obligation for education. Teachers who are adequately comfortable with their jobs are in a position to fulfil the educational and business objectives of the schools and in turn achieve national economic growth (Kumari, 2008). Research points out that pay is perceived as the most important aspect of a chosen profession (Skaalvik, 2011). The salaries of teachers and school leaders should be at the same level as the salaries of other professions (Constitution and Rules of GNAT, 2000). However, many schools either struggle to pay salaries or in extreme cases, underpay the teachers. This is why even the most qualified teachers are not attracted to the education sector (Ansah-Hughes, 2016). Teachers enjoy favourable conditions of service because they can contribute their best to improve the school and offer better learning support for the students (Toropova et al., 2021; Kunter et al., 2013). However, unfavourable conditions of service discourage teachers making them seek jobs in other schools or leave the profession entirely (Ansah-Hughes, 2016). A dissatisfying work environment is a major reason for teacher turnover thereby undermining the status of the profession and making it difficult to recruit new teachers (Ingersoll, 2017).

Facilities management is a fundamental aspect of the general administration of the school. Actualising the goals and objectives of education require the provision, management, and maximum utilisation of the school facilities. School facilities include the physical learning environment, infrastructure, acoustics, lighting, the architecture of the classroom, and seating

arrangement in the classroom (Baafi, 2020). An environment structured to facilitate the teaching and learning process creates a change in the students through critical thinking (Asiabaka, 2008). Studies show that there is a close relationship between the physical environment and the academic performance of the students (Baafi, 2020). The school facilities management is a collective effort. Management processes and ideas from stakeholders are applied in facilities management. In some schools, available facilities may be regarded as obsolete in terms of quality and quantity (Asiabaka, 2008). Flexibility should be part of the management process in providing facilities that will serve the leap in school enrolment and the increasing number of academic programmes. For effective facilities management to be achieved in the school, Regnier (1980, p.102) 'advocates team efforts of facilities planners and capital budget analysts, administrators, academic staff, fiscal and institutional research personnel'. The school management is responsible for ensuring facilities maintenance, preventive maintenance, routine management, emergency repairs, and predictive maintenance (Asiabaka, 2008). The management requires a combination of experts in different fields who possess the necessary human relations skills to assemble and utilise the skills of relevant individuals within and outside the schools for efficient facilities management. Quantitative and qualitative information is needed and forms the basis for facilities management decision-making. Quantitative information involves the nature and condition of existing facilities, nature of present use, and possible future use; and the qualitative information involves access to support facilities, room configuration, and space for equipment according to the subject.

3.6.4 Talent Management

Aina (2004) emphasizes that the quality of teaching and research is reflected in the services provided by the teacher. Teacher performance is a major determinant of the success or failure of a school. It is therefore important to understand the expertise needed to meet current and future

performance outcomes of teachers in the school (Tripathy, 2014). Evidence from research shows that for organisations to be successful, the performance of their employees is very important (Salah, 2016; Dobre, 2013). The need for highly competent teachers to satisfy the needs of the school and society is very crucial. Human capital is a key driver of the school's success story. The school, therefore, needs to leverage the knowledge and skills of its human capital. According to Omotunde and Alegbeleye (2021), human capital in the school is attained by attracting talented teachers who are qualified, highly motivated, skilled, effective, and can use their skills to ensure student outcomes. Talent management describes the human resources the school attracts, acquires, develops, and retains to meet its goals and objectives. Teacher performance is managed by developing, identifying, rewarding, and measuring best behaviours and dedication to service according to the school's business strategy (Olufemi et al., 2020).

Omotunde and Alegbeleye (2021) further note that talent management entails the HR manager's systematic approach of sourcing talents, screening (sorting qualified and unqualified candidates), selecting (interviewing), on-boarding (offer and acceptance), deploying (assigning roles and responsibilities according to the area of strength), and retaining (keeping talents that contribute to the success of the school), through motivation and clear career progression. In the case of the school, the HR manager is the Principal. The recruitment and selection process is aimed at obtaining the right number of teachers who will meet the human resource needs of the school (Armstrong, 2003). It also aims to attract potential teachers who have the knowledge, skills, and abilities to help the school achieve its goals. Appropriate management infrastructure is needed to build and sustain a committed workforce in the school (Chew, 2005). It is important to adopt different recruitment methods depending on the vacancy to be filled and the teacher's abilities based on the demands of the job (Arthur, 2006).

A study by Mbagwu and Nwachulwu (2010) revealed that on-the-job training, development, workshop, seminars, and conferences enhance job performance. Training and development are important for a successful talent management programme in the school (Omotunde and Alegbeleye, 2021). Training and development are also an investment in the school's human assets. In many cases, funding is the major factor that inhibits training in schools (Abba and Dawha, 2009). However, the biggest concern is when teachers seek job opportunities in other schools. The schools deal with his challenge by getting the teachers to share the training and development cost (Cappelli, 2009). Provision for training and development is in the ability to provide learning opportunities and to attract and retain the best teachers for the schools.

PART THREE

'Entrepreneurship is the cornerstone to African development and the key to local value creation in Africa. I am determined to ensure that Africa's next generation of entrepreneurs have the platform they need to turn their entrepreneurial aspirations into sustainable businesses that will drive economic growth and job creation across Africa' (Tony Elumelu)

3.7 Economic Growth

Entrepreneurship education, which has been fully incorporated into the Nigerian education curriculum, is a major way to guarantee the emergence of capable entrepreneurs. Nwangwu (2006) emphasizes that the greatest weapon against poverty is the education of the youth. He further says that any form of education that does not equip its recipients to be self-reliant is a flawed system of education. People are empowered to be confident and self-reliant when they are given good

education to prepare for jobs and to create jobs¹⁷. They can enjoy good living, provide for their families, and offer quality services through the practices of what they learned which will serve to advance society.

Nigeria is richly endowed with entrepreneurship opportunities like educational services, import and export of agricultural products, fashion, hospitality, waste management, refining, alternative power installation, and many others. However, these opportunities have been dampened by the adoption of inappropriate policies (Ebiringa, 2012). The nation is not able to reap the numerous opportunities as a result of poor implementation of government policies and a generally poor approach to the empowerment of would-be entrepreneurs.

Economic growth is one of the most important aspects of the global economy. Developing countries need economic growth as a powerful tool to improve the quality of life and alleviate poverty. Studies show that quick and sustained economic growth is the pathway to make progress not only towards improving the conditions of people living on less than \$1.90 a day (UN, 2019) but mainly towards achieving the SDGs. Economic growth creates continuous circles of prosperity and opportunity (DFID, 2005). Job opportunities motivate parents to invest in education for their children. This then leads to a strong group of entrepreneurs for human development. Therefore, economic growth is a major determinant for further economic growth (Boldeanu and Constantinescu, 2015). A successful strategy to reduce poverty reduction is that measures must be in place to encourage rapid and sustained economic growth. The measures must be set up and promoted to allow the poor to participate fully in opportunities that lead to economic growth. These

¹⁷United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs Division for Social Policy and Development (2013) *Online survey on promoting empowerment of people in achieving poverty eradication, social integration and full employment integration full employment and decent work for all*. Available at www.un.org/esa/socdev/publications/FullSurveyEmpowerment.pdf (Accessed: 19 September 2021).

measures include better labour markets, elimination of gender inequality, and an increase in financial and educational inclusion¹⁸. Future growth is based on an increasingly globalised world that offers not only new opportunities but new challenges. The economic growth of a country is determined by its leadership, policies, and educational institutions.

The need for a country's socio-economic growth is the responsibility of both the government and the citizenry. This can be achieved by school management practices to ensure that entrepreneurship practices and incorporating entrepreneurship education are a core content of the curriculum (Table 2 – learning objectives for SDG 8). Entrepreneurship education is a vital tool for enhancing the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills for identifying business opportunities that will provide jobs for the citizens and enhance income to the government treasury to enable economic development through taxation and other business levies (Ukommi et al., 2015). The dawn of the 21st century in countries of the world has given rise to several reforms in the education sector targeted at high-skilled human capital development through entrepreneurial practices and science and technology to serve as drivers of economic growth.

3.8 Entrepreneurship Development

According to the UNDP (1999), entrepreneurship development is the process of improving entrepreneurial skills and knowledge through regulated training and institution-building programmes. The aim of entrepreneurship development is to develop skills in entrepreneurs to create more new ventures. It accelerates employment generation and economic growth focusing more on growth potential and innovation. Iheonunekwu (2003) further notes that entrepreneurship

¹⁸State Department, *2020 Investment Climate Statements; Nigeria*, September 2020.

development involves training the individual's mind, developing skills, and inducing willingness in them to be job creators and business owners through a structured learning process.

Entrepreneurship serves as a push for economic growth and development. The Nigerian government must prioritise sectors that have the potential to contribute to GDP growth, meet the demand of consumers in both the local and export market, and can absorb a significant number of the labour force (NESG, 2018). Shubham Chaudhuri, The World Bank Country Director for Nigeria says 'reforms would help achieve faster, more inclusive, and sustained growth with jobs' (World Bank, 2018, para.6). Entrepreneurship education reduces the high level of poverty. While the private sector could bridge the gap in job deficit in Nigeria, it cannot proffer a solution to the increasing rate of unemployment unless the government embarks on policies to establish sectors strategically for job creation. NESG (2018) reports that although 77.5 million people were active in the Nigerian labour force, only 25% worked for pay/wages. This is a very low share and it shows the weak capacity of both the public and private sectors to provide formal jobs for the economy. On the other hand, 75% were either apprentice, informally employed, or family-employed in the case of family businesses. The income of these workers is highly inconsistent meaning that there is no potential to expand their business or increase their income.

Entrepreneurship education is also seen to create a smooth shift from a traditional (old) to the new economy. Reports from World Bank (2019) show that the Nigerian economy has not been able to transform the capital, labour, land, and other inputs into goods and services compared to other countries. This has hindered productivity, economic growth, living standards, and job creation fearing that people living in poverty will continue to rise, increasing by more than 30 million by 2030. Entrepreneurship education aims at employment generation. World Bank (2018) reports that Nigeria created 450,000 new jobs in 2018 while over 5 million Nigerians entered the labour market

in 2018. This is not enough to tackle the problem of the new generation entering the labour force. Finally, entrepreneurship education provides graduates with enough training and support that will enable them to establish a career in small and medium businesses. The Nigerian education sector needs to emphasise value addition to ensure that citizens are intellectually relevant to the changing business environment.

Human talent is the most productive aspect of the present-day economy. For youths and graduates to find suitable jobs and companies to attract the skilled workers they want, emphasis must be placed on developing a skilled workforce and expanding human capacities through a high-quality system of entrepreneurship education, training, skill acquisition, and life-long learning (Ojeifo, 2012). Unlike unemployable graduates who flood the labour markets, entrepreneurship education brings about a competitive advantage of business ownership, job creation, and more chances of securing jobs as the graduates will be highly skilled to take opportunities as they come up. These graduates become unemployable because they either study outdated courses not relevant for the 21st century or they are not sufficiently equipped with the needed hard and soft skills for their new jobs (Cox, 2016).

According to Nwafor and Udensi (2015), the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) was developed in 1986 and the Work for Yourself Programmes (WFYP) in 1987 to boost opportunities for entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. These programmes were aimed at empowering graduates for future jobs and creating wealth through entrepreneurial thinking. The NDE had three core programmes namely: the Youth Employment and Vocational Skills Development Programme; the Agricultural Programmes; and the Small Scale Industries and Graduate Employment Scheme. They were charged to foster entrepreneurship, providing an enabling environment for self-reliance, and creating employment opportunities. Graduate unemployment

has continued to be a major problem in Nigeria despite the policies put in place by the government. According to the National Planning Commission (NPC) (2005), to further address this issue, the Federal Government of Nigeria launched the NEEDS to equip individuals with the skills they need to be resourceful and to alleviate poverty in the country. The NEEDS focused on re-orienting values, creating wealth, reducing poverty, and generating employment. On 3rd September 2012, President Goodluck Jonathan launched an empowerment initiative – Youth Enterprise With Innovation in Nigeria (YOUWIN) to enhance opportunities for entrepreneurship development and practices and to reward creative performance among young entrepreneurs (Ukommi et al., 2015). Results from this policy showed that it raised entrepreneurs who were able to grow their businesses beyond a small scale with 1200 winners of the business plan competition and 7000 new jobs created. However, this program was dropped in 2015 by the current President, Muhammadu Buhari¹⁹.

To achieve economic growth in Nigeria through entrepreneurship, Ojeifo (2012) develops strategies to reduce the problems of entrepreneurship education. These strategies are to combine local public and private funds to generate a small nature capital fund; set up affordable business schools where students can join; run internship programmes where students can be paired with locally successful entrepreneurs that have clearly designed entrepreneurship education programmes; curriculum-based organisations where students can identify a potential business, plan, create and operate a small business using the organisation as mini-incubator; and create an enabling economic and political environment. This serves as a behavioural learning objective that seeks to promote and empower young people and gives them opportunities to apply their education in everyday situations (Table 1 – learning objectives for SDG 4).

¹⁹ Okwa, N. (2021) *YouWin! – A Gift of Nigerian Genius*. Available at: <https://medium.com/nero-okwa/youwin-a-gift-of-nigerian-genius-41ba9ca9b3d9> (Accessed: 18 October 2021)

Nigerian educational institutions have the responsibility of producing well learned and competent graduates through innovation, entrepreneurial curiosity, and risk-taking (Olulube et al., 2014). Educational administrators, therefore, ensure effective implementation of the entrepreneurship education curriculum at the secondary school level which is relevant to job creation and the labour market in the 21st century. To achieve this, the school becomes an entrepreneur by embarking on some investments and production which will be done through the students to facilitate their interest and practical experience and equip them with the 4Cs of communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking (Nwafor and Udensi, 2015). To appreciate the subject matter of entrepreneurship in practice, internship programmes should be initiated for students to have hands-on experience and face-to-face contact with already established entrepreneurs.

3.9 Economic Growth as the basis for Nigeria's Development Policy

Economic growth removes people from poverty. UNICEF (2018) identifies certain basic needs such as food, shelter, and clothing that must be addressed to keep people out of poverty. Poverty has been defined as scarcity in the material requirements to sufficiently meet basic human needs including food (Waziri and Abdullahi, 2018). This definition goes beyond an individual lacking private income, but it comprises the need for education, basic health, and essential services that society must provide to prevent people from falling into poverty. Economic growth is an effective way to pull people out of poverty and offer opportunities for a better life. According to Rodrik (2007, p.280), 'nothing has worked better than economic growth in enabling societies to improve the life chances of their members, including those at the very bottom'.

The number of people living in extreme poverty has continued to rise, comprising more than half of the extremely poor globally (UN, 2019). 23% of the world's poor are situated in Nigeria, the

Democratic Republic of Congo, and Ethiopia. These nations are among the five countries with the largest populations living in extreme poverty. In Nigeria presently, 85 million people live in extreme poverty (UN, 2019). Amidst rapid population growth even in some of the fastest-growing economies of East and West Africa, the number of people living in extreme poverty continues to rise. Therefore, eradicating poverty in Africa by 2030 is becoming difficult because 60 million people have been estimated to live in extreme poverty. As a result of these, SDG 1 which states ‘eradicating poverty in all its forms’²⁰ is gradually becoming a big challenge. As stated by the UN (2020), the way out of extreme poverty across Africa is to accelerate economic growth, reduce income inequality and ensure effective implementation of redistributive and inclusive fiscal policies to achieve the SDGs.

Although Nigeria has recorded an average GDP growth rate of 6% (UNDP, 2009) and there are so many government programmes aimed at fighting poverty in Nigeria (like the NEEDS) and now SDGs, there is still no answer to the rising poverty incidence. Son and Kakwani (2004) argue that poverty can be reduced through economic growth, but the opposite is prevalent in Nigeria. Comparing economic growth and the poverty level in Nigeria reveals the contradiction of growth in the face of poverty and inequality. Therefore, there is a need to explore the impact of growth on a major macroeconomic poverty indicator – the education sector. Knowing the impact of education on economic growth in Nigeria will help in formulating policies that will increase quality and access to education to fight and in turn reduce the level of poverty (Son and Kakwani, 2004). Improvement in GDP is expected to reduce the level of poverty because investments in real sectors like education contribute to the real growth of GDP (Agbasi et al., 2018).

²⁰ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/poverty/>

Growth ensures human development. Education has been seen to contribute to significant socio-economic, human, political growth and development of Nigeria (Ajeyalemi, 2009). The importance placed on education made the Federal Government of Nigeria organise the first-ever National Curriculum Conference on Education in 1969 (Ikpeze, 2010). The outcomes of the curriculum conference gave rise to the National Policy on Education which was first published in 1977 and revised in 1981, 1996, and 2004 (Olure-Bank and Olayiwola, 2017). The implementation of the National Policy on Education has resulted in innovations and reforms in the Nigerian education system (Nwagu, 2010).

Economic growth is not only about reducing poverty but also ensuring measures for human development. Growth generates virtuous circles of prosperity and opportunity (Gower and Schroder, 2016). Strong growth and employment opportunities improve incentives for families to invest in education. This leads to the emergence of a strong and growing group of entrepreneurs which will result in good governance (Gower and Schroder, 2016). Strong economic growth encourages human development which further results in more economic growth. On the other hand, weak economic growth leads to a decline in the economy which results in deterioration in human development (UNDP, 1996). In many countries, vicious circles need to be broken to enter virtuous circles to achieve the SDGs.

Human development plays an important role in improving the quality of life, increasing competitiveness, and generating economic advancement. As of 2015, Nigeria was working towards being among the twenty most developed countries in the world by 2020 (Anyanwu et al., 2015). However, the nation is far from achieving this because the government fails to invest in human development through education. Benhabib and Spiegel (1994) insist that education, as a

measure of the availability, quantity and quality of human resource, is the only method that can be used to analyse the effect of human resource on economic growth.

Economic growth and human development operate through two channels. First, the macro link creates an increase in a country's tax base and makes it possible for the government to spend more on the key public services of health and education (UNDP, 1996). The second channel through which economic growth and human development operate is the micro link (UNDP, 1996). This growth increases the income of the poor and also increases their ability to easily pay for activities and goods that advance their health and education. A growing economy provides greater job opportunities. This leads to an increase in the demand for education as more returns are expected from the investment of time and money in acquiring skills (UNDP, 1996). Improved government allocation to education can boost growth in the future, and households can reap the benefits through higher future incomes. This generates a virtuous circle of development (HMT DFID, 2005).

Growth creates jobs. Economic growth creates job opportunities and higher demand for labour. Increasing employment is also crucial for higher growth. In different countries of the world especially in Nigeria, youth unemployment continues to be a major issue. This is seen in higher than average unemployment rates: young people make up 25% of the working population worldwide; however, 47% of them are unemployed. With Nigeria's fast-growing population and the sharp increase in the labour force annually, the unemployment rate has increased from 3.6% in 2006 to 23.1% in 2018 (NESG, 2018). Nigeria is challenged with underemployment as 20% of the labour force are engaged in economic activities that underutilise their skills, time, or educational qualifications. The relationship between growth and employment is not simply about whether growth creates a specific number of jobs but also on the types of job opportunities created. Informal employment is voluntary because the unemployed try to earn a living by taking on unskilled jobs

while they queue for a scarce number of the formal sector skilled and better paying jobs. Informal employment is assumed to be the second-best to formal employment and better than no employment at all. This is seen with roughly half of Nigerians doing informal jobs²¹. Evidence suggests that informal employment should not be seen as a disadvantaged part of the formal sector but as a legitimate alternative as it encourages the entrepreneurial spirit of people (Maloney, 2004). A combination of formal and informal employment is applicable in developing countries. According to OECD/ILO (2019), the informal employment sector is mainly applied in developing economies and refers to all economic activities owned by individual household members that are in law or practice not taxed or registered by the government and are not entitled to certain employment benefits like advance notice of dismissal, or annual paid or sick leave. The informal sector forms a major segment of the Nigerian economy and contributes to its development in terms of capital savings, employment generation, self-reliance, efficiency, strong linkages with other sectors, education and training ground for entrepreneurs, and utilization of local technology (Fasanya and Onakoya, 2012).

The benefits of economic growth does not seem to impact many Nigerians because 88 million people are still trapped in extreme poverty (NESG, 2018). Nigeria is faced with the challenge of ensuring that growth is seen in economic opportunities for the citizens. Achieving this growth means higher participation in the workforce and more productive jobs for the unemployed. More jobs with good incentives are needed across the sectors of Nigeria to ensure economic opportunities and sustainable growth.

²¹World Bank (2020) *Nigeria in Times of COVID-19: Laying Foundations for a Strong Recovery*. Available at: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/695491593024516552/pdf/Nigeria-in-Times-of-COVID-19-Laying-Foundations-for-a-Strong-Recovery.pdf> (Accessed: 12 February 2021).

3.10 The Endogenous Economic Growth Theories

This research focuses on the endogenous growth (new growth) theory which is used to explore the data. The endogenous growth theory maintains that economic growth is the result of internal forces and argues that improvements in productivity are directly tied to innovation and investments in human capital development and accumulation from the government and private sector. These investments in terms of education are a key factor for SEG. This theory of new growth occurred in the 1990s to explain key determinants of economic growth which are based on some growth models: the quality of human capital, which relies on investments in human development (in terms of education); state support developing of science and technology; creation of necessary conditions for the protection of intellectual property rights in the conditions of imperfect competition; and the government's role in creating a favourable investment climate and attracting new technologies (Dang and Sui Pheng, 2015). This study focuses on investment in human development through education.

These factors are divided into two groups. In the second group of theories, research and development are key factors of growth. The theory of J. Grossman (1953 – to date) and E. Helpman (1946 – to date) describe the effect of endogenous high-tech innovations on economic growth rates (UN, 2011). According to this theory, technological progress drives economic growth, ensures competition between firms, generates and implements long-term products, and technological innovation (Soyer et al., 2020). Each innovation develops new interim goods (product and technology) used to effectively produce goods than it was before. Thus, Nelson and Phelps (1966) believe that the endogenous growth theories seal the relationship between economic growth tools and how new knowledge is obtained and accumulated through technological innovations. Education, technological progress, and growth are seen to be connected. Therefore, sustainable

economic growth is achieved when countries generate new knowledge (Lilles and Roigas, 2015; Nelson and Phelps, 1966).

Sustainable economic growth incorporates public and private agencies that act towards a common goal to benefit the health and welfare of the economy, create work opportunities, and achieve continuous long-term growth which will also benefit future generations (ICTSD, 2016). These goals as seen in the first two factors include theories propounded by Paul Romer (1989b) and Robert Lucas (1988) in which human capital is an important determinant to creating sustained economic growth. The term – information or knowledge – in the theory of Paul Romer assumes that the information contained in the inventions is available for everyone and can be used at the same time. Romer’s theory suggests that ‘there is an exchange between consumption today and knowledge that can be used for the expansion of consumption tomorrow’ (Sharipov, 2015, p.770). Thus, the rate of economic growth in Romer’s theory depends on the value of human capital, focused on acquiring new knowledge. The existence of knowledge and information is a necessary condition for economic growth because it drives human capital accumulation through employment, purchasing power, and production (Soyer et al., 2020). Romer’s theory implies that countries with greater accumulation of human capital will have higher economic growth rates. According to Schultz (1961), this further implies that the development of free international trade will also contribute to higher growth rates since the exchange of products enlarges the limits of the economic system and leads to an increase in the total human capital. Although, brain drain may be experienced in countries if products (that is, human capital) are constantly taken out without being replenished. This is the case with Nigeria, where as a result of the poor education system, students are sent abroad to study and do not return after completion to contribute to the development of the

economy. Also, the poor economic state of the country forces the citizens to migrate to other developed countries, thereby draining the available human capital²².

On the other hand, Robert Lucas' theory explains that more public resources are needed to accumulate human capital through investments in education and sustainable development (European Commission, 2017). He suggests two choices of either participating in current production or accumulating human capital. A reduced spent on production leads to a drop in the current product output. On the other hand, more investments in human resources increase the product output growth.

According to Romer (1989b), knowledge is nonrival rather than rival – which means that the use of knowledge by one person does not reduce the ability of others to use it. Private goods are considered rival in the sense that everyone cannot use the same product in a competitive market economy. Knowledge can be used multiple times by one person or shared with other people at zero cost. However, if a person does not pay any cost to acquire knowledge; then the market cannot provide monetary reward for researchers who incur costs to create this knowledge.

Education involves the transmission of knowledge which in turn leads to human capital that is characterised by the health, strength, stamina, and experience of a worker. There is a huge difference between human capital and knowledge capital. Knowledge is a public good while human capital is not. Students' human capital is increased when knowledge is imparted by the teachers, but it does not create new knowledge for society. On the other hand, successful research conducted by teachers leads to new knowledge capital that everyone can share on a nonrival basis (Ndofirepi and Cross, 2017). In stable economies where education is allocated efficiently; a person's education is reflected in his or her enhanced productivity. This means that a person who

²²Olaniran, O. (2020) 'Brain drain and the Nigerian economy', *Vanguard*, 1 February, Available at: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2020/02/brain-drain-and-the-nigerian-economy/> (Accessed: 12 August 2021).

has gained more knowledge and skill from his education should receive higher wages. The individual can now decide whether the higher returns (in terms of productivity and wages) he receives is a justification for the cost of acquiring more human capital (knowledge).

Several problems may alter the efficient allocation of resources in education markets. First is the problem of borrowing to finance investments in education. Investments in physical, human, or knowledge capital require substantial initial expenditure, followed by a long period in which this investment yields a return (OECD, 2002). If the person desiring to invest does not have sufficient liquid funds initially, a capital market is used – in which case the lenders are sure that they will be repaid. The lender can seize and resell a physical capital good (a building or machine) to recover at least part of his money if the borrower fails to repay the loan as agreed. However, in countries that abhor slavery, a borrower and/or their education cannot be seized by the lender. This makes it difficult for the private market to provide access to loans for human capital investment. Government-subsidized student loans attempt to proffer a solution to this market failure in place of collateral (World Bank, 2019). The Nigerian government does not issue student loans but scholarship opportunities mainly to middle or lower-class citizens. However, many people do not have access to these opportunities and the rate of recovery of loan repayments is very low (Eseyin, 2018).

The second problem arises when human capital is acquired through on-the-job learning. On-the-job learning is achieved when the worker learns about the job during the first few months of employment. During this period, the worker's productivity increases rapidly; the new worker is paid a very low wage (or may even pay the firm for learning on the job) which increases as productivity rises, and a borrowing situation might occur if the worker is willing to incur the cost of increasing his human capital value (OECD, 2002). This borrowing situation raised the same

problem of collateral. In many economies, much of the knowledge acquired on the job is relevant only to the firm and may not be useful if the worker moves to another firm. For example, in cases where knowledge is only about the internal rules and operations of a particular firm. Workers will be reluctant to bear the cost of any training that is only specific to a particular firm, and the firm will also be reluctant to invest in a worker who may eventually leave the firm (OECD, 2002). These difficulties in appropriately measuring the returns to human capital investment may lead to underinvestment in training.

Another problem with allocating resources to human capital is the link between education and productivity. It is agreed by the endogenous growth model that highly educated workers are more productive; whether being more productive by investing in more education or being productive as a result of the education itself. Some researchers insist that education acts as a mechanism to measure an individual's productivity (Shah, 1985). Companies would normally employ college graduates because of the notion that completing college makes an individual more productive and of higher ability and not because they have learned anything that makes them stand out. In support of this argument, researchers reveal that companies measure human capital by the number of years enrolled in school (Rjoub et al., 2016; Cohen and Soto, 2007). For example, a century ago, a small number of people finished high school and a smaller number finished college. At that time, being a high school graduate signalled that an individual was a high-quality worker, and being a college graduate signalled that the individual was ranked in a category of high achievers. However, many individuals now finish college which no longer indicates exceptional ability. To achieve elite status, Soyer et al. (2020) suggest that an individual must attend graduate school and get an advanced degree because it is believed that an advanced degree raises an individual's productivity, employment opportunities, competitiveness, and could be a catalyst for sustainable economic

growth. But if the additional years of study do not increase productivity, then it is a costly waste of resources.

3.11 Justification for the use of the Endogenous Growth Theories

Endogenous growth theories maintain that economic growth is the result of internal forces like education, innovations, and more investments in human capital from public and private sectors. Maré (2004) says that endogenous growth theories is a consequence of scale and accumulation. In the Lucas theory, it is the human capital formation itself that creates endogenous growth. The effort needed to produce an extra unit of human capital should be the same and independent of the level of human capital. The school curriculum can be shared at a minimal cost and a person with higher education is likely to receive extra knowledge or skills. However, capital owners would not want to invest in knowledge capital that would earn nothing because it is considered nonrival. Therefore, investors build models to earn money from Research and Development and to pay for the capital and labour used. Earnings can be in form of tuition fees, public funds, the formation of human capital, and an increase in knowledge. Although Lucas (1988) does not state how human capital formation brings endogenous growth, whether from education or research; the model is likely unsustainable for growth. Therefore, to achieve sustained economic growth, a shift is suggested from Lucas' model to Romer's model. Romer represents an endogenous growth process that results from physical capital investments and is driven by investments in education that generates new ideas for new goods (Abbas, 2001). The creation of these new goods is a function of the stock and growth of human capital. Romer's (1989b) theory differentiates ideas from objects. Objects are rival traditional goods, so a person's use of an object stops others from using the same object. On the other hand, ideas (knowledge) are nonrival and act as a set of instructions that transform existing objects to generate more output or utility. According to Jones (2019), new ideas are scarce

and limited as opposed to existing ideas. Therefore, investments in research generate new ideas and human capital and expand the knowledge of existing ideas. Romer highlights that production increases returns to scale. For example, using the production function (of paper) below:

$$Y = F(A, X).$$

Where A = technology level and/or the number of ideas

X = other rival goods like trees, paper-making machine, factory workers

Y = the number of papers produced

The combination of rival goods and the set of knowledge determines the amount of paper produced. The researcher justifies the use of Romer's theory that the availability of more public funds and the ideas gathered produce goods and/or services for the economy, innovations, and higher economic growth rates. Jones (2019) further notes that each idea or innovation only needs to be produced once and can be reused by different people.

3.12 Summary

This chapter provided a discourse on the empirical evidence that laid the foundation for the study. An important area to note is that the role of education functions to train students by developing their skills and knowledge as a way to contribute to developing the economy. Other areas to look at in this chapter are the school management practices and theories of business sustainability. These theories are critical because they are the basis on which research assumptions are made and explain possible linkages between the constructs used for this research. The endogenous economic growth theory discussed accumulating human capital through investments in education. Entrepreneurship education is seen to equip the students to be self-reliant, prepare for and create

jobs, and contribute to Nigeria's economic growth. The position of the researcher allows for a broader insight into the study and the issues discussed in the succeeding chapters.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

4.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter is really important and the crux of the thesis. It illustrates the factors that contribute to education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria; using education and human capital as the antecedents and sustainable economic growth as the outcome. The structure of the literature review and the entire thesis is centred around the conceptual framework, therefore this chapter shows the relationship between the research constructs. The research constructs which will be discussed are funding, government policies, teaching and learning aids/methods, labour market demand, and quality of education. Entrepreneurship education is a core theme in this research and is reviewed in this chapter based on Schumpeter's focus on innovation. The conceptual framework is developed based on the literature review and theories about the research context.

4.2 Introduction

Evidence shows that the only reliable way to sustainably develop any people or nation is through education (Onano, 2015). It has been said by scholars (Aristotle and Plato) that 'As is the state, so is the school', 'what you want in the state, you must put into the school' (Akinsanya, 2004). The skills that are acquired in individuals through education must be applied to support both the present and the future generations in their daily lives. According to Abiodun (2002), this guarantees the development and sustenance of society.

Education, which is an important factor in developing the human capital, is important to increase the productivity and mental capacity of people. Education does not only supply the needed human

capital which is germane for sustainable economic growth, but according to Todaro (2007), it is also a major pathway to reduce poverty and ensure equity, fairness, and social justice.

4.3 Funding

For this research, funding will be discussed under three categories: government allocation to education, the school's access to credit facilities from financial institutions, tuition fees, and other levies concerning infrastructural development and teachers' salaries.

Figure 4 Sources of funding for educational institutions

Source: Faborode and Edigheji (2016)

The major rationale for funding of education by the government is to prepare individuals with the needed knowledge, capacity, and skills to improve their quality of life and increase new techniques for production to participate in the development process. Education has been regarded as a 'free

good' by the provider. However, the demand for it in Nigeria rose to an extent that the government could not cope by the end of the 1980s (Ubogu and Veronica, 2018). The quantity of education and education providers have increased in Nigeria; however, the quality has deteriorated drastically to a very low standard. Ige (2013) revealed that education has not received the sufficient funding it requires in Nigeria despite its great influence on economic growth. As recommended by the Education for All Coalition, UNESCO (2015) and the Abuja Declaration (2001) (Blampied et al., 2018), the Nigerian government's budgetary allocation to education should be 26%. However, the government has not met this target as a result of its delay in releasing the allocation, lack of accountability for the allocated fund, unhealthy political interference in education, and government preference for higher education to the detriment of the primary and secondary education. To solve the problem of funding education in Nigeria, the private sector and NGOs should take part through bilateral agreements and monitoring of the funds allocated.

Although the government plays a leading role in financing the SDGs, these public funds remain inadequate to support implementation. UNESCO (2015) estimates that about USD 34 billion per annum will be required to achieve SDG 4 in Nigeria between 2015 and 2030. However, only a meagre share of the nation's economy has been allocated to the education sector because of the staggering 2.1% growth of the economy (World Bank, 2020). Ubogu and Veronica (2018) note that only 7.04% of the N8.6 trillion (USD 29.9 billion) national budget was allocated to the education sector. The total sum allocated to the sector is N605.8 billion, with N435.1 billion for recurrent expenditure, N61.73 billion for capital expenditure, and N109.06 billion for the UBEC (Adedigba, 2017). The allocation is lower than the 7.4% that the government gave the education sector in the N7.4 trillion 2017 budget. The underfunding of education has led to a decline in the quality of the education system (Ubogu and Veronica, 2018).

The high influx of students enrolling in primary and secondary schools calls for urgent intervention by the government to employ other ways to fund the education sector. This influx in enrolment has led to the creation of afternoon sessions in many states of the country (Adeyemi, 2011). Certain questions need to be addressed regarding this issue: ‘who pays for education?’, ‘what sources are there to fund education?’, ‘would the funding be from private sources, the public sector, or foreign aids?’. Although quality education funding is important for sustainable economic growth (Ubogu and Veronica, 2018), Nigeria has not reached its 20% expectation for funding education. This is because the government has not allocated up to 17% of its national budget to education in any given year (Adeyemi, 2011). Nigeria, which is classified as a lower-middle-income country is still behind and has not been able to achieve the budgetary appropriation (spending) on education (which is a target of 20% of the government’s expenditure). This target has been set by the Education for All coalition, UNESCO (2015), and the Abuja Declaration (2001) (Blampied et al., 2018).

Proper financing is very important in the process of attaining a quality education that is inclusive and equitable, provides lifelong learning, and aims to achieve sustainable economic growth. It is also important to take note of all financial streams while coordinating them for the greatest impact (UNSG, 2014; Global Monitoring Report, 2012). These include:

- domestic private (financial institutions, individuals, private organisations)
- domestic public (government)
- foreign aid (UNESCO, World Bank, multilateral and bilateral donors/agencies like the African Development Bank (AfDB), European Investment Bank, Inter-American Development Bank (IADB), European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD).

In present economies, the government is solely responsible for and provides the means to finance the education sector for a long-term. This aspect of funding has a significant relationship with government policies. The High-Level Group on EFA recommended in 2006 that government spending between 4-6% of GNP and 15-20% of public expenditure should be allocated to education (EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2015). This is opposed to Nigeria's public expenditure on education which was 7.04% in 2018 (Odigwe and Owan, 2019). In lower and middle income countries, foreign aid and financing remain crucial because large spending for infrastructural improvements in education systems is needed. Although Nigeria is classified as a middle-income country, the country has the necessary financial arrangements to invest in and improve the education system. However, the Nigerian government lacks the appropriate laws and policies for proper implementation towards financing quality education (Ofei-Manu and Didham, 2015) because most of the allocated funds for education are diverted towards other corrupt purposes (Egbefo, 2012).

According to EFA Global Monitoring Report (2012), in the past decade, 63% of countries globally recorded an increase in domestic spending on education and larger shares of total national income. However, Steer and Smith (2015) note that despite this increase in education through domestic financing, many lower and middle-income countries have still recorded flaws in raising the required resources to meet up with quality education financing. The contributions of multilateral donor agencies are needed in lower-income countries where education does not receive adequate funding. It is noticed in Nigeria that the share allocated to education funding is channelled majorly to higher education, proving about 90% of the total expenditure, rather than an equal share to include basic education (Ahmed, 2015). This explains why there is no effective implementation of the UBE programme resulting in poor school facilities, inadequate qualified teachers, and no

access to quality education by children of the low class (Dogra, 2011; Olibie et al., 2013). This inequality calls for a review both now and in the future. A key factor affecting the financing of education, especially from the domestic private (individuals and private organisations) is the idea of expecting a quick return on investment. Education, which is capital intensive, produces its turnover in the longer-term. As a result, this is likely to discourage potential donors who have expectations for quick, short-term returns on investment (Sachs, 2015).

Nigeria, which has been termed the Giant of Africa is endowed with an abundance of natural resources such as oil, coal, tin, zinc, and many more. Sadly, the earnings from these resources have not been sufficiently used to develop the education sector. Instead, the government relies more on its oil proceeds and has been indifferent to other sectors of the economy such as education, health, and agriculture for the citizens. There is inadequate funding for education by the Federal, State, and Local Governments. This problem of poor funding in schools is noticed in the shortage of infrastructural facilities, poor teachers' salaries and other benefits, and misappropriation of the available funds. It is also seen in the lack of materials for teaching, use of outdated notes by teachers, no incentives for research and other co-curricular activities, economic hardships among teachers which have encouraged pilfering of any of the school's property in sight, the massive share of the budget element which is usually allocated to teachers' salaries and the slim funds for other important elements which determine the quality of learning received like the infrastructural development which include well-equipped libraries, laboratories, playfields (Victor, 2002; Boyi, 2013). This problem has led to the low standards of education in some schools and the irrelevance of the curriculum to meet the pressing economic, social, and cultural needs of the nation as compared to other developed countries.

Having well-paid teachers is a very important element of the budget. However, in many lower and middle-income countries like Nigeria, the non-salary expenditure for education is less than 5% of the budget. This is further heightened where effective mobilisation of resources is a major problem as a result of corruption (EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2015). This calls for the urgent need to develop national strategies and governance to effectively manage budget allocation.

4.4 Government Policies

It is the responsibility of the government to implement, manage and finance effective national education systems. Education planning should be fused into reducing the rate of poverty and guaranteeing sustainable economic growth strategies and it must ensure that these policies are aligned to fulfil, respect, protect the right to education²³. However, the poor government leadership of Nigeria has affected the education system. The political leaders, educational administrators, and teachers who are not result-oriented, lack the necessary academic, administrative, and managerial skills needed to execute the educational policies and programmes.

According to Okoroma (2000), government policies on education are strategies adopted to determine the direction of the education system. Education policies are needed in every society to increase the quality of life of the people. An education policy must be distinct from other policies, feasible and sustainable (Okoroma, 2006). To receive the rewards of education, every citizen must have access to quality and affordable education. Education is capital intensive but has unfortunately been left in the hands of individuals or organisations thereby making it very

²³UNESCO (2015a) Framework for Action Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (draft). Incheon: UNESCO.

expensive and unaffordable for the middle and lower class in the society as seen in the case of private schools (Dogra, 2011). This is because of the instability of the government policies regarding education.

To achieve sustainable economic growth in any country, policies and laws need to be set up by the government and strictly adhered to by all concerned. These policies are mainly geared toward the education of the human capital which is the key to unlocking the puzzle of the pathway to economic growth. The puzzle remains on the fact that most countries are yet to meet up with the internationally recognized spending on education. Nigeria, which is classified as a lower-middle-income country is still behind and has not been able to achieve the budgetary appropriation (spending) on education (which is a target of 26% of the government's expenditure). This target has been set by the Education for All coalition, UNESCO (2015), and the Abuja Declaration (2001) (Blampied et al., 2018).

The Nigerian National Policy on Education was formulated in 1977, seventeen years after the country attained independence from Britain in 1960. Before this era, Nigeria operated education policies that did not meet the requirements of the nation. According to Daniel-Kalio (2018), these education policies were narrow in scope, irrelevant to post-colonization and nation-building, and did not meet the expectations of Nigerian citizens. The policies also included obsolete methods, irrelevant curricula, and high drop-out rates. A National Curriculum Conference was held in 1969 to review the inherited curriculum to establish new national goals for Nigeria's education (Okoroma, 2006). An aspect of the National Policy on Education is the UBE which was established in 1999. Mild evidence of management by control and compliance is contained in the preface to

the NPE 2013 written by the Executive Secretary, Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council that:

‘It is therefore expected that the National Policy on Education will be publicly owned, internalized, and complied with by all. To leverage this expectation, Federal, State/FCT, and Local governments shall establish and adequately empower Special Policy Implementation Monitoring Units within the appropriate existing structures in their Ministries of Education and Local Government Education Authorities and diligently monitor and provide necessary feedback on compliance’ (FRN, 2013, p.vi).

Despite this effort by the NPE, this policy has still suffered poor implementation as a result of lack of funds, inadequate qualified teachers, poor motivation of teachers, and inadequate teaching and learning facilities (Ubogu and Veronica, 2018). This has resulted in a very poor quality of education at the secondary levels compared to the pre-1976 era. A study by Okoroma (2001) showed that the 3-3 aspect of the secondary education policy has also suffered set back due to ineffective implementation. According to the 3-3 model of secondary education, a child spends three years in junior secondary school and then moves to senior secondary school to spend another three years, if they are academically sound. The Federal Government of Nigeria set up two Federal Government Colleges (FGCs) in each of the six geopolitical zones in the country. The state governments also set up secondary schools to take care of the people's needs. However, these government policies did not cater to motivating the teachers and equipping the schools to meet the students' educational needs. This led to private organisations setting up secondary schools which are only patronized by those who can afford them (Dogra, 2011).

Despite Nigeria being the giant of Africa in terms of its abundance of oil and gas, 85 million people still live below the poverty line of \$1.90 per day (UN, 2019). Nigerian leaders lack the political will to formulate sustainable policies. Nigeria practices the Presidential System of government in which new political leaders are elected once every four years. The tussle for political power, short time spent in political positions, and distractions from opposing parties hinder the leaders from drawing up action plans due to a lack of preparation for any development effort whether in education or other sectors. This is because of the instability of governments and lack of continuity. These issues are supported by Hodges (2001, p.26) where he noted that:

‘In the final analysis, Nigeria’s development failures have sprung from the lack of success in achieving an effective model of governance. At the head of this problem has been the instability generated by the rivalry for control of the huge resources accruing to the State from the oil industry, and the use of political power to milk the state for personal gain rather than promote economic and social development.’

Education policy implementation has remained a near-impossible task because of political opposition which does not guarantee the political will to implement these policies. The lack of human capital to implement these policies makes it difficult for policies to be sustained when the tenures of specific governments come to an end. Furthermore, the failure of the policymakers to review the goal-achievement gap factor is the reason (Babalola, 2018) why leaders come up with strategies that are not feasible considering the short time spent in political positions.

According to Egbefo (2012), corruption is a major factor in the poor implementation of the development of education in Nigeria. A study by Ejiogu (2005) notes that corruption and the mismanagement of resources are the leading reasons for the poor state of Nigeria’s education system. The cost of corruption in the Nigerian education system represents about 15.5% of its GDP

(Alli, 2004). This has led to the continuous scarcity of resources needed to fund the education system. The objectives of most feasible policies like the National Policy on Education are stalled because lawmakers usually have other motives when they present budgets for the implementation of these policies, the executive arm of government is often unwilling to release funds for implementation, and the funds released (whether sufficient or not) are not fully utilised to promote the cause of education. Much of these funds are diverted to other corrupt purposes either at the source or the local level. In 2018, the Federal Government of Nigeria allocated N605.8 billion (\$1.4 billion) to the education sector, amounting to just 7.04% of its national budget and only N100 billion (\$243 million) given to the UBEC. Millions of Nigerian children have been denied access to basic education because of poor funding allocation and corruption as seen in the diversion of funds meant for the education sector (Samuel, 2018).

4.5 Teaching and learning aids/methods

Okebukola (2010) identifies the input factors in the teaching and learning process such as the curriculum, facilities, managers, students, teachers, finance, instructional materials, and other general resources. These input factors are merged in the research and teaching process, leadership, student services, administration, community impact, and quality assurance. The output shows the skilled and employable graduates, responsible citizens, creation of new knowledge, and economic growth. Okebukola (2010) further explains that the teaching and learning activity remains the most visible input as it is seen in the attitudes, skills, and research orientation of the students. A lot of teaching and learning aids have been identified as key factors for the level of education, which are the classrooms, well-stocked libraries, laboratories, and aids for extra-curricular activities (Odia and Omofonmwan, 2007). However, most government-owned schools that are affordable lack the necessary teaching and learning aids for the students which are most times caused by inadequate

funding. For computer education and ICT software development, according to Agabi (2008), the policy planners have been given the duty of ensuring and verifying the availability of required facilities, curriculum content, and laboratories to accommodate students. Also, teachers who are responsible for transferring knowledge need to be sufficiently trained on the methods of teaching and the use of teaching/learning aids (NESG, 2018). Laboratories must be built to be teaching-learning friendly in which students can put their theoretical learning into practice.

Students and teachers may be affected by negative physical and social conditions that disrupt the quality of teaching and learning²⁴. An enabling environment is important to achieve effective learning skills. All levels of government should prioritize investing in quality education infrastructure. This not only provides a better learning environment for students and improves access to education, but it also creates job opportunities for those involved in providing such service (NESG, 2018).

The National Policy on Education has presented the objectives of education to invent effective ways by which contents of the curriculum can be taught (Ogbulogo et al., 2014). These objectives are expected to help students think outside the box, explore real-life opportunities for career growth, develop practical skills for the labour market, and enable them have a smart understanding of the increasing need and changes in technology. To enhance teaching and learning activities and reduce the likelihood of students being distracted in class, thereby retaining less of what is taught, teachers are encouraged to use pictures, short video clips on any subject matter, connecting to social media networks like YouTube, Twitter, Facebook, other learning platforms. These help students to have a vivid picture or real scenario of a particular context. Ogbuogo et al. (2014) note

²⁴UNESCO (2014) *Education learning environment*. Available at: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/educational/themes/strengthening-education-systems/quality-framework/core-resource/learning-environments/> (Accessed: 13 July 2020).

that the implication of using these media for teaching and learning activities can increase the student's classroom experience, foster virtual interaction around the world using online tools and software, and encourage teamwork on shared documents. Teachers are expected to have good understanding and full grasp of their subject to promote quality teaching delivery and students' learning outcomes. Teachers are also encouraged to source information from colleagues and the internet that will be needed to help students have a full understanding of the subject.

4.6 Labour market demand

The future of the labour market is linked to the structure of the economy. Economic policies and systems are set up to make sure that workers have jobs to alleviate poverty. However, there will be no guarantee for poverty alleviation if the wages are low (Yeyati et al., 2019). More than 300 million people in developing countries are either unemployed or have a job but still live in poverty²⁵. 30% of youths in low-income countries have no basic educational qualifications, with many not having basic skills even in schools. Almost 2.7 billion workers, representing around 81% of the workforce globally have been affected by Covid-19 and the lockdown measures²⁶. Evidence from the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2016) shows that job vacancies are concentrated in the Trade and Services; Consulting; and Information Technology (IT) / Telecommunications sectors because people lack the knowledge and technical skills to work in these sectors. The G20 has committed to SDG Goal 4 of providing inclusive quality education for

²⁵ILO (2018) *The daily reality of working poverty*. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/newsroom/news/WCMS_617406/lang--en/index.htm (Accessed: 13 July 2020).

²⁶ILO (2020) *Covid-19 and the world of work. Updated estimated and analysis*. 2nd Ed. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/documents/briefingnote/wcms_740877.pdf (Accessed: 13 July 2020).

all by 2030. Therefore, individuals should be equipped with the basic literacy skills to enter the labour market and learn further skills. There is a rising demand for cognitive skills in Nigeria following emerging sectors like IT, Branding, and Consulting whereas people still use manual skills (Favara and Appasamy, 2015). Therefore, learning further skills is particularly important for people to adapt to these technological changes, and entrants from different sectors can also fit in and learn on the job.

The SDG-Education 2030 Steering Committee seeks to make education and training adaptable and responsive to meet the demand for new skills in society and the global economy (SDG-Ed2030 Steering Committee, 2020). This commitment to youth skills and the future of the labour market recognises the importance of education for economic and human capital improvements as well as poverty reduction and should be echoed in the policies of the G20, both as advocates for and education leaders (OECD, 2020). However, education in Nigeria is not meeting the contemporary challenges. As a result, the SDG target of provision of education for all by 2030 may not be achieved. Education should therefore play an important role in increasing productivity and preparing students for the labour market by providing them with the necessary skills for the workforce (Fasih, 2008). Individuals with poor skills experience a greater risk of unemployment, therefore, leading to economic disadvantage. However, the higher skills an individual has, the better their earnings and chances of being employed (OECD, 2015). Education aims for people to gain employment and contribute to the development of society. Osagie (2014) believes that the labour market can only be functional when education produces the needed workforce. It is for this purpose that UNESCO (2015) recommends that 26% of the government's annual budget should be channelled towards education.

Basic literacy skills are important to provide a solid base for people to succeed in education and the labour market. 125 million people globally are not acquiring basic literacy and numeracy skills even after spending years in school²⁷. This leads to a poor quality labour market with a large number of working-age individuals in developing countries being illiterate and unable to read and write. The basic skills gap exists globally but is greater in developing countries with an estimated 70% of 25-64 year olds (OECD, 2018b).

Academic skills and qualifications are not only needed for the labour market. Considering Nigeria's shift to a service-dominated economy; there are notable areas of deficiency because communication, collaboration, problem-solving, analytical, technical skills, and other emerging soft skills are now demanded by employers (Uzor and Nwabuikwu, 2016). The education system cannot teach all the skills needed for the labour market because students will still be in the job markets for the next five decades. G20, therefore, focuses on the content of education by teaching students how to learn – giving them the ability for lifelong learning, reskilling throughout their lifetimes, and adapting to emerging markets and opportunities²⁸. The Nigerian economy has transformed from predominantly agricultural to service-dominated with the rise of technology; therefore the government and the Federal Ministry of Education need to expedite the training of future labour market entrants to the new skill requirements of the labour market (Favara and Appasamy, 2015). To tackle the skills divide where people are not sufficiently qualified for jobs

²⁷UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) and GEMR team (2019) *Meeting commitments: are countries on track to achieve SDG 4?* UNESCO. Paris. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000369009> (Accessed: 13 July 2020).

²⁸UNESCO, UNDP, UNFPA, UNHCR, UNICEF, UN Women, World Bank and ILO (2016) *Education 2030: Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action*. Paris: UNESCO Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000245656?posInSet=2&queryId=4e812163-e415-483f-b852-f4dd584e069e> (Accessed: 13 July 2020).

because they lack the required years of experience or specific skills; employers should collaborate with the education sector to shape a curriculum for employment.

According to the classic model of Mincer (1958, 1974) and Becker (1964), the annual earnings or hourly wage of an individual is dependent on the years of schooling and experience gathered. Studies (Bonnal et al., 2002) show that in developed countries like France, students who obtained their degrees with an apprenticeship experience quickly get jobs and earn more than those who only had school-based education (Margolis and Simonnet, 2003). However, apprenticeship experience has not been fully exploited to tackle the unemployment surge in Nigeria (Fajobi et al., 2017). This could be actual driver to create job opportunities and reduce poverty even at a low investment cost in Nigeria. Students with a mix of apprenticeship experience and school-based education have the relevant skills to use their initiative to create and identify market opportunities. According to Adedokun (2011), students who learn through experience understand the importance of being involved in collective efforts to equip them with skills and competencies which they do not have; promote their self-confidence; make useful decisions that affect them; encourage them to take responsibility for identifying and meeting their needs; and fully participate in school activities, community activities and that of the wider society. Through this effort, students are enabled to seek ways to be employable, bridge skill gaps, and contribute to their development and that of the economy.

Education must create a balance between skill acquisition and labour market demand (Ionescu, 2012). Investments in quality education help to broaden citizens' access to education thereby increasing skills for people to get better jobs. The issue with the Nigerian labour market remains that while employers struggle to find sufficiently skilled workers, those who are working are often under-employed (having insufficient paid work or working below their skill and ability level).

According to Saint et al. (2003), skills and competencies, in the struggle to meet the demand of the labour market, are mainly gathered during secondary education. This is because the basic skills gathered at this level of education make possible a lifetime of learning. A study conducted by Kashefpakdel et al. (2018) in the UK shows that 90% of teachers believe that the top five skills and competencies which employers look out for are developed in the secondary school. These skills and competencies are acquired through classwork and extra-curricular activities. Teachers in this study believe that communication, confidence, teamwork, problem-solving, and creativity are the top five skills and competencies developed through extra-curricular activities. They also note that class activities develop teamwork, communication, reflection, problem-solving, and creativity in the students. These extra-curricular activities provide students with information about the labour market and boost their communication skills.

Despite the effort of schools in developing these skills and competencies, certain challenges still affect the level of development. A study by Cappelli (2015) reveals that skills gap exists where education fails to provide students with job-related skills for sectors like IT, and this leads to a disparity in the skills supplied by the labour force and the skills demanded by the employers. To bridge this gap, there must be a coalition among schools, student placements, excursions, and research funding, and the private sector must be involved in planning and executing the contents of the curriculum (Clark, 2001; Boateng, 2002). This partnership will facilitate the exchange of information, keeping the school more informed about current employers' needs and trends in the labour market. Quality education further eliminates the huge cost of training and retraining given skills gap and outsourcing of roles to employees from other countries.

4.7 Quality of Education

UNESCO (2014) states that education for sustainable economic growth is a life-long learning process in which individuals acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to contribute to a sustainable society. The quality of education received by a student has a significant influence on lifetime earnings regardless of the level of the nation's development (Solomon, 1985). Quality of education is also seen in curriculum development and teaching and learning methods. Education incorporates issues regarding sustainability such as global citizenship, poverty reduction, sustainable consumption and production, and gender equality (UNESCO, 2014). According to Choi and Kipp (2009), education should be defined to fit both regional and local contexts. These researchers also recognize the essential features of education for sustainable economic growth:

1. Interdisciplinary and holistic: learning for sustainable economic growth is embedded in the curriculum, not as a separate subject;
2. Values-driven: the assumed norms, values, and principles regarding sustainable economic growth must be practical, easy to understand, studied, discussed, and verified;
3. Critical thinking and problem solving: which increases confidence to address challenges of sustainable economic growth;
4. Multi-method: word, art, drama, math, debate, experience, science are the different pedagogies that model the processes. This is a strategy which teachers and students adopt to acquire knowledge and shape practical learning rather than just passing on knowledge;
5. Participatory decision-making: students participate in decisions on how they are to learn;
6. Applicability: the learning experiences offered are applied in day to day personal and professional life;

7. Locally relevant: addressing local as well as global issues, and using the language(s) that students are more familiar with. ‘Concepts of sustainable development must be carefully communicated in the indigenous language – languages and cultures say things differently, and each language has creative ways of expressing new concepts’ (UNESCO, 2006, p.17).

As stated by Mamman (2014), the curriculum is to be reviewed regularly by the curriculum planners (usually the Ministry of Education). This process is done to check that the curriculum can realise the desired outcomes or it has to be modernised to meet the desired outcomes. The aim of the curriculum should be to prioritise the development and application of knowledge to provide future skills needs of industries (NESG, 2018). Education for sustainable economic growth has been described by UNESCO (2014) as a whole-school approach that adopts sustainability into the curriculum, teaching and learning process, management, interaction with surrounding communities, governance, and capacity-building; and ensures that young people are taught skills which are relevant in different industries like advocacy, critical thinking, problem-solving, and conflict resolution to make them become responsible global citizens.

Figure 5 Education for sustainable economic growth as a whole-school approach

Source: UNESCO (2012)

The whole-school approach uses management practices to encourage the students and teachers of the school to be familiar with issues relating to sustainable economic growth by integrating them into the curriculum. UNESCO (2012) views that successful adoption and implementation of education for sustainable economic growth can only be achieved through the support of teachers and school administrators. According to Watanabe (2015), the whole-school approach focuses on the following issues:

- a. The formal curriculum contains the knowledge, skills, and values relating to sustainable economic growth.
- b. School ethos towards sustainability is seen in the treatment of others, school property, and the environment.
- c. School management practices reflect sustainability (for example procurement, recruitment process, and infrastructural development).
- d. School policies that reflect social and economic sustainability.
- e. Interaction between the school and the community in terms of corporate social responsibility (CSR).
- f. Real-life issues as a way of learning to enhance students' motivation and learning process.
- g. Special events like research clubs, debates, and excursions are applied to foster learning about sustainability.
- h. Students engaging in decision-making that affect school life.

The quality of education also implies that students are properly prepared for potential opportunities. The different needs of the students should be considered in both content and methods used in schools²⁹. Participatory learning and in-depth understanding of what is being taught should be encouraged rather than just memorization. Administrators and managers of schools should ensure a strict adherence to policy implementation that exposes students to skills and competencies (Aboluwodi and Owolewa, 2018). The use of examination as the only criterion to measure the academic ability and knowledge of the students has led to cheating and examination malpractice in some Nigerian schools³⁰. Students are no more eager to learn because they only rely

²⁹UNESCO (2005) *Global monitoring report*. Paris: UNESCO.

³⁰Yunus, S. (2019) 'Causes and solutions to the problem of examination malpractice', *Guardian*, 24 October. Available at: <https://guardian.ng/opinion/causes-and-solutions-to-the-problem-of-examination-malpractice/> [Accessed: 19 October 2021].

on either cramming the entire term's work or cheating in the examination halls. As a result, they are less able to be creative and innovative in finding solutions to academic puzzles. To solve this issue, teachers and educational administrators should be more proactive and less rigid in testing the knowledge of the students. Different methods can be used to assess the students like having research groups where there can be a presentation either as a group or individually at the end of the exercise; encouraging the students to write a project on a specific topic; an online or classroom quiz; or a seminar where the students can initiate a conversation, ask questions among themselves and respond to the questions on the topics covered throughout the term. These methods can be graded as well and this will encourage variety within the school system, rather than just the conventional methods of written tests or examinations.

The Ministry of Education in Nigeria responding to the new global SDGs has reviewed the curriculum of the Junior Secondary School to accommodate some subjects needed for the 21st century. The subjects contained in the curriculum are English language, Mathematics, Cultural and creative art, Nigerian languages, Arabic language, Basic science and technology, and Religion and National Values. The inclusion of subjects such as Climate Change, Peace and Conflict Resolution Education, Disaster Reduction Education, Consumer Education, and Civic Education is a response to what is required in the UN's education for sustainable economic growth (Aboluwodi and Owolewa, 2018).

The World Economic Forum (2015) lists the skills and competencies that constitute the elements of quality education that aid the achievement of sustainable economic development. The skills needed in today's innovation-driven economy are creativity, problem-solving, collaboration, and character qualities like curiosity, initiative, persistence, and hard work. Shortage of these skills

hinders the desired quality of education needed ‘to stimulate students to ask questions, analyse, think critically and make good decisions’ (Laurie et al., 2016, p.231). Furthermore, UNESCO (2014) suggests actions for fostering curriculum change, which is the use of continuous efforts to deepen the understanding of quality education to include relevance, purpose, and values for sustainability; increased capacity building for policy-makers, education leaders, and educators; flexibility in curriculum policy that allows schools to develop content and projects that are locally and globally relevant; instilling education for sustainable economic growth in competencies, professional standards, certification and accreditation of teachers and teacher education institutions; and opportunities to assess and share experience on how curriculum change has been approached.

Requirements for graduate recruitment into teaching in Nigeria are merits of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed), Postgraduate Certificate in Education (PGCE), or Postgraduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) programmes. The debate continues that failure in the Nigerian education system has resulted in low teaching standards; and a lack of basic opportunities for learning has resulted in low quality of teachers being produced (Fasoyiro, 2016). Furlong et al. (2011) questioned the effectiveness of Institutes of Technical Education (ITE) in increasing teacher subject and professional knowledge. The school management must ensure that subject mastery is an important consideration for the recruitment of graduates. This is on the expectation that possession of academic qualifications can support the development of relevant skills for instruction. According to Fasoyiro (2016), recruiting graduate teachers may be the first step in the government’s attempt to raise the academic requirements of those entering the teaching profession. Teaching should become an actual graduate profession not just a measure to solve years of unemployment

(Okechukwu, 2014). This way, entrants into the teaching profession are qualified and competent to raise the educational standards in Nigeria.

Nakpodia (2008) and Aitken (2004) define on-the-job training as a process arranged by the school boards to regularly update the teachers in the knowledge, skills, and interests of their chosen field. It is a process of continuous professional growth, which encourages the extension of technical assistance by teacher educators. On-the-job teacher training is an important aspect of the staff development programme, which is organised for teachers still in active service. Nakpodia (2008) says the benefits of on-the-job training for teachers are to:

- a. Enable teachers obtain higher academic and professional qualifications to improve their positions in the school system;
- b. Help teachers acquire more practical knowledge and skills in their teaching subjects and pedagogy to improve their competence in teaching;
- c. Provide teachers with the capability to be dynamic and flexible to changes in the 21st century teaching and learning. A study by Akinbode (1996) established that investment in the form of on-the-job training was a crucial factor in the developing teachers' commitment to their job. The result of the study further showed that teachers who had the opportunity for on-the-job training became highly committed to work.

The success of the education system is based on the availability of good and qualified teachers who are internally motivated (Boyi, 2013). The quality of education is also achieved through teachers' commitment to work as a result of the incentives given and a motivating environment. Studies were done by Ajayi (1999) and Arikewuyo (2006) and revealed that secondary school teachers in Nigeria are dissatisfied with their jobs and have poor attitudes to work. The teaching

profession does not enjoy any recognition from the public because teachers' welfare is not properly taken into consideration. This is seen in displacement, absenteeism, and truancy in their attitude to work thereby causing danger to school effectiveness (Udofia and Ikpe, 2012). Tensions in the working environment of Nigerian teachers are captured where teachers have been dejected because of poor salaries or salaries not paid regularly forcing them into a perpetual life of poverty (Nwadiani, 2008). Because teachers are generally resistant to change, certain motivation strategies must be put in place by the school leader to encourage them to engage in professional development activities, especially for those with long work experience (Carlson and Gadio, 2002).

4.8 Entrepreneurship Education

Raposo and Do Paco (2011) state that entrepreneurship education does not only teach someone to run a business but mainly encourages creative thinking and promotes a strong sense of self-worth and empowerment. It involves training students to be potential entrepreneurs. Students learn to recognize opportunities; pursue opportunities by generating new ideas; think critically; establish and operate a new firm; work with people to achieve goals; and bear and manage risks. At the secondary school level, management policies aim to adopt entrepreneurship education to create awareness for a career option and also serve to boost entrepreneurship attitudes and intentions (Unachukwu, 2009). Entrepreneurship education serves as a medium to build a better Nigeria that is free from poverty and offers surplus employment opportunities which are geared toward economic growth.

The world has become more complex and dynamic and therefore Schumpeter's theory of the need for innovation has become evident for economic development (Śledzik, 2013). Schumpeter (1934) describes innovation to mean the launch of a new product or new species of an existing product;

application of new methods of production or sale of a product; opening of a new market; new industry structure; and acquiring new sources of supply of raw materials. He argues that an individual must be innovative to make profits and that innovation is an essential driver of competitiveness and economic change. In Schumpeter's innovation theory, the activity of an entrepreneur entails unique activities that generate value and transform into new opportunities for profits, investment, growth, and employment. Schumpeter (1949) says that entrepreneurship is more than setting up and running a business which is the stagnant view of entrepreneurship. He further states that entrepreneurship is the spring of all business innovations and is the main source of economic development. Entrepreneurship is born when individuals are on the lookout to recognise new opportunities, new processes, and products to make a profit and increase growth (Drucker, 1999). According to O'Boyle (2017), the Schumpeterian entrepreneur is not just fascinated by the goal of making profit as there are more unconventional values behind entrepreneurial innovations. These values are seen in accomplishments, poverty alleviation, and economic growth. It has therefore become necessary to train students in entrepreneurial skills, especially in this era of the digital economy.

According to Ojeifo (2012), entrepreneurship education in the school aims to achieve the following goals – entrepreneurship education provides graduates with sufficient knowledge so that they are creative and resourceful in recognising business opportunities. There must be a synergy between the public and private sectors to review the curriculum and apply the knowledge that will be useful for the 21st century and beyond skills needs of industries (NESG, 2018). Entrepreneurship education is important for the youth and adults to be self-employed, self-reliant, and to build the spirit of perseverance which will help them succeed in any business venture they embark on. However, Anyaogu (2009) criticises the curriculum for its insensitivity to the dynamic nature and

contemporary life of society. Regardless of the need for innovation and entrepreneurship, the education system prepares students strictly for employment only. Success in Nigeria is only measured based on securing government or private sector paid employment. According to Ubogu (2020), equipping students with the right skills is one of the major challenges of entrepreneurship education. Some of these challenges impede teaching innovation and entrepreneurship education in Nigerian secondary schools. Agbonlahor (2016) notes that the teaching system and courses for innovation and entrepreneurship are not established. The basic courses and career development courses for entrepreneurship are not entrepreneurial in the true sense and so students do not have a full grasp of the concept of entrepreneurship apart from just setting up a business. Offorma et al (2012) further note that teaching methods in Nigerian schools are not systematic and so career development is affected by a lack of practical learning and innovative research. Another challenge is caused by the lack of relevant resources and support needed for both theoretical and practical teachers who will serve as mentors for innovation and entrepreneurship (Agbonlahor, 2016).

4.9 Summary

A key aspect to note in this chapter is that education supplies the needed human capital to alleviate poverty and increase economic growth. The chapter explored the relationships between the research constructs. Relationships between these constructs show that education is capital intensive, therefore school managements require sufficient funds to provide and maintain the quality of education. Government policies determine the direction of the education system. The Nigerian government has the task to meet up with the 26% spending target on education (UNESCO, 2015) to unlock the puzzle of the pathway to economic growth. Quality education is also seen to be a whole-school approach, therefore teaching and learning activities in the schools must reflect this approach to prepare students to meet the demands of the labour market.

Entrepreneurship education is now necessary to train students to be innovative and to recognise business opportunities. The conceptual framework discussed in this chapter is signposted as a direction for further research in the concluding chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Chapter Overview

This research study has been conducted in four phases – the foundation phase; pre-field phase; field phase; and reporting phase. The researcher will discuss the case study research and justifies the use of this preferred research strategy. The foundation phase outlines the research philosophy used for the study. The pre-field phase shows the research decisions made before the field phase, the flow chart of the case study protocol, and the steps to develop a template for the case study protocol using Stake’s (1995) idea. The pre-field phase also highlights the case study themes which have been developed by the researcher based on the research questions and data findings. The field phase explains in detail the sample size, procedures of recruiting participants for the study, and the data collection methods used – questionnaires, interviews, observations, and documents. The researcher’s in-the-moment thoughts and experiences during the field phase are also discussed. The reporting phase outlines how the quantitative and qualitative data will be analysed using descriptive tests and thematic analysis respectively. Codes will be extracted from the data and further generated into themes using the procedures of Braun and Clarke (2020), Creswell (2013), Campbell et al. (2021), and Miles et al. (2014). Lastly, the chapter will give a detailed summary of the ethical considerations used for the study based on UWS Ethics Committee guidelines.

5.2 Case Study Research Method

The nature of the research question usually determines the type of methodology to be used for the research. The purpose of a case study research method is to conduct an enquiry that aims to investigate a phenomenon and gather in-depth knowledge without distorting the context of the

research. The case study research method is also a holistic, in-depth investigation that is adopted and used in contexts such as education (Gulsecen and Kubat, 2006), sociology (Grassel and Schirmer, 2006), and community-based problems (Johnson, 2006) like poverty, unemployment, and illiteracy. Tellis' (1997) view is that this method uses quantitative and qualitative data to explain the process and outcome of a phenomenon by observing, interviewing, and analysing the cases under investigation. In areas like education, the case study research method is used to evaluate the usefulness of educational programmes and policies where quantitative methods alone are not sufficient to reveal all relevant data. The case study research method aims to deeply retrieve more information through various data sources to analyse a situation that is of interest to the researcher (Yin, 2009; Farquhar, 2012).

The two main approaches to case study research are explanatory research and exploratory research. According to Imas (2009), the explanatory case study research method creates and investigates a link among research constructs and involves multi-methods in analysing data. It is valuable when conducting a causal research study and employs several cases to examine a plurality of influences (Rahim and Daud, 2015). On the other hand, the exploratory case study works well with social sciences research (Ogawa and Malen, 1991; Yin, 1991). It aims to define the research questions and hypotheses and determine the possibility of the research procedure. According to Rahim and Daud (2015), this is done by gathering data and fieldwork. This type of case study is used for conducting emerging areas of research (Rahim and Daud, 2015) that involve innovation and originality. This is useful in the new area of sustainable economic growth.

This research entailed observing events, reviewing documents, conducting interviews, and collecting other relevant data through questionnaires in a manner that did not affect the phenomenon. The study also focused on 'assessing the role of education as a tool for Nigeria's

sustainable economic growth' and adopted the exploratory case study research type. Sustainability, sustainable economic growth, and sustainable development goals are new areas of research and focus on constructs used to explain these concepts. The conceptual framework (which is discussed in chapter six of this study) has been developed by the researcher to provide an in-depth understanding of the research and it is observed that there is a relationship between each or more of them. The case study method has been conducted in four phases – the foundation phase; the pre-field phase; the field phase; and the reporting phase.

5.3 Justification for the use of case study research method

Iacono, et al. (2009) justify the use of case studies as the preferred research strategy when the phenomenon being investigated cannot be separated from its context. While the focus is on events, the experience of the researcher and research participant is also important. In this research study, the case study method is used to explain, understand and explore 'how' and 'why' a phenomenon, within a particular context, is what it is. The case study was used in this research as the context of sustainable economic growth which is explored in this research is happening in the present and therefore, affecting the future (Schoch, 2020). Although it is a mixed study, much of this research used qualitative methods. This means that there was little or no control over what happened throughout the research process, as opposed to using only quantitative research that does not explore the 'how' and 'why' behind a phenomenon and can be manipulated based on the researcher's perceptions (Johnson and Christensen, 2008). According to Schoch (2020), qualitative data will be collected to describe the phenomenon and enhance overall understanding. Using the case study method for this research aims to provide 'an extensive and in-depth description of some social phenomenon' (Yin, 2018, p.4).

FOUNDATION PHASE

This is the first step in conducting this case study research. It will be difficult to understand the latter stages if this first stage is difficult.

5.4 Philosophical Consideration

The researcher's use of the philosophical pattern depends on an understanding of the ontology, epistemology, and paradigm choices (Denzin and Lincoln, 1998). This leads to the choice of the research methodology, whether quantitative – the use of numerical data (Maree, 2010) or qualitative – the use of descriptive data (Brynard et al., 2014). The mixed research approach was adopted (as against using only one type of method) to have a holistic understanding of the research problem of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This way, the researcher collected different views from participants as well as explored the relationships between the research constructs used. The views of participants were based on their understanding of the concept of quality education; government policies regarding education in Nigeria; school management practices; education as a holistic approach seen in the attitude, knowledge, and skills of students; and the relevant and up-to-date education needed for Nigeria's economic advancement. This qualitative and quantitative reasoning explained the data and led to the best understanding of the research phenomena (Mitchell, 2018). According to Santos et al. (2017), it is not possible to generate meanings using either quantitative or qualitative data; therefore the qualitative findings can be enriched by quantitative findings. These researchers further explain that qualitative data is used before the quantitative data to study and understand the new concept of sustainable economic growth in Nigeria – this is because new economic policies are being developed to achieve the nation's objective.

Mixed methods combines numerical and cognitive reasoning that lead to a ‘best answer’ that may not be sufficiently explained using other research methods (Mitchell, 2018). Therefore, in this study, Johnson et al. (2007, p.123) define mixed methods research ‘as the type of research in which the researcher or team of researchers combine elements of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (for instance, use of qualitative and quantitative viewpoints, data collection, analysis, inference techniques) for the broad purposes of breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration.’

The process of combining both qualitative and quantitative methods according to Greene et al. (1989), ensures that triangulating the results from questionnaires; interviews with teachers, students, management, and employers; observation; and school and government documents correspond with each other and provide a full and rich picture of the phenomena – although, the responses/views of each of these participants may vary in some instances. Philosophical models that exist within this research describe a single construct encompassing multiple perspectives (Maarouf, 2019). This is because no two people have identical experiences, therefore their worldviews can also not be identical. For example, what quality education means to the employers, teachers, students, management, parents, and other stakeholders; and what they would characterize as high or low quality of education within the school environment. In this case, quantitative research uncovered the relationship of this construct to other constructs in this context and also revealed meanings among the interviewed research participants through qualitative research (Bryman, 2006). Mixed methods can be used to examine different aspects of a single research question which provide fuller and richer information from different participants. For example, the construct of funding with its different aspects – ‘who funds education in Nigeria?’ or ‘are funds sufficiently allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development?’ – and the

construct of labour market demand with its different aspects – ‘are the students taught the required skills for the labour market?’ or ‘in what ways are the 4Cs reflected in the education of the learner?’

5.4.1 The Paradigmatic Stance

It was important to search for an appropriate paradigm in this research and provide justification for using it as opposed to the generally accepted paradigm choices for quantitative and qualitative methods separately. Four meanings have been identified with paradigms that are commonly used in discussions of social science methodology (Morgan, 2007). They are the researcher’s world view; an epistemological stance; shared beliefs among a community of researchers; and model examples of research. According to Johnson et al. (2007), mixed methods can be qualitatively driven (which relies on a qualitative, constructivist view of the research process), or quantitatively driven (relying on a quantitative, postpositivist view of the research process). However, the paradigm choice for this research is pragmatism (an ‘interactive’/equal-status study). The pragmatic worldview is seen to be compatible with and has more philosophical support for mixed methods research (Hall, 2013). Some researchers contend that at a deeper paradigm level or in its justification, quantitative and qualitative methods have opposing views because they represent different models of reality, truth, and the relationship between the investigator and the phenomenon being investigated (Smith and Heshusius, 1986; Guba, 1987). However, pragmatism defies this notion that quantitative and qualitative methodologies are incompatible because fundamental values can be shared and differences integrated to enlighten each other (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004).

The equal-status research is easily conducted when research is composed of quantitative and qualitative methods in which they continually interact and address one superordinate goal – which

is to expand and strengthen the conclusions from this research study and contribute to the literature (Schoonenboom and Burke Johnson, 2017). Pragmatism provides the epistemology and logic for combining both qualitative and quantitative methods, assumptions, and methods of collecting and analysing data (Johnson et al., 2007 and Creswell, 2014). This is done by examining the different aspects of a single research question to get more in-depth information based on the study design (Schoonenboom and Burke Johnson, 2017). Pragmatism does not only take on the nature of knowledge but uses individuals' experience to solve practical problems in the real world – in this case (Feilzer, 2010). An example of a real world problem is the issue of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The researcher's choice of pragmatism in this mixed methods research is based on the research questions that have been formulated and the overall purpose of the research – which is 'to explore the relationship between education and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.' Nigeria already has an active education system with government policies and human capital that guide this system. Therefore, functional pragmatism explains that the purpose of having scientific knowledge is to improve on this existing action of having an education system and develop innovative actions to make practical changes (Goldkuhl, 2008; 2012).

Hall (2013) has criticized pragmatism because it is not easily possible to justify the use of the mixed methods design from a methodological point of view as to 'what works' till this research thesis is completed and the findings interpreted. The research starts with an interesting thought or a question to be answered and an objective to answer the research question to add knowledge to this area of research regardless of the underlying philosophy (Biddle and Schafft, 2015; Creswell, 2014). However, mixed methods design embraces justifiable foundations that are important to this study. These foundations were used in a study by Dovona-Ope (2014) and were based on – focus on the research outcomes by emphasizing the importance of the questions; the need to gather

different views and voices from participants within the context of the study; and dedication to recommend and stimulate change within the Nigerian education sector as an outcome of this research.

Morgan (2014a), Tashakkori and Teddlie (2008) note that pragmatism exists as an objective reality and poses a different meaning from human experience. However, this reality is grounded in the real world and is only gotten through human experience. It is difficult to determine the concept of reality because pragmatists view reality according to their experiences, beliefs, habits, and generally what works and is acceptable over time (Baker and Schaltegger, 2015). As a researcher, meaning is based on own experience, the experience and the needs of the participants in the context of this research, and the desired outcomes, rather than on a priori philosophical argument. According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (2008), a positivist researcher would define an object as what it is being used for; or a constructivist researcher would define an object based on his perspective. However, as a pragmatic researcher, an object would be defined based on how it would achieve the purpose of the research. For example, a researcher would view a school as a business venture if it is intended for profit-making; an institution of learning to impart knowledge to students; a platform for value/skills creation to create a locally and globally inclined workforce; or as a corporate responsibility aimed at contributing to the development of the society. Therefore, for this research, the researcher views a school as a platform for value/skills creation to create a locally and globally inclined workforce. 'Pragmatism affords a flexible approach to data interpretation to be of best use to answer the research question' (Morgan, 2014a, p.1049). An inquiry can be effective only if it achieves its purpose (Hothersall, 2019).

5.4.2 The Ontological Stance

The principle of ontology says that the researcher needs to have a clear understanding of reality to make the right methodological choices (Lohse, 2017, p.7). On the other hand, ontology is an overlooked aspect of the pragmatic philosophy because pragmatism is usually seen as epistemological and methodological stances, not as a whole integrated paradigm (Al-Saadi, 2014). Johnson and Christensen (2012) mention that mixed research has both subjective and objective interpretations of reality. This means that in the research, one reality exists and individuals have different views of this reality. It is therefore important to understand the participants' viewpoints without being biased or affecting the phenomenon under investigation. The unclear ontological position of pragmatism makes it difficult for a pragmatic researcher to be either subjective or objective in research (Maarouf, 2019). However, for this research, 'education' exists in an objective sense and covers different perspectives because the actors within the education system behave as if it is objective reality in the same way as currency in the banking system.

According to Maarouf (2019), the ontological stance uses the reality cycle which explains that an idea exists and there are different opinions of this reality in the participants' minds. There is only one reality in a certain context at a certain time and this reality changes when the context changes thereby changing the perceptions of humans. Humans' perception of reality controls their actions. Interactions among these actions generate new perspectives within a period and generating a new perspective creates a new reality. Although these changes in the perspective occur constantly, it does not have immediate practical effect. In the same way, notable changes in government or economic policies affecting education have notable realistic effects in the long run. This reality is stable most of the time but changes periodically.

When reality is stable – as regards the fact that quality education requires adequate funding – the reality cycle adopts one reality view and uses the quantitative approach to test a theory about reality. Testing a theory means that there is minimal knowledge about the phenomenon under investigation and its context; therefore variables are developed and measured, hypotheses tested and generalizations made. This matches the pragmatic notion of ‘what works’ (Hall, 2013). On the other hand, when there are regular changes to reality – for example, if the curriculum is restructured to fit the modern-day learning, it becomes impossible to generalise because of changes in the context. This means that these theories need to be constantly reviewed to make sure they remain valid and represent the truth. A new theory is created when these theories become obsolete or when research is conducted in a new context. In this case, the reality uses the qualitative approach to examine participants’ views of reality. This provides a deep understanding of the context of reality, develops new theories, or reviews the current theories. Once the theory is developed the pragmatic researcher can switch back to the one reality position and test the theory through quantitative research (Maarouf, 2019).

5.4.3 The Epistemological Stance

The epistemology of pragmatism views the world based on social experiences. Knowledge is distinct and is created by an individual’s unique experiences. Historically, according to Dewey (1931, 1938), epistemology or “theory of inquiry” involves the human effort to understand some aspects of reality to change or improve that part of reality. The question then is ‘what is economic growth and in what way can Nigeria’s economic growth be improved?’. The researcher’s view is that Dewey’s inquiry is concerned with understanding the relationship between what actions we make in improving education for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth and the consequences of

these actions. The theory of inquiry helps us to plan and use our experiences to gain more control and achieve desired outcomes as opposed to using trial and error (Biesta, 2010).

Education provides a means of creating experiences by interaction within the school environment for an individual's holistic development, skills acquisition, and preparation for the labour market (Osagie, 2014). This interaction encourages experiential learning and forms 'habits', which according to Biesta (2010) is another concept of pragmatism. As individuals, we are capable of establishing and maintaining a dynamic interaction with our environment. The process of establishing and maintaining this interaction forms our habit. Our habits then become a learning process of trial and error through which we acquire a complex but flexible set of habits for action (Biesta, 2010) without opportunities for decision making. In opposition to habit, an enquiry is a self-conscious process of decision making (Morgan, 2014b) using intelligent action through previous experiences rather than blind trial and error to achieve the desired consequences (Biesta, 2010).

Decision-making is needed in both everyday enquiry and research. Research needs more careful attention and intentional decision-making to evaluate likely consequences (Morgan, 2014a, 2014b). As a pragmatist researcher, it was important to consider the potential consequences of designing and conducting this research in a particular way (Morgan, 2014a). The researcher's prior experience of working in the education sector draws attention to some lapses for which there was no solution at the time. This was mainly seen in the insufficiency of funds and unstable government policies running the system. This has influenced the researcher's choice of the mixed methods design to gather all necessary information and have a better understanding of the context of the research. The researcher's interaction with the research participants further probed these issues and helped me to proffer possible solutions. It was helpful for the researcher to keep a diary of all

activities in the field to capture all ‘in the moment’ thoughts and feelings when collecting data. The potential consequences of choosing the mixed methods research are therefore based on the original research question – How well do education providers in Nigeria align provision with the SDG of quality and access to education? – and the purpose of the research study – to explore the relationship between education and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. It was important to compare and contrast the research question with the philosophical considerations (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2008) and to note the usefulness of the philosophical assumptions, the methodology, and the data in generating the anticipated outcomes (Goles and Hirschheim, 2000).

5.4.4 Enquiry techniques consideration

Two common inquiry techniques are quantitative and qualitative methods. Positivist research is linked to quantitative research method associated with reliability and generalizability; or interpretivist research which is linked to qualitative research method associated with dependability and credibility or a mixed approach (Denzin and Lincoln, 1998). Combining quantitative and qualitative methods was done using the convergent parallel design method. The qualitative and quantitative data were collected and merged equally, simultaneously, and independently, mixed the results during interpretation, and analysed results by looking out for contradictions and/or relationships between the two sources of data (Bian, 2018).

Figure 6 Convergent parallel design method

Material redacted due to copyright restrictions. Figure can be found: Bian, H. (2018) 'Office for Faculty Excellence', *Mixed Methods Research*.
<https://www.scribd.com/document/216825927/Mixed-Methods-Research>

Source: Bian (2018)

The researcher collected and analysed two independent aspects of quantitative and qualitative data in a single phase. The quantitative aspect is the statistical scores gotten from teachers' knowledge and skills for the 21st century and how sufficient funds are allocated to other elements of education. The qualitative aspect is the analysis of the feasibility of government and management policies for education, teaching and learning methodology, student outcomes, and observation of the aids and methods used in the teaching and learning process.

5.4.5 Research logic consideration

Induction and deduction are the two common research logics in social sciences research. While Lincoln and Guba (1985) believe that the logic for qualitative and quantitative research are incompatible; Patton (1990), on the other hand, believes that an open-minded researcher can combine both the research logics. As opposed to induction and deduction, abduction generalises from the interactions between the specific and the general (Dudovskiy, 2016) through critical

thinking. Pragmatism produces useful knowledge and serves as a support and rationale for the use of abductive reasoning (Mitchell, 2018).

Mabsout (2015) argues that regular updates of social reality means that economic theories even if they are correct and applicable today, need to be constantly updated, revised, or abandoned. The use of abductive reasoning, therefore, means that the research process starts with ‘surprising facts’ that must be explained. These facts were seen when the theories of economic growth, for example, did not give a proper explanation to discoveries the researcher encountered in the course of collecting data for this research. Therefore, abductive reasoning generated hypotheses by combining both numerical and cognitive reasoning and offered me the ‘best’ answer to explain the ‘surprising facts’ (Kovács and Spens, 2005). ‘Surprising facts’ may be, for instance, sudden changes or modifications in government policies that affect how the education system operates in Nigeria.

Combining methods and using abductive reasoning leads to better evaluations and robust conclusions (Davenport, 2009). In most cases and particularly in this research, it is not a good decision to make predictions based on past data or theories. This research focused on a guide linking the present and the future, therefore it was the best decision to create new data and analysis because some past data or theories are obsolete and not applicable to the present and future state of education and economic growth in Nigeria.

PRE-FIELD PHASE

5.5 Decide

The first step in this phase was to determine whether the case study method was a suitable choice for gathering evidence. Jarvensivu and Tornroos (2010) suggest that the case study method is applicable in business relationships and networks. According to Baxter and Jack (2008), the case study research design helps to explore the phenomenon of education for sustainable economic growth within the context of Nigeria using a variety of quantitative and qualitative data sources to uncover multiple viewpoints considering the phenomenon to recommend actions and create a difference (Kaarbo and Beasley, 1999).

5.6 Case study protocol

The case study protocol is a document that captures all procedures involved in collecting relevant data. It includes the research method, research questions, ethical considerations, permission seeking, and interpretation process (Yin, 2009). The case study protocol is particularly applicable in real-world projects like the education sector in Nigeria. Below is a flow chart of the steps that were taken in the course of this research study for clarity.

Figure 7 Flow chart of the case study protocol

Source: The Researcher

For this research, the researcher adopted the idea of Stake (1995) to develop a template for the case study protocol. In his research, he uses a more interpretive approach to discuss case study protocol and involves evaluating education policies:

5.6.1 Criteria for selection of cases

This is an intrinsic case as it is the object of interest itself. Stake explains that the case study research is holistic and maintains an inseparable link or interrelationship between the phenomenon and the context being studied. Although the literature argues for an unbiased, objective approach in collecting and analysing data, the researcher's position as neither an insider nor an outsider brought about the choice of this research and a compatible interaction with the participants because

of life experiences gained within the context. Therefore, the primary and secondary data collected and selection of cases were done to fit the research context; the participants that fitted into the inclusion criteria; and the lapses encountered in the Nigerian education sector have informed this research study. Adopting Kanuha's (2000) idea in this case, meaning was expressed through shared understanding of unsaid comments, hints, and incomplete sentences.

5.6.2 Research questions, issues, and information questions

Issues may specify possible cause-effect relationships or potential problems that may arise if certain actions are not taken. It was important to note that to achieve desired goals within the education sector and the Nigerian economy, there are causes of action that should be taken within the educational institutions. It is not possible to give answers to the research question as it may become repetitive, therefore during this research, certain questions were asked (with some prompts) to provide more detailed information rather than the main research question only.

5.6.3 Data gathering

This was done by listing out the type of questions that were asked in the questionnaires and interviews. These questions provided a deeper understanding of the concept of this research. The researcher categorised the questionnaires and interviews to fit each participant. Questionnaires were distributed while focus groups and semi-structured interviews were conducted with the students, teachers, management, and employers. This was because some elements of the study required specific answers from each of the participants. School documents were also reviewed to get a deeper understanding of the study and complement the answers provided by the participants. Before the data gathering phase, it was important for the researcher to take note of ethical guidelines needed to have access to the schools for field visits. The ethical consideration section

is seen towards the end of this chapter. This research also got ethics approval from the University before the field phase.

5.6.4 Analysis and interpretation

This considered aggregation of data by categories or direct interpretation. Descriptive statistics have been used to analyse the quantitative data gotten from questionnaires. Results from the data were a list of points for and against drawn from the research questions and the issues that have been addressed. Qualitative data have been presented and analysed using thematic analysis. Triangulation uses different techniques to collect data within a study to confirm that the data achieved is the same as the expected data. It ensures the validity of the case study research using multiple sources and techniques in the data collection process (Yin, 2009). Triangulation involves bringing together data collection methods, theories, data sources, and investigators to confirm the information being researched. This section is further discussed in the latter part of this chapter.

5.6.5 Case study researcher role

Having previous work experience within the education sector has made the researcher familiar with all procedures to follow before gaining access to the field for visits. This was to ensure confidentiality. However, the researcher acted as a participant-observer using the ‘enquiry from the outside’ approach (Evered and Louis, 2001) formally as a doctoral research student to interact with the participants. This research investigation has been conducted overtly; therefore the researcher, interests, and intentions were identified by the participants in this research study, and they were informed of the nature and scope of the investigation. The researcher engaged in the constant process of narrowing down the research topic, checked and improved the questions, and used the most appropriate research method for this study. Although there is a personal relationship

with some of the participants, the researcher ensured that the research process was based on trust so that the participants can give accurate information without bias or influence, and that all data gathered have been analysed objectively (Iacono et al., 2009). In the course of this research, care has been taken to fully display the evidence, objectively analyse the evidence, compare it with existing literature, triangulate data sources following the methodology, eliminate alternative interpretations, and produce a case. Through this, the reader can express his/her own opinion to follow the arguments raised and assess the validity of the findings (Iacono et al., 2009).

5.6.6 Report writing

Writing the reports at the end of the research process includes organising the report during the data collection process, identifying potential readers, telling a story (the organisational structure of the report), and briefly describing practically what happened at each stage of the process.

As recommended by Brereton et al. (2008), the researcher constructed a template to plan the case studies. Issues arising were discussed in synergy with the case study context and goals. In the analysis and discussion stage, further case studies were developed while discussing the current case.

Table 7 Case Study Themes

The table below shows the case study themes which have been developed and designed by the researcher based on the research questions and the data findings.

Case Study Themes	ID	Research Question
Quality of education	RQ3	In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria? (Quality of education is a holistic approach embedded in the curriculum and is achieved in student engagement, ethics, school management policies and practices, local and global relevance, and school and community interaction) UNESCO (2014).
Problems facing education	RQ1	How does funding in middle/low income private schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
Government policies	RQ3	How well do education policies in Nigeria align provision with the SDG of quality and access to education?
Labour market demand	RQ2	How does management practices within middle/low income private schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
Teaching and learning aids	RQ4	How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?
Access to education		How well do education providers in Nigeria align provision with the SDG of quality and access to education?
Problems facing human capital availability	RQ2	How does management practices within middle/low income private schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?

FIELD PHASE

5.7 Contact

Before collecting the data, the researcher was involved in the data generation and interpretation throughout the research process. There was some form of interaction between the researcher and the participants when reviewing the schools' documents and when questionnaires were filled out.

Conducting semi-structured interviews brought about two-way communication. Some of the questions were rephrased to ensure understanding and get further information about the context being discussed. This ensured a smooth process and built rapport between the researcher and participants (Perecman and Curran, 2006). The researcher's previous work experience and familiarity with the school environment gave me the added advantage to access the schools and collect the required data that has been used for this research.

5.7.1 Questionnaire

The questionnaire is not only related to positivist and post-positivist philosophies. However, the use of questionnaires within the pragmatist philosophy used for this research focused mainly on providing the best opportunity for answering the research questions (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Questionnaires have been used as the research mechanism containing a chain of questions to get information to which participants respond by writing out their answers (deVaus, 2002). A justification for using questionnaires is that it will allow the opportunity to explore trends in attitudes and opinions of participants within the sample which will then be triangulated with the qualitative data to generate generalisable findings. According to Akinici and Saunders (2015), for a questionnaire to be functional and up to standard, it must collect the specific data that is needed to answer the research questions and achieve the research objectives; the questions should be easy for the participants to understand and provide the necessary information to make it easy for the researcher to record the information gotten; it should possess the most accurate and complete information; and the questionnaire should not include jargons, acronyms and other terminologies which the participants are not familiar with. The questionnaires used in this study considered all ethical issues which were stated clearly in the consent form and participant information sheet. The

questionnaires were handed over directly to the respondents; after which, they were returned to the researcher.

The validity and reliability of the data require the researcher to review the literature carefully, discuss ideas widely, and conceptualise the research before designing the questionnaire (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2010). When developing the questionnaire, the questions were put in a logical order to measure a specific concept and were designed to fit each category of the participants to answer the questions. Foddy (1994, p.17) emphasizes that ‘the question must be understood by the respondent in the way intended by the researcher and the answer given by the respondent must be understood by the researcher in the way intended by the respondent.’ It allowed for a more in-depth focus on the phenomenon because the samples were only used to statistically represent the population being studied (Schoch, 2020). The questionnaires were succinct and designed by the researcher based on the conceptual framework with constructs used as headlines for the questions. These constructs are quality of education, funding, economic growth, government policies, school policies and practices, and labour market demand. They included multiple-choice, dichotomous, and Likert-type scale questions. The questionnaire only aimed to answer the research objectives and was not beyond the scope of the research. The researcher did not find standard questionnaires that provided a framework for the research and therefore used the study to explore the research context and develop new knowledge. Boynton and Greenhalgh (2004) justify this method when there is no ‘off the peg’ (p.1313) questionnaire available. As an exploratory study, the questionnaire did not ask questions directly from the research questions or previous research or questionnaires. Rather, the researcher asked questions separately to analyse the relationships between the constructs and create a story from the data gathered (Rowley, 2014).

5.7.2 Interviews

Semi-structured and focus group interviews have been used for this research study. The interview questions were given to the participants to have an idea of issues discussed before the agreed date/time of the interview. Setting up the semi-structured interviews meant that there were agenda for the interview guide, an outline of planned topics, and questions to be addressed. This allowed for a flexible and interactive approach to the discussion. The interview guide may be subject to change when feedback is gotten or when adjustments are made to the questions (Galletta, 2013). Interview topics were centred around the curriculum; government policies; socio-economic and extra-curricular activities of the school; challenges to funding; teaching and learning aids/methods; managers' expectations regarding teachers' professional qualifications; and school management policies. The sequence of questions may be rethought for subsequent interviews when important and unanticipated issues emerge. With the permission of the participant and assurance of confidentiality, interviews were recorded to ensure that the researcher was actively engaged in the conversation, had detailed information, and pondered on the next question rather than struggling to concentrate on taking notes (Adams, 2015).

Preparation for the interview was important. It was necessary for the researcher to know the questions thoroughly, understand the purpose of each question, and the priority level of each question in the overall research. The interviews were conducted remotely and took casual, conversational approaches that were neither overly cold nor overly familiar. Leech (2002) notes that the researcher should appear generally knowledgeable, in a humble, open-minded way, not coming across as more skilled in the research area than the respondent but making sure to understand the views of the participant. During the interview, the researcher must listen actively, ask for an elaboration of a point and when necessary, repeat in one or two sentences using mainly

the participant's own words, what was just said (Adams, 2015). This shows that the researcher is intently interested and understands a point that has been discussed. It was important to build consent, rapport, respect, and trust by ensuring that the research was carried out with the participants and not on them (Nagy Hesse-Biber, 2013).

Semi-structured interviews and focus group sessions were conducted and categorized among the employers, management, teachers, and students. Semi-structured interviews are more flexible and allow for a better understanding of the interviewee's perspective (Dane, 2010). It also allows for a refocus on the question or prompt for more information when something interesting emerges. Under privacy and ethical guidelines, only the schools' prefects in the senior class were interviewed. Protocols for the interview process are useful to ensure consistency of the interviews across the individuals being interviewed (Schoch, 2020). Different protocols have been used for the different groups in this research – employers, school management, teachers, and students. Maintaining rapport between the researcher and the participants was seen in eye contact, verbal nods, understanding of the research aims, emotional connection, attentiveness, and friendliness. This encouraged interaction, the richness of the data, and a better understanding of the subject of the research (Seidman, 2013). Towards the end of the interview session, the researcher reviewed the interview guide to ensure that no key questions were missed. At the end of the interview, a short 'Thank You' letter was sent to the participants acknowledging them for their helpful comments.

5.7.3 Observation

During the data collection phase, the researcher watches and takes note of how the research participants behave within and relate to their physical environment as it unfolds (Mays and Pope, 1995). Observation provides an understanding of how participants interact with each other;

demonstrates the entire research framework; captures the process and context; and informs about the influence of the physical environment (Mulhall, 2003). The observation method provided a chance to learn things that the participants were unwilling to discuss in the interviews. It is also important to take note of all ethical issues when conducting observations. The observation method was conducted remotely. For example, there was a virtual tour of the classrooms, libraries, and laboratories. Some of the classroom activities and field trips were also observed remotely. Protocols are used in observations and help for a better understanding of what was looked for and how the observational methods provided answers to the research questions.

5.7.4 Documents

Bowen (2009) answers the question of how many documents the researcher should gather. There should be a wide choice of quality documents to make sure that there is an adequate source of information. Relevant documents have also been reviewed to complement the data from questionnaires and interviews. The documents reviewed are listed below:

Table 8 Outline of documents used for data collection

Documents	
Curriculum	School Timetable
Minutes of meetings	School policy documents
Staff and student handbook	School reports
Training materials	Academic calendars
Newsletters	Government data, reports, policy documents
Financial records	Inventory records
Marking scheme	Exam question papers, records
Employment letters	Staff job description
Key Performance Indicators	School flyers

These documents are accessible and provide a reliable source of information because they portray an authentic interpretation of the participants and an argument based on strong evidence (Bowen, 2009). The justification for the use of documents is that they can be read and reviewed several times and remain unchanged irrespective of the research process (Bowen, 2009). Analysing these documents incorporated coding the content into themes similar to what was analysed from the interview transcripts (Bowen, 2009). Document analysis supported the purpose of triangulations to provide a collection of evidence for credibility. The documents eliminated potential bias by examining information collected through different methods. The documents used for this study were scanned and the soft copies were sent by email. The documents outlined below show what data was analysed based on the research questions:

Table 9 Relevance of documents for data analysis

Documents to analyse	Relevance to research questions
Staff/student handbook	Teaching/learning aids and methods
Academic calendars	School routine including classes, excursions, co-curricular activities like clubs, open days
Curriculum and timetable	Relevance for 21 st century skills and labour market
Mission statement and policy manuals	School policies and regulations in line with the government's requirement
Annual reports	Includes reports on schools' progress, funding, goals, and strategies for sustainability
Training materials	Teachers' qualification and ability to impart knowledge to the learners for human capital generation

Source: The Researcher

Using the 8-step planning process by O’Leary (2014), documentation was needed to ensure reliable results:

- a. Create a list of texts to explore (as seen in the documents listed earlier);
- b. Consider how texts will be accessed with a focus on linguistic or cultural barriers. Considering the educational difference between the UK and Nigeria, there were opportunities for participants to ask questions for clarification.
- c. Acknowledge and address biases by clearly defining the purpose and outcome of the research to the participants. The original purpose of the data in the documents collected was evaluated.
- d. Develop appropriate skills for research. Skills for research have been taught and developed in the first year of this Doctoral program.
- e. Consider strategies for ensuring credibility. Credibility links the research study’s findings with reality to demonstrate truth and trustworthiness. This has been done through triangulation of data collection methods, and member-checking where the data are shared with the participants to clarify their intentions, correct errors, and provide any necessary additional information.
- f. Know the data being searched for: relating to school/management policies and practices, quality of teachers and their responsibilities, government policies affecting school operation.
- g. Consider ethical issues. Ethical issues have been addressed in the UWS ethics form and confidential documents were read and signed by the participants.
- h. Have a backup plan. Permission will be sought from the participants to have e-copies of the documents collected.

5.8 Interact

The case study method involved a range of data collection methods to properly answer the research questions. This was done through semi-structured interviews, observations, and documentation (Yin, 2009). The combination of these sources of data collection adds richness and authenticity to the study being carried out (Flick et al., 2004). Field notes were an essential part of this research and were used to document vital information to enhance the data and add richness to the research context (Creswell, 2013). These notes were used to document the researcher's on-the-spot impressions, descriptions of the study context, the encounters with participants, interviews and focus group sessions, and interactions within the field. This documentation prompted the researcher to observe the participants' behaviours, identify any potential bias, and encourage reflection on the findings.

The field notes were in the form of sketch notes and were divided into field notes about the study context and field notes about interviews and focus groups (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2017). Field notes about the context of the study included basic information about the research – study title, researcher's experiences, data collection methods, location of the study, and critical reflection of the study. Field notes about interviews and focus groups included the setting of the interview, the appearance and behaviour of the participants, participants' responses to the interviews, and the researcher's critical reflection on the interview and focus group sessions (Berger, 2015). These field notes were taken in the course of interviews and placed with the interview transcript for easy use and analysis.

REPORTING PHASE

5.9 Triangulation and case study reporting

The reporting phase is as important as the data collection and interpretation. According to Denzin and Lincoln (1998), a sound report structure is crucial to case study reporting. It includes descriptions of the case, participants' views on the case, relationship descriptions, researcher's notes of the field protocols, data interpretation and analysis, and conclusion (Rashid et al., 2019).

Data serve as the basis for a research study. For this research, the case study method used questionnaires, interviews, observations, and document analysis as data collection methods. In this research method, the interview process was semi-structured (Rahim and Daud, 2015) and allowed a less rigid and flexible response to the questions and an interaction of emerging views between the researcher and participants (Yin, 2009; Yin, 2011). Collecting data relating to the quality of education, for example, was best done through interviews because the concept of 'quality' had different meanings to the school managers, teachers, students, and employers.

Merriam (1988) suggests that an effective researcher has the responsibility to immediately take notes of any occurrence during interviews or documentation to be sure that the observation is accurately captured and understood. Analysis of teaching and learning aids was done through observational methods. Notes were taken of specific aids used by the teachers and students in the classroom or in extra-curricular activities, their availability, and how well they were used. In addition to the questionnaires and interviews, relevant documents depending on availability were reviewed by the researcher to support the validity of the data (Rahim and Daud, 2015). Relevant documents were used for this research study and were used in conjunction with the interview data (Willet, 2009). Therefore, as the researcher, it was important to keep an open mind to make necessary adjustments in subsequent interviews and the study design. Case study research is often

linked with the evidence (qualitative data), types of data collection methods (ethnography), and the research strategy.

Triangulation in the case study method is used to find various sources to confirm relevant information (Rahim and Daud, 2015). It uses different data collection methods within one study to confirm that the data achieved is the same as the expected data and ensures the validity of the case study research using multiple sources and techniques in the data gathering process (Yin, 2009). Triangulation involves bringing together data collection methods, theories, data sources, and investigators to confirm the information being researched. Hammersley (1996) says that triangulation uses quantitative research to confirm the qualitative findings meaning that the data is validated if it converges with data derived from another source. Triangulation, therefore, minimises bias and supports a finding by showing that independent measures or constructs either agree at least or do not oppose themselves (Miles and Huberman, 1984).

According to Harling (2012), the case study research method combines quantitative and qualitative data collection and data analysis techniques. Quantitative research searches for explanations using 'why', while qualitative research searches for in-depth meaning and understanding using 'how' or 'what'. The choice of using qualitative research or quantitative research or both was solely dependent on the research question(s) as the research questions framed the methodology used and the results. Data sets gotten from the quantitative and qualitative methods were analysed independently by the researcher, comparing the separate results or transforming one data type to fit the other (Clark et al., 2008). Although the different data sets appeared to be the same, the findings have built a fuller picture of how education supports sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, the results were investigated to identify irregularities and causes of the conflict.

Mixed methods (a combination of qualitative and quantitative research) were preferred in this study as they used the strengths of each method and combined different levels of techniques, methods, strategies, and theories (Saunders et al., 2009). When mixed methods are used, the researcher can investigate more complicated research questions and gather richer information or evidence that cannot be achieved using any single method alone. The results of the two different data sets can be either combined to achieve more comprehensive results or qualitative data is connected to the quantitative data and vice versa (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). The steps to analyse data in case study research must follow a logical sequence. Yin (2003a) explains that data analysis consists of categorizing, examining, testing, tabulating, and recombining both qualitative and quantitative evidence to address the initial purpose of the study. The process of data analysis in a mixed study shows which data can be analysed first and the reason why one data should come first before the other (Kohlbacher, 2006). When both sets of data are analysed at the same time, the researcher also explains the reason for this at the analysis stage.

The data collected through questionnaires, interviews, observations, and documents in this study were triangulated by confirming that the data corresponded with the desired outcome of the research. This was done by taking notes of participants' comments about the case study report. This was to ensure the validity of the data collected in this process (Yin, 2009). The researcher adopted Wargo's (2014) study to suggest a three-step approach to triangulate the data.

Step One: Interviews were conducted and recorded. A recording is recommended as opposed to note-taking to ensure that all information is taped and further questions can be asked for clarification when the participants' views are vague.

Step Two: The recordings were transcribed and returned to the participants for their review and approval. Vogt (2005) calls this authentication to ensure the accuracy of the data.

Step Three: The research findings were converted into themes for further discussion.

The data was gathered in a variety of ways to prevent bias, build up a better picture, and reflect changes in the participants' experience. Using different methods to investigate the same course does not mean that the findings generated will be consistent or complement each other. The reason for triangulation, therefore, was to study and understand when and why there were differences (Patton, 1980). Attempting to make sense of the research findings required strengthening the data with a holistic understanding of the investigation and a general knowledge of the phenomenon (Mathison, 1988).

5.10 Recruiting Participants for this Study

It was important to ensure that the participants used for this study were all within the inclusion criteria. A formal letter of invitation was written to each school, through the Principal, to seek their consent to use the school, the teachers, students, and management for this research study. The Principals responded to this letter in writing. Invitation letters were given to three Board members (the employers) - Owner, Chairman, Vice Chairman, and Human Resource Manager to participate in this research. They responded to this letter in writing. Invitation letters were also given to the management staff – Principal, Vice-Principal (Academics), and Heads of Departments. They also responded to this letter in writing.

There were posters around each school to inform students and teachers of the researcher's intention to perform a research study and to welcome those who wanted to take part in the research. The call to participate was for students (in the final year class) for focus group interviews; teachers (for interviews and focus groups). This was on a first-come, first-served basis. Teachers who

volunteered to participate in the research were all on the same level in the schools' organisation structure to avoid any form of bias while conducting the interviews.

5.11 Sample Size

The research took place in three private secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Nigeria namely – ACMGS, Elelenwo; BCMSS, Rumuobiokani; and WOF, Woji. The justification for using these schools is that: ACMGS, Elelenwo was originally owned by the Rivers State Government (for which Port Harcourt is the State Capital) but was returned formally to voluntary individuals and religious organisations in 2005 to be privately run as a cure for the education crisis (Gabriel, 2005) since government take-over of schools in the 1970s. The other two schools were also given to the Owners to be professionally run and managed. It was important for the researcher to study how these schools are managed privately as opposed to being managed by the government.

Another justification for using the schools is that the researcher has familiarity with the city of Port Harcourt and the schools from previous work experience. Also, Port Harcourt is the fifth most populous city and an economic hub in Nigeria because of its very rich oil reserve and industrial centres³¹. The city values education as it houses most of Nigeria's top secondary schools and universities and therefore has the potential to contribute to reviving the Nigerian system of education³².

Furthermore, the schools were used by the researcher because of resource constraints. While resource constraints result in complications, Hansen et al (1953) argue that no survey is designed without cost constraints. The resource constraints were seen in the restricted time to complete the thesis and expectation to complete multiple research milestones within this timeframe, and

³¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kano_\(city\)#Economy](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kano_(city)#Economy)

³² Umesi, E. (2020) *What the education system is like in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria*. Available at: <https://pedagogue.app/what-the-education-system-is-like-in-port-harcourt-rivers-state-nigeria/> (Accessed: 16 April 2022).

financial constraints that influenced the sample size. Therefore, it was justifiable to limit this research study to only three secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Only students in final year classes were used in each school. This is because they are all 16 years old and above and therefore did not require parental consent and ethical consideration to conduct the research. 4 to 6 students from each school were invited to participate in the focus group interviews. This number of students was to save time during the interview process, make sure that the interview is orderly, encourage the students to be open and comfortable to discuss issues among themselves and the researcher, and so that the researcher can take records of all the necessary issues discussed.

The research which is based on the context of education for economic growth used the curriculum, quality of teachers, marking scheme, school environment, and government/management policies. Therefore, only teachers fitted into the inclusion criteria for this research. The researcher invited all the teachers from each school to fill out the questionnaires in the data collection phase. It was important to have different options depending on the researcher's experience in the field during the research. 5 teachers from each school were invited to participate in the semi-structured interviews and 4 to 6 teachers for the focus groups. Class teachers were selected to take part in the interviews because they have direct closeness with the students and are more aware of the complaints and behaviours of the students. These teachers are on the same level in the schools' organisation structure to ensure that they were comfortable discussing issues relating to the research without the fear of being reported to the management.

Questionnaires were distributed to the management staff of each school – which include the Principal, Vice Principals, and Heads of Departments. There are 11 management staff in 2 of the 3 schools (ACMGS and BCMSS). This comprises the Principal, 4 Vice Principals (2 each for the

junior and senior schools), and 6 Heads of Departments. The third school (WOF) has 9 management staff – the Principal, 2 Vice principals (1 each for junior and senior schools), and 6 Heads of Departments. This is a total of 31 management staff to fill out the questionnaire.

Seven management staff from the first two schools were invited to participate in the interview process – the principal, vice principals, and 2 heads of departments. While 5 management staff from the third school were invited to participate in the interview process – the principal, vice principals, and 2 heads of departments. This is because they are part of the School’s Board and are familiar with the decision-making process and organisation of the school. A total of 9 members of the Governing Board (employers) were invited to participate in the interview process. The breakdown is – 3 members of the Governing Board of each school (the employers) comprising the Proprietor (Owner), the Chairman, and the Human Resource Manager.

For clarity and easy understanding, this is summarised in the table below:

Table 10 Sample Size

	ACMGS, Port Harcourt	BCMS, Port Harcourt	WOF, Port Harcourt	Total
	Number of Participants			
SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS				
Teachers	5	5	5	15
Management	7	7	5	19
Employers	3	3	3	9
FOCUS INTERVIEWS GROUP				
Students	4-6	4-6	4-6	12-18
Teachers	4-6	4-6	4-6	12-18
QUESTIONNAIRES				
Teachers	All Teachers			
Management	11	11	9	31

5.12 Data Collection

The multiple sources of data that were used in the case study method were gotten from the different categories of participants and other sources. The research questions usually determine the kinds of questions to be asked in questionnaires and interviews, what to observe, and what documents to review (Yin, 2018). As indicated by Stake (1995), the research questions guide what happens in the field – from gaining access to triangulating data. Purposeful sampling was used for distributing the questionnaires as it is mainly used for quantitative research. It is necessary for the researcher to establish the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the research participants when designing high-quality research protocols. Designing the appropriate inclusion and exclusion criteria evaluates how the decision will impact the external validations of the results of the research. Inclusion criteria are the set of predefined characteristics used to identify subjects who are eligible to be

included in this research study. This includes teachers, schools in Nigeria, management, and employers of labour. However, the exclusion criteria include characteristics that disqualify participants from inclusion in the study and require their removal as subjects. For example, non-teaching staff, students who are in junior classes, and individuals/contexts that portray potential bias. For example, lack of parental consent and influences that provide distortion in the results of the study because of different opinions and experiences (Schoch, 2020).

It was necessary to keep a proper organisation of field notes, documents, questionnaire results, interview records and transcripts, and other materials. Records of the data collected were uploaded and stored in electronic storage systems. The data collected and the conclusions were tracked backward to ensure validity. There must be an alignment between the conclusions, the evidence, and the research questions (Schoch, 2020). Most times, data collection involves ‘a small invasion of personal privacy’ (Stake, 1995, p.57). This means that required permissions must be obtained, in form of informed consent and the university’s ethical approval, and how the final report will be used or distributed.

5.13 Data Analysis

5.13.1 Quantitative data analysis

Quantitative data have been captured using questionnaires with hard copies. The first step was to check that the returned questionnaires were suitable to be used for analysis. Questionnaires returned by participants may not be used if some pages of the questionnaire are missing, participants’ pattern of responses show that they either did not understand the questions or follow instructions, or the questionnaire has been answered by someone who is not in the inclusion criteria or a member of the sample size. In this case, the number of questionnaires that cannot be used are

normally insignificant and do not create a setback. However, if this happens, it will be reported in the findings and discussion stage of this research.

Editing the questionnaires involved verifying that the responses were consistent and accurate, making necessary corrections, and deciding whether some or all parts of the questionnaire should be discarded. Some of these checks include:

- a. Logical checks. For example, a primary school teacher claiming to be a secondary school teacher without the necessary knowledge and experience to teach a specific subject, or a teacher claiming to be a management staff;
- b. Response set checks. For example, a participant has ‘strongly agreed’ with every item on the Likert scale;
- c. Range checks. For example, a code of 6 is entered when there are only four response categories for the question.

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the survey data showing measures of frequency, central tendency, and variability. These measures are based on the different forms of questionnaires used in the data collection. Tables and graphs were also used as a support to illustrate points and to give an understanding of the qualitative data.

5.13.2 Qualitative data analysis

Case studies are in-depth examinations of complex events based on a thorough understanding of the phenomenon, extensive description of the phenomenon, and analysis of the phenomenon as a whole and in context. Analysing case study data ‘consists of examining, categorising, tabulating, testing or recombining evidence to draw empirically-based conclusions’ (Yin, 2009, p.126). Analysing case study data together with data collection activities allows the researcher to make

quick adjustments to the study design as required (GAO, 1990). However, conclusions that are not justifiable are caused by using only a subcategory of the data, linking findings across cases without context, and applying analytic techniques that contradict each other. The research design and approach were presented as an enquiry framework using thematic analysis that offered orderly processes to collect data, and then analysing the data, by generating codes and themes. According to Duran et al. (2006), the main components of this enquiry framework include identifying the issues, collecting the data, preparing and engaging with the data, thematically analysing the data, interpreting the data analysis, and ethically composing the research findings.

As a flexible and useful research tool, thematic analysis provides a rich and detailed account of data (Braun and Clark, 2020). It uses a six-stage approach to describe the process of data collection and analysis. This approach confirms the role of the researcher as being deliberate, reflective, and thorough by understanding the philosophical assumptions that determine the chosen research methods for collecting and analysing the data (Braun and Clarke, 2014). The data analysis began with collecting, familiarising, and managing data from the schools. Tables and maps have been used to code data as they illustrate relationships and contradictions between the research constructs. This coded data was reduced systematically into code categories. The next stage of the analysis was to generate themes from the data by sourcing existing knowledge from the literature. The generated findings have provided detailed pictures of the analysed data. Interpretation of these findings addressed and provided answers to the research questions.

The researcher has adopted the procedures of Braun and Clarke (2020), Creswell (2013), Campbell et al. (2021), and Miles et al. (2014) for the six-stage data collection and thematic analysis process for this research study as seen below:

Table 11 Data collection and thematic analysis process

Six-stage data collection and analysis	Braun and Clarke (2020)	Creswell (2013)	Campbell et al. (2021)	Miles et al. (2014)
Collect the data	All data collected is referred to as the data corpus		Engage in the iterative process of reflexivity	
Engage with the data	Familiarise with the data, read and re-read transcripts, listening to audio transcripts, and note all initial codes.	Manage files by transcribing data, organising text files in relation to the research questions.	Revisit the research questions and re-read transcripts to understand the what the dataset is saying.	
Code the extracts from the data	Code interesting features of the data systematically across the dataset, collate data relevant to each code.	Form a list of codes that expand as the data are reviewed and re-reviewed.	Use descriptions that include illustrative quotes and codes to exemplify the theme.	Code data extracts and write analytical memos
Generate code categories from the codes	Collate codes into potential themes; check if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire data set, generate a thematic 'map'	Reduce codes to categories	Refine and discuss how the codes work together across the whole dataset and in relation to the research question.	Generate categories to condense the data

Conceptualize themes from the categorised coded extracts	Refine the specifics of each theme and generate clear names for each theme	Interpret the data by linking the raw data with the research literature	Identify key elements that reflect the essence of the dataset.	Develop themes
Represent findings	Select appropriate extracts, discuss the analysis relating back to the research question or literature.	Present a detailed report of the analysed data	Make a convincing argument to address the initial research question.	Compress meanings from data and assemble the information using tables and networks.

5.13.2.1 *Coding extracts from the data*

This stage started by categorising notable extracts in the transcripts and generating initial codes. Data extracts are an important segment of the data that reveal information that is relevant to the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2020; Campbell et al. 2021). The researcher’s interpretation of the data collected has formed the analysis at this stage. The process of analysing the data involved using codes to explain the data extracts emanating from the transcribed data (Clarke and Braun, 2017). The transcribed data was a more polished version of the full-verbatim script that removed all extras (including ‘umms’, ‘hmms’, ‘ermms’, and pauses) and made it easy to read. Emphasis was placed on the participants’ viewpoints and on the observation notes to identify the important ideas and assumptions.

Figure 8 shows a screenshot of some codes developed by the researcher. This is further discussed in Section 6.4 Coding and Theming). Appendix XXIII also gives a short transcript of the interview extract with some codes highlighted.

Figure 8 Code Exemplars

When the code list was created, suitable code labels were used to describe these codes to give a clear meaning. The code labels were actual words and behaviours of the participants as signified in the data. For example, a participant's words and/or expressions during the interviews in

explaining the teaching and learning aids/methods. Describing each code meant that the extracts were accurately coded, re-coded, or new codes generated, if needed. It was not necessary to code every word or sentence within the transcript. However, the researcher listened to the interview transcript multiple times, read, re-read and identify relevant codes in the data by writing memos, confirming evidence, and was conscious of the participants' silences and subtle languages (Cousin, 2009).

5.13.2.2 *Generating code categories from the codes*

Generating code categories presented an opportunity to address the research questions (Creswell, 2013). This process reduces the codes and generates the code categories by identifying and describing the features of the category (Morse, 2008). In this stage, the researcher categorised the code into chunks. For example, codes like the Covid-19 challenge, funds, pressure to pay fees, and government failure were lumped into the code category – funding problem. The code list, codes' descriptive statements, and the coded extracts were reviewed to identify emerging patterns. According to Baxter and Jack (2008), these code categories join different components of data, promote a better understanding of the case, and strengthen the findings.

5.13.2.3 *Conceptualising themes from the codes and the code categories*

The thematic data analysis was informed and guided by the existing literature resulting in the findings (Peel, 2019). Case study themes and findings from the data were used to further address the research questions. From the code categories, the researcher further arranged them into themes. These data-generated themes highlighted earlier laid the foundation for learning the concept of education for Nigeria's sustainable economic growth. For example, codes categories of indicators,

school events, growth in education, and future-based curriculum were grouped into the theme of quality of education.

5.13.2.4 *Conceptualising the data to represent the findings*

The data findings and interpretations were combined with the literature to answer the research questions (Peel, 2020). In this final stage of the analysis, the data generated and presented from the themes have been combined to apply and discuss the findings based on the literature.

5.14 Ethical Consideration

A good research significantly adds to the field of academic knowledge and addresses a gap in the research. This research addresses issues that surround the way and manner the education sector in Nigeria equips students for the competitive world. The unexpected global pandemic of Covid-19 which forced nations of the world to be locked down has exposed the huge gap of the education sector and dampened the nature of education in Nigeria. The nonchalant attitude of the government towards the education sector has been exposed by the poor facilities for remote teaching and learning activities. This well-planned research has used the case study research design and sought ethical approval from the UWS Ethics Committee to protect organisation's and participants' personal information.

Objectivity: Although the literature argues for an unbiased, objective approach to collecting and analysing data (Šimundić, 2013), this was unlikely because of the sample size used; previous work relationships the researcher shared with some of the participants; the primary and secondary data which was gathered to fit the research context; and the participants that fitted into the inclusion criteria. The participants were given an invitation letter which informed them of the intention to conduct a research study and an invitation to participate. All research activities were conducted

remotely and the participants were given a day to reply in writing confirming their decision about whether or not they wanted to participate in this study. Participants who volunteered to take part in this research were given a briefing note. This briefing note contained the summary and purpose of the research study. It ensured that the participants had an idea of the research context and prepare to fill out questionnaires and participate in the interviews.

The participant information sheet was distributed to all the participants which showed the researcher's contact details so that participants can ask questions (if any). It also included journals that the participants could refer to if they needed further clarification on the nature of the research. Copies of the participant information sheet are attached in the appendix section. Also, a consent form was signed by all the participants. This form took the nature of an agreement confirming that the participants agreed to volunteer to participate in the study; their understanding of the nature of research; ensuring the confidentiality of the information they provide; access to the information they have provided during the period of the research; and a space for them to attach their signature.

Justice and Fairness: It is important for the researcher to take note of issues about justice and fairness and ensure that none of the participants are unfairly burdened with the demands of the research (Schroeder et al., 2019). Interviews were done remotely and final examinations were ongoing at the time of data collection. Therefore, the researcher allowed the participants decide the interview schedule to reduce the possibility of them feeling pressured or compelled to take part in the interview process.

Privacy and Confidentiality: During the research, procedures that protect the privacy of the research participants were implemented and the information gathered was not disclosed to others other than the University community. To maintain confidentiality, the researcher and the University research and examination community only had access to data from questionnaires,

interviews, and documents. It was necessary to discuss issues of privacy and confidentiality at the start of the field phase to acquire informed consent and build trust with the participants. The data collection phase was done remotely and interviews were conducted only in the offices of those being interviewed. This was to limit the possibility that others could see the participants taking part in the research activity or hear the information being shared in the interview. The researcher adopted the following measures to protect the confidentiality of information gathered during the study:

- Only the necessary data was collected and participants were labelled (using codes) according to their school and job position on electronic copies including audio recordings and questionnaires.
- The completed questionnaires, school documents, and interview audio recordings were immediately uploaded to online storage platforms. With this, only authorised persons had access to this information and there was no breach of confidentiality.
- These electronic documents are stored in password-protected computers.
- Response to the research invitation letters, consent forms, and participant information sheets were signed by the employers, managers, teachers, and students and stored electronically.

Validity and Reliability: Data was obtained through different procedures to elevate the dependability and trustworthiness and their interpretation (Zohrabi, 2013). Research is considered valid when it is believable and evaluates the quality of what it is supposed to evaluate (Burns, 1999). The quality and validity of instruments used to collect the data are crucial because conclusions are drawn based on the information obtained from these instruments (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2003). Validity also concerns the compatibility of the research findings with the reality

through which triangulation helps to strengthen the validity of the data and findings (Merriam, 1998). Although repeated observations were not conducted at the time of data collection, the results and interpretations were given to the participants to confirm the content of what they stated during the interviews. This serves as a way to confirm the truthfulness of the information. Merriam (1998) notes that the research data and findings must go through a peer examination process. In this case, colleagues at academic conferences and the researcher's supervisory team who are familiar with the research area gave their feedback and criticism which augmented the validity of the research. This research is applicable in other settings or subjects beyond this context because that issues of education and economic growth rates affect individuals and economies of developed, developing, and under-developed countries. As Burns (1999, p.160) notes – 'how generalisable to the other contexts or subjects is our research.'

Reliability deals with the consistency, dependability, and replicability of 'the results obtained from a piece of research' (Nunan, 1999). Obtaining the same results in quantitative data is easy because the data are in numerical forms. However, using the qualitative approach becomes difficult because the data are subjective and in narrative form. Lincoln and Guba (1985) point out that the dependability and consistency of the data should be emphasised and not checked out for the same results. These authors further note that to ensure the dependability of the results, the researcher needs to explain in a clear and detailed manner the different processes and phases of the research. This was done through the participants information sheets which was distributed to the participants before the field phase of the research. Different methods were used to collect data and this information was obtained through different sources – students, teachers, management, and employers. Therefore, collecting varied types of information through different sources enhanced the reliability of the data and the results.

External reliability, which concerns the replication of the study (LeCompte and Goetz, 1982), was taken into consideration to check for some aspects of the research. The study noted that the researcher had a previous work relationship with some of the participants; the choice of the participants were the students, teachers, management, and employers because they were the sample size; the research was conducted in a group of three schools and interviews were done with groups of participants in the same category and organisation structure; the different procedures of collecting data were clearly explained in the field phase section of this chapter. The main methods of gathering information in this research were through questionnaires, interviews, documents, and observations. The quantitative data were analysed through descriptive statistics and qualitative data through descriptive and thematic interpretations. Internal reliability is obtained when an independent researcher has similar findings to the original researcher after reanalysing the information (Zohrabi, 2013). In this study, the researcher used some mechanisms to guard against threats to internal reliability as suggested by LeCompte and Goetz (1982) and Nunan (1999). These are low inference descriptors that can be readily observed and measured by ‘asking factual questions’ (Richards and Schmidt, 2002, p. 239); peer examination and review of other research studies and findings; and recording the interviews to easily reanalyse the data by other independent researchers to increase the internal reliability of the data and findings.

5.15 Summary

The chapter outlined the case study research method and discussed the different phases used to conduct the research. The philosophical stances showed that the study was carried out based on the objective views of the researcher and the participants to reveal the nature of the education system in Nigeria. The chapter went on to discuss the sample size and different techniques that were used to collect and analyse both quantitative and qualitative data based on the research

questions (this is explored in the succeeding chapters). In the pre-field phase, the case study protocol outlined the procedures taken in the course of the research following the idea of Stake (1995). An illustration showed the expected duration of participation in the study. Ethical considerations have been noted in compliance with the UWS Ethical guidelines.

CHAPTER SIX

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

6.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter will look at the presentation and analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data. The chapter is discussed in two parts. Part one shows the analysis of the quantitative data. The data collected through the questionnaires is categorized and summarized to obtain answers to the research questions. Part two presents and analyses the qualitative data. The data collected from the research participants using questionnaires, semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews, observations, and documents will be triangulated and analysed. The method of qualitative data analysis used is thematic analysis. A coding and theming template is developed by the researcher and is used across the data findings. The themes discussed in this chapter are quality of education, problems facing education, government policies, labour market demand, teaching and learning aids and activities, access to education, problems facing human capital availability, and management policies.

PART ONE

ANALYSIS OF QUANTITATIVE DATA

6.2 Introduction

The quantitative data is gotten from the questionnaires and presented together showing participants' responses from the three schools. This is because the schools are under the same management and the data collection process was done at the same time. The questionnaires were properly filled out by the teachers and management and returned to be used for the data analysis.

The main aim of analysing the data is to reduce the data to an interpretable form so that the constructs can be used to draw a valid conclusion for the study.

Table 12 Response to Quality Education

Response from Teachers

S/ No	Items	(f) SA	(f) A	(f) I	(f) D	(f) SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
4	I have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector	46	26	-	-	-	4.64	0.48
5	The school management provides opportunities for my training and development	31	35	4	2	-	4.32	0.71
	Average	39	30	2	1	-	4.48	0.60

Table 12 shows all the items had weighted mean scores and were seen as quality education. In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 4.48 which is above the average, the participants agreed that they have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector and the schools' management provides opportunities for training and development.

Figure 9 Percentage distribution of respondents on the required knowledge and skill for the education sector

Response from Management

As can be seen in **Figure 9**, 10 (53%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector, 8 (42%) of them agreed, while 1 (5%) of them disagreed that they have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector.

Table 13 Response to Teaching and Learning Aids and Methods

Response from Teachers

S/No	Items	(f) SA	(f) A	(f) I	(f) D	(f) SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	There are sufficient teaching and learning aids for education	15	32	8	14	15	3.38	1.15
2	Teachers are well trained on the methods of 21 st century teaching	19	30	7	16	-	3.72	1.09
3	Examination is the only criterion used to test the academic ability and knowledge of the learner.	12	12	5	26	17	2.67	1.43
	Average	15	15	7	19	16	3.26	1.22

Table 13 shows almost all the items had weighted mean scores and were seen as the teaching and learning aids and methods. In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.26 which is above average, the participants agreed that there are sufficient teaching and learning aids for education, and teachers are well trained in the methods of 21st century teaching.

Figure 10 Percentage distribution of respondents on the criterion to test the academic ability and knowledge of the learner

Response from Management

Figure 10 shows 1 (5%) of the respondents strongly agreed that examination is the only criterion the schools use to test the academic ability and knowledge of the students, 4 (21%) of them agreed, 3 (16%) of them were indecisive, 9 (47%) disagreed, while 2 (11%) strongly disagreed that education is the only criterion the schools use to test the academic ability and knowledge of the students.

Table 14 Response to Labour Market Demand*Response from Teachers*

S/No	Items	(f) SA	(f) A	(f) I	(f) D	(f) SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
7	Learners are taught the required skills for the labour market	10	35	15	11	1	3.58	0.96
8	The curriculum is relevant to meet the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement.	9	31	15	11	6	3.36	1.14
	Average	10	33	15	11	3	3.47	1.05

As can be seen in **Table 14**, all the items that had weighted mean scores were seen as the labour market demand. In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.47 which is above the average, the participants agreed that students are taught the required skills for the labour market and that the curriculum is relevant to meet the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement.

Table 15 Response on the relevance of the curriculum to meet the pressing needs of Nigeria's economic advancement*Response from Management*

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Relevant	47	65.3	65.3	65.3
Irrelevant	25	34.7	34.7	100.0
Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Table 15 shows that 47 (65.3%) of the respondents said the schools' curriculum is relevant in meeting the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement, while 25 (34.7%) of them said it is irrelevant to the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement.

Table 16 Response to Labour Market Demand

Response from Management

S/No	Items	(f) SA	(f) A	(f) I	(f) D	(f) SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Learners are taught the required skills for the labour market	4	13	-	2	-	4.00	0.82
2	Education is the only determinant for economic growth in Nigeria	3	5	4	7	-	3.21	1.13
	Average	4	9	2	4	-	3.61	0.98

Table 16 shows all the items had weighted mean scores and were seen as the labour market demand. In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.61 which is above the average, the participants agreed that students are taught the required skills for the labour market and education is the only determinant for economic growth in Nigeria.

Figure 11 Percentage distribution of respondents on how schools are funded

Response from Management

Pie chart on distribution of respondents on school funding

As can be seen in **Figure 11**, 18 (95%) of the respondents said that the schools are internally funded; while 1 (5%) of them said that the government funds the schools.

Figure 12 Percentage distribution of respondents on issues related to economic growth that are embedded in the curriculum or extra-curricular activities

Response from Teachers

Figure 12 shows 9 (12.5%) of the respondents agreed that CSR activities are related to economic growth and are embedded in the schools' curriculum or extra-curricular activities, 8 (11.1%) of them said student placement, 21 (29.2%) of them said entrepreneurship education, 18 (25%) said research clubs/projects, while 16 (22.2%) of the respondents said debates are related to economic growth and are embedded in the schools' curriculum or extra-curricular activities.

Figure 13 Percentage distribution of respondents on issues related to economic growth that are embedded in the curriculum or extra-curricular activities

Response from Management

Figure 13 shows 1 (5.3%) of the respondents agreed that CSR activities are related to economic growth and are embedded in the schools' curriculum or extra-curricular activities, 5 (26.3%) of them said student placement, 6 (31.6%) of them said entrepreneurship education, 5 (26.3%) said research clubs/projects, while 2 (10.5%) of the respondents said debates are related to economic growth and are embedded in the schools' curriculum or extra-curricular activities.

Figure 14 Percentage distribution of Teachers on teaching and learning aids and methods

Response from Teachers

As can be seen in **Figure 14**, 34 (49%) of the teachers strongly agreed, 31 (45%) of them agreed, 2 (3%) of them were indecisive, and 2 (3%) of them disagreed, that there are sufficient teaching and learning aids for education and that teachers are well trained on the methods of 21st century teaching and examination is the only criterion used to test the academic ability and knowledge of the learner.

Figure 15 Percentage distribution of respondents on whether teachers are trained in the methods of 21st century teaching

Response from Management

From **Figure 15** above, 12 (92%) of the respondents said that the teachers are trained in the methods of 21st century teaching; while 7 (8%) of them said that the teachers are not trained in the methods of 21st century teaching.

Table 17 Response on who funds the education sector in Nigeria

Response from Management

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Private Sector	3	15.8	15.8	15.8
Public Sector	5	26.3	26.3	42.1
Foreign Aids	1	5.3	5.3	47.4
Private and Public Sector	9	47.4	47.4	94.7
Public Sector and Foreign Aids	1	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

As can be seen in **Table 17**, 3 (15.8%) of the respondents said that the private sector funds the education sector in Nigeria, 5 (26.3%) of them said the public sector, 1 (5.3%) of them said foreign aids, 9 (47.4%) of them said private and public sectors, while 1 (5.3%) of them said that public sector and foreign aids funds the education sector in Nigeria.

Figure 16 Percentage distribution of respondents on whether salaries and other remunerations are paid on time

Response from Teachers

Figure 16 shows that 69 (96%) of the respondents said salaries and other remunerations are paid on time, while 3 (4%) of them disagreed with that.

Figure 17 Percentage distribution of respondents on whether salaries and other remunerations are received

Response from Teachers

As can be seen in **Figure 17**, 64 (89%) of the respondents said that they receive salaries and other remunerations; while 8 (11%) of them said they do not receive both salaries and remunerations.

Figure 18 Percentage distribution of respondents on funds allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development

Response from Teachers

Figure 18 shows 12 (17%) of the respondents strongly agreed that funds are allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development, 28 (39%) of them agreed, 14 (19%) of them were indecisive, 15 (21%) disagreed, while 3 (4%) strongly disagreed to funds allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development.

Figure 19 Percentage distribution of respondents on funds allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development

Response from Management

Figure 19 shows 1 (6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that funds are allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development, 3 (16%) of them agreed, 1 (5%) of them were indecisive, 13 (68%) disagreed, while 1 (5%) strongly disagreed that funds are allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development.

PART TWO

ANALYSIS OF QUALITATIVE DATA

6.3 Introduction

The qualitative data analysis shows that a total of 67 participants were in the inclusion criteria for this research. These were the students, teachers, management staff, and employers. However, not all the participants were available at the time to take part in this research. Participants' responses were gotten from semi-structured and focus group interviews. The table below shows a breakdown of the participants who responded.

Table 18 Participants' Responses

	EXPECTED	ACMGS, Port Harcourt	BCMS, Port Harcourt	WOF, Port Harcourt
	Number of Participants			
SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS				
Teachers	15	4	2	2
Management	19	2	2	1
Employers	9	2		
FOCUS GROUP INTERVIEWS				
Students	12	3	1	2
Teachers	12	1	2	2

The duration of the interviews for employers was an average of 45 minutes; an average of 30 minutes for the management staff; an average of 25 minutes and an average of 22 minutes for the students. Transcription is an important phase of the analysis process (Clarke and Braun, 2017) because it helps to familiarise with the data, generate themes and provide detailed pictures of the analysed data. Although time-consuming, transcription was done manually because of the accent

barrier. The transcribed data was read and re-read to identify relevant codes, confirm evidence and write memos (Cousin, 2009). The relevant codes were words and phrases that represented important and recurring themes in each participant's response.

6.4 Coding and Theming

The researcher has developed the coding template below and it has been used across the data gotten from interviews, focus groups, and documents.

Table 19 Coding Template

<p>1. Quality of education</p> <p>1.1 Indicators</p> <p>1.1.1 Bringing out the best in a child through examination</p> <p>1.1.2 Self-survival</p> <p>1.1.3 Economic survival</p> <p>1.1.4 Students' character, behaviour, thought-process</p> <p>1.1.5 Deep thinking</p> <p>1.1.6 Holistic development</p> <p>1.1.7 Responsible global citizen</p> <p>1.1.8 Economic growth</p> <p>1.2 Future based curriculum</p> <p>1.3 Ministry of Education responsible for curriculum development</p> <p>1.4 Skills to excel even without a university education</p> <p>1.5 Growth in education</p> <p>1.6 Training and re-training of teachers</p> <p>1.7 School events</p> <p>1.8 Teachers' strengths</p> <p>1.9 Schools' partnership</p> <p>1.10 Test of knowledge and skills</p>	<p>2. Problems facing education</p> <p>2.1 Finance</p> <p>2.1.1 Budgetary allocation</p> <p>2.1.2 Pressure on parents to pay fees</p> <p>2.1.3 Late payment of fees</p> <p>2.1.4 Bad debt</p> <p>2.1.5 Parents' contribution and levies</p> <p>2.2 Emotional wellbeing</p> <p>2.3 Academic performance</p> <p>2.4 Government sponsorship</p> <p>2.5 Upgraded facilities although inadequate</p> <p>2.6 Covid19 pandemic</p> <p>2.7 IT challenges</p>
<p>3. Government policies</p> <p>3.1 Erratic policies</p> <p>3.2 Good ideas on paper but no implementation</p> <p>3.3 The political will to ensure action on policies</p> <p>3.4 Responsible leaders</p> <p>3.5 Government effort and commitment to education</p> <p>3.6 Change of government</p> <p>3.7 Failure to improve on quality</p> <p>3.8 Policy review</p>	<p>4. Labour market demand</p> <p>4.1 Reflection of the 4Cs in teaching</p> <p>4.2 Display of skills and talents</p> <p>4.3 Academic qualification</p> <p>4.4 Interaction with other students</p> <p>4.5 Curriculum for nation's needs</p> <p>4.6 Knowledge and skills</p>
<p>5. Teaching and learning aids and activities</p> <p>5.1 E-learning</p> <p>5.2 Infrastructural facilities</p> <p>5.3 Practical teaching and learning</p> <p>5.4 Learning process</p> <p>5.5 Specific teaching to student's needs</p>	<p>6. Access to education</p> <p>6.1 Students' background</p> <p>6.2 Affordability</p> <p>6.3 One-to-one contact between the teacher and student</p> <p>6.4 Ethnic influence</p>

5.6 Teaching methods	6.5 Student performance 6.6 Gifts and donations 6.7 Assistance from other organisations
7. Problems facing human capital availability 7.1 The government's plan for graduates 7.2 High percentage of those without jobs compared to those with job offers 7.3 Decline in education 7.4 Paper qualification as opposed to actual knowledge and skills 7.5 Teachers' incentives 7.6 Recruitment test 7.7 Job opportunities 7.8 Lack of interest in school activities 7.9 Brain drain	8. Management policies 8.1 Core values 8.1.1 Academic standards 8.1.2 Zero tolerance for exam malpractice 8.1.3 Stakeholders' needs 8.2 Training and re-training 8.2.1 Schools' collaboration 8.2.2 Collaboration with other organisations 8.2.3 Annual training 8.2.4 Resource persons 8.3 Prudence in managing school funds 8.4 Funds allocation 8.5 Job opportunities for members of the host community 8.6 Low staff turnover 8.7 Schools' sustainability 8.8 School policy documentation

FINDINGS:

The interviews revealed participants' views and responses to the impact and need for education for Nigeria's sustainable economic growth. Eight themes were developed from the data which will be discussed below.

6.5 Quality of Education

This theme discusses participants' views on the indicators for quality education, the schools' role in ensuring quality education, and the processes that lead to quality education. Participants indicated that quality education is a holistic development and is seen in the students' character, behaviour, thought process, and ability to express an opinion. It is meant to *“bring out the best”* in the child (E1). Also according to (S1), *‘with good education, I can achieve anything I wish to’*. Participants' views on this correspond with the learning objectives for SDG 4 stated in CHAPTER ONE that quality education is important for the humanistic and holistic development of the child (Table 1 – cognitive learning objective for SDG 4). Education trains the minds of people to be

relevant, useful, and able to contribute to Nigeria's development. Dr Dakuku Peterside (a chieftain of the All Progressives Congress – APC) notes that *'education is the way to secure the future...'* (Njoku et al., 2022)³³.

'...It is your thought process, mannerism, your way of interfacing with people, the way of addressing issues and problems, these are the things that structured education teaches you. It enables you to fit in as a good member of society. You can reason logically, you can contribute what you are expected to because you have been taught how to be a good citizen' (E1).

A participant indicated that education trains an individual for self-sustenance and economic survival. It is not possible to dismiss the role of education in an individual because apart from gaining academic qualifications; quality education helps an individual cope with different challenges.

'Nigeria will not go too far without government paying attention to the provision of quality education for her citizens...I consider it very difficult for anybody to think of surviving economically without having a solid educational base. So I am an advocate of quality education and I encourage every person who has access to such to take advantage of it not just for personal academic development but for future economic betterment for such a person and the country' (E1).

Although studies suggest that education is the only determinant for economic growth in Nigeria (Faraq and Taylor, 2011; Wang and Wong, 2011); views from a participant further explain that education is a strong factor but not the only determinant. This participant explained that in some parts of Nigeria, where cultural values are very much prevalent, the males engage in commerce and trade as a means of survival. However, according to this participant, education *'gives the basis*

³³<https://guardian.ng/features/stakeholders-decry-poor-allocation-to-education-sector-as-it-continues-to-slide/>

for doing whatever you do, better' (E2). That is to say, an individual cannot go beyond a certain level without the impact of quality education. Quality education *'empowers an individual with skills to excel even without university education'* (E2). Another participant views education as a vital tool for the growth of Nigeria's economy. *'...They go hand in hand. If we say we have quality today, it means that we have a growth in the economy'* (M2).

Studies show that the skills needed for the 21st century are gathered during secondary education compared to the university education which teaches only specific skills and course content (World Bank, 2007). *'...It was intended to produce for the nation, students who have a broad knowledge of education and some other components of it. In other words, people who are able to graduate and are equally able to fit in here and there without being confined to one strict area'* (E1).

In this theme, school events were seen as a step toward quality education for the students. This is in line with UNESCO's (2012) recommendations because school event is an area that contributes to teaching and learning about sustainability. The schools engage in events like excursions, sports activities, debates, research activities, field trips, career days, etc. They collaborate among themselves, other schools, public and private organisations to manage the events. *'The school's harvest held on xxx. It was solely organised and executed by the students. Funds were raised by the students (and supported by the parents) which are being used to support the school's projects'* (School's Report – ACMGS). These events are done to give the students real-life experiences. It was observed that the students went on an excursion to a water factory. This gave the students first-hand experience and a better understanding of their Chemistry lessons and laboratory activities because they saw live sessions on the importance and procedure of water purification (Observation).

The schools organise sports activities individually and invite each other and other schools to participate. At the beginning of the academic year, the school management allocates each student to a team (otherwise called a 'house' with unique colours and uniforms) where they can engage with themselves, exercise their bodies, and prepare to compete against themselves at the end of the academic year. Teachers are also allocated to these teams to guide and support the students as they engage in these activities. The team ('house') that wins the competition takes the medal and in some cases, the best athlete in the team wins a scholarship for the next academic year. This allows the students to engage in extra-curricular activities; improve their attitude to learn; explore other areas of strength apart from academics in terms of sports, soft skills, and social behaviours; and improve parents' views on the schools. Some sporting activities done in the schools are football, athletics, egg-race, chess, basketball, high jump. The schools aspire to have more facilities, so infrastructure is being built like swimming pools.

At career day events, the schools bring in professionals in business and academics to enlighten the students, explain different career choices, and impact their daily lives. *'The girls' school...the Old Girls' Association based in North America has readily always come to support the school, encourage them and give them exposure in different areas of life' (E1).*

The teachers believe that there is a growth in the quality of education in Nigeria. According to them, they have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector. Table 12 also shows that 100% of the teachers in this study agree that they have the right knowledge and skills to work in the schools.

On the other hand, the employers are of the view that there is a decline in the quality of education in Nigeria. As a result, recruiting and selecting the right candidates to work in the schools has continued to be a challenge.

'...I think they show a decline. I went to secondary school in the 1960s and being in a position now of managing education, I can see a difference between then and now; between the products then and the products now; and between the teachers then and the teachers now...we are doing recruitment exercise right now. I have been in recruitment exercises where you interview people who are supposed to be graduates and you actually wonder what school they went to' (E2).

Education for sustainable economic growth is a life-long learning process in which individuals acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to contribute to a sustainable society (Table 1 – cognitive learning objective for SDG 4). This statement corresponds with the outcome of the findings that the schools make effort to train the teachers to excel in their job roles. This has helped with student outcomes. In the chairman's report at a stakeholders' meeting:

'...We are pleased to report that one of our students, Master xxx (of BCMSS) emerged 3rd out of 192 other participants in the 2017 Rotary International, Port Harcourt South Essay Competition' (School Report - BCMSS).

The schools provide opportunities for training and development for successful candidates. They collaborate with local and international bodies to train and re-train the teachers and management to equip them with the required standard of teaching and management. Table 12 indicates that 66 (91%) of the teachers agree that school management provides opportunities for their training and development.

Observing the teachers' CVs for job interviews and their **employment letters** that follow show that teachers in the schools are given responsibilities based on their areas of strength, knowledge, and skill as opposed to other schools that only recruit candidates without emphasis on their knowledge or skill.

Aboluwodi and Owolewa (2018) assert that school administrators and managers should ensure a strict adherence to policy implementation that exposes students to skills and competencies. They also claim that the use of examination as the only criterion to measure the academic ability and knowledge of the students has led to cheating and examination malpractice in Nigerian schools. To solve this issue, the teachers and managers demonstrated more proactive ways of testing the knowledge of the students.

As can be seen in Table 13, 43 of the management staff agree that examination is not the only criterion used to test the academic ability and knowledge of the learner.

Different methods revealed from the literature review can be used to assess the students like research groups where there can be individual or group presentations at the end of the teaching, encouraging the students to write a project on a specific topic, an online or classroom quiz, seminars or debates where the students can initiate a conversation, ask questions among themselves and respond to the questions on the topics covered throughout the term. With these, the ability of the learner can be assessed in different ways.

'Apart from examination, there is a need for the school to embark on what I call talent hunt... because every human being is embedded with one talent or the other... I think if we create an opportunity for the children to display what they have right inside of them, I think it will help them a lot... So I think talent hunt should be included apart from examination' (T1). The schools engage in competitions that encourage student learning and engagement. *'The Principals also welcomed CUDAS' suggestion for competition among the three (3) schools to present students for such competitions as SPAK and PZ Chemistry competitions...'* (**Minutes of Meetings**).

The participants agreed with their views on the curriculum used by the schools. This participant captures it thus:

'Whatever any school uses as curriculum or teaches the children is what such a school must have received from the relevant arms of government particularly the Ministry of Education. So government is equally getting aware that somehow our teaching must make provision for the future of a child and the nation' (E1).

Another view of Nigeria's educational curriculum is that it does not solve the nation's problems nor meet its needs. However, there is a disparity in participants' opinions on the relevance of the curriculum to Nigeria's economic advancement. *'The curriculum is not really tied to societal needs in this country because every nation has to tailor its educational system, its research, and development towards the things that the country needs...our education, our technology has to be geared towards the needs of the country...'* (E2).

The Ministry of Education in Nigeria has the responsibility to make useful changes in the education system. The education system in Nigeria should be futuristic and should give importance to the nation's development, students' training, skills, and professional qualities (Ordu, 2021).

6.6 Problems facing education

This theme discusses the problems facing education in the schools used for this study. The major challenge which has been observed and also confirmed by the participants is funding. The schools in this study struggle to provide infrastructural facilities because of the low tuition fees, late payment of fees, and even fees avoidance by some parents. The schools have suffered losses on many occasions because some parents refuse to pay fees till the students write their final examinations and graduate. Some other schools insist on full payment of fees by withholding the transcripts and certificates of the students so that their parents are forced to pay all accruals. However, the schools in this study have an unwritten policy of not putting the student's life on hold by seizing the transcripts and certificates. The management would normally expect these

parents to be responsible enough to pay up any outstanding fees. This has caused the schools to suffer a lot of bad debts.

A participant notes that *'fees are not paid on time by parents. It's actually a battle for parents to commit themselves to regular payment of fees. Some parents are too smart to the extent that you see them trying to dribble the schools as it were even up to the point of their children graduating. And that continues to affect the funding or income generation of the schools'* (E1).

Despite the challenges faced by the Nigerian education sector and the inability of the government to meet the budgetary allocation requirement of 26% (Education for All Coalition; UNESCO, 2015 and Blampied et al., 2018); the Nigerian President – Muhammadu Buhari has proposed to give the sector its lowest allocation in 10 years. A review of the Premium Times Newspaper below shows the percentage budgetary allocation by the Nigerian government to the education sector between 2011 and 2021.

Figure 20 Nigerian 2021 Budgetary Allocation to Education Sector³⁴ **(Government Data)**

Material redacted due to copyright restrictions. Figure can be found at Premium Times Nigeria.

Another challenge faced by the schools is inadequate infrastructural facilities which has been caused by the challenge of funding. To explain this, the owner notes:

'...We have upgraded our facilities up to, I can say 80%...there are libraries, laboratories, there are decent classrooms and classroom facilities for teaching and learning, there are dormitory facilities. But in some of the schools, they are not enough. If you go to the girls' school, the facilities available for dormitory life have become grossly inadequate and we have started putting up a fresh one but the project is not moving as fast as we desire basically because of the challenge of

³⁴ Olufemi, A. (2020) 'Buhari's 2021 budget share for education is Nigeria's lowest in 10 years', *Premium Times*, 24 October. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/422829-buharis-2021-budget-share-for-education-is-nigerias-lowest-in-10-years.html> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).

funding. And that is something that runs through the three schools. Funding is a major challenge and we believe that help can come to us through government or some other agencies as well' (E1).

A memo sent out by the Chairman of the Board further explains that *'hostel accommodation is fast becoming a concern due to the increase in students' population. Remedial plans are being articulated'* (Schools' Report).

The teachers suggest that the schools need financial help from the government to tackle the issue of insufficient funds. *'... I cannot say that the government has given us any funding support in strict terms but there was a time the government promised to provide buses for student shuttle services, which they did, and for us, that has been one outstanding support we have received ever since'* (E1). The management feels one of the best ways to tackle this funding challenge is to take loans from financial institutions since the schools cannot increase the tuition fees so as not to lose some of the parents and children who are middle and/or low income earners.

UNSG (2014) and Global Monitoring Report (2012) suggest that it is important for schools to take note of all financial streams including funds from domestic private (financial institutions) to ensure great impact. However, the owner does not see the need for loans because of the high-interest rate, collateral, and instability of the Nigerian economy. Apart from tuition fees and other levies paid by parents, funds come in from the office of the proprietor. These funds are disbursed at the beginning of the academic year and infused into the schools' budget and then at the end of the academic year, the schools remit a certain percentage (about 10%) of their profit to the owner.

The owner also partners with and makes appeals to some organisations to raise funds. *'...Some individuals, some organisations like the Old Girls have at some point given us financial support which at the point of giving the support, they specify what they would want it done with...they have been like donations so we don't need to pay back...'* (E1).

The Covid-19 pandemic put a strain on the schools and the wellbeing of the students and entire staff because schools were shut down for over six months during this period. It became a struggle for the management to pay salaries and other remunerations during this period because there was no income for the schools in terms of school fees and levies. Even though online teaching and learning were ongoing, the teachers had to go through all the topics again when the schools resumed because it was very difficult to get the students to concentrate. This has caused the schools to lag in trying to meet up with the curriculum. Normally, the academic calendar runs from September to July with breaks in between. However, the challenge of the pandemic disrupted the academic year and in trying to meet up; schools resumed in September for the first term and had to fast-track the teaching and learning to prepare for the second term in November with only a weekend break between the two terms. This affected the emotional well-being of the students more because many of them who live in other cities were forced to stay back in school thereby depriving them of being with their families. The students in examination classes also were not sufficiently prepared for their final examinations. This has brought about very poor performance in WAEC, NECO, and JAMB examinations all over the country as the JAMB registrar blames this on the coronavirus pandemic which also affected the smooth running of the academic calendar (Alabi, 2021). The school's management has organised counselling seminars for staff and students to discuss issues about their health and wellbeing (**Minutes of Meetings, BCMSS Report**).

6.7 Government policies

This theme discusses participants' views on the Nigerian government policies regarding education. Government policies in Nigeria continue to be a big challenge because of the nonchalant attitude displayed by the relevant authorities and leaders. These policies concern providing quality education and schools for the students; and job opportunities for graduates. As a result of the first

concern, private individuals, groups and religious organisations have decided to bear the responsibility of providing quality education and in the same way, providing jobs for the teeming population of unemployed graduates. The government focuses its ideas and resources on other sectors of the Nigerian economy with little or no attention to education. *'...they forget that education is the key to every other sector'* (T3).

'I will say government policy on education appears to be erratic...as governments leave office and are replaced by another, each new one comes up with what it considers 'best' for the educational sub-sector in the country, and most times new governments have the tendency to dismiss entirely whatever was on ground before they came to power. That affects the teachers. That affects the students. That generally equally affects even proprietors of schools. Even the schools run by the government itself. So I think that government needs to be a bit more stable in the drafting of policies and the implementation of policies on education. It will help the future development of the country' (E1).

Most times, the leaders who come into power are visionary and passionate and have the ideas to move the country forward in terms of education. *'For instance, you see leaders that have interest in education... make policies that are favourable to the education sector and to enhance education'* (T2). However, because of *'political, ethnic influences'* (M2), criticisms from opposing parties, and the short time spent in political offices, government leaders are not able to successfully initiate and implement any policy. Also, there are no measures in place to review and audit the politicians in terms of the promises they made during their campaigns and what they have achieved. *'...Several policies have been made, but the issue is implementation. Change of government, a new government bringing new policies...but not being able to carry them out and implement them. But we have good policies that have been made so far, as far as education is concerned'* (T5). This

statement is in support of Hodges (2001, p.26) that ‘Nigeria’s development failures have sprung from the lack of success in achieving an effective model of governance...’

A participant notes that: *‘...In some of the government schools I know, the parents still complain that they pay fees whereas the government announced to the masses that they have given scholarships to students’ (T3).*

‘The free education has gone a long way to pave way for many persons who because of their background wouldn’t have had the opportunity to go to school...But it doesn’t apply to our schools’ (M1).

Again, the UBE was reformed in 2008 and the 9-3-4 was introduced into the education system. The schools operate using the 9-3-4 system of education. This was meant to bridge the gap between primary and secondary education and meet the MDGs by 2020.

‘The negative at times seems to be speaking more because the way they go about the policies is people come in with different ideas instead of helping to push the nation forward. It affects the education aspect of the nation. A situation where we have been working with the 6-3-3-4 system and suddenly there was a change, things are not coming out of it’ (M1).

‘...From the original idea of policymakers, it was intended to produce for the nation, students who have a broad knowledge of education and some other components of it...So that is okay for me. The problem we have is in the area of implementation. On paper the ideas are good, but to what extent has the same government been able to put structures or facilities in place to enable teachers and students to arrive there?’ (E1).

When asked about the procedures for setting up a school in Nigeria, the participants were unanimous in their responses and said that these procedures are meant to ensure that the schools

being established are not only for business purposes but for institutions of learning and adding value to society. For example, a participant said:

'Government now insists that schools should not be an all-comers business. That is, before you are registered to function as an institution of learning, whatever is required in terms of infrastructure, quality of teachers must be in place before you are granted approval' (E1).

These policies are very effective because many of the government workers ensure that the schools are compliant. However, there are still lapses in some areas and many corrupt government leaders and workers do not implement these procedures.

According to Egbefo (2012), corruption is a major factor in the implementation of educational advancement in Nigeria. This supports the statement of the participant: *'Good ideas are there. But even in the aspect of saying you cannot take off until we see you are fully prepared; you know the system is largely corrupt and with little inducements here and there, some people can be asked to just go ahead with whatever is on ground'* (E1).

The schools in this research are inspected at different times of the academic year to ensure quality and compliance. The inspectors come from the Federal Government, State Government, local authorities, and each of the school's Governing Boards. *'The Inspectorate committee of the Board has continued to carry out routine inspection exercises of our schools'* (School policy documents). These inspections are usually at random and are unannounced.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, the government authorised all schools to set up sanitation facilities to curb the spread of the virus in schools. One of the schools used in this study was inspected at random during this period and they achieved 100% compliance with the government regulations (School's Report – ACMGS).

'We have hand washing exercise on our timetable daily. That is an excellent development' (M1).

This school built hand-washing stations, made customised face covering for students and staff, ensured social distance during school gatherings and in the classrooms and laboratories, and management organised daily sessions to discuss with the students and staff the nature and effect of the pandemic and good hygiene.

6.8 Labour market demand

This theme discusses the participants' views on students' level of education to meet labour market demands. From the survey, the teachers agreed that students are taught the required skills for the labour market and that the curriculum is relevant to meeting the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement. Figure 9 is an example of this as 95% of the management staff confirm that they have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector. Table 14 also shows an aggregate weighted mean of 3.47 which is above the average. The teachers agreed that students are taught the required skills for the labour market and that the curriculum is relevant to meet the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement.

The teachers are trained regularly to use the curriculum to properly apply their knowledge and skills in the methodology of teaching. In support of this, a participant had this to say:

'On a termly note, we do like two trainings for teachers, so we have six trainings at the end of the year. Sometimes, it is more than that, as the need arises' (E2).

While observing the students and their teacher in an Economics class, the teacher split the students into three teams and assigned a leader. Each group chose a topic to discuss and present their findings to the class. By so doing, every student participated in the classwork, interacted with each other and their leader presented the findings to the class. They were able to share their ideas, ask questions and come up with recommendations (**Observation**).

'...Collaboration, communication, and critical thinking are reflected in our curriculum. In sciences, we have group work, where the students are grouped, most of them benefit from it because they interact with each other... I think we are trying in that aspect. Also, critical thinking makes them think outside the box, from what they are taught' (T5).

'... I will mention that we can now think outside the box to do things on our own. We can work as a team because that is what group work has taught us and we can communicate effectively' (S2).

Developing the students' skills is needed to examine and work towards resolving issues with local and global significance. This way, the students engage actively in their learning, cultivate their curiosity, and can think critically (Ordu, 2021).

Fasih (2008) says that education should play an important role in increasing productivity and preparing students for the labour market by providing them with the necessary knowledge and skills for the workforce. This is in line with the findings of the study because the students are exposed to the relevant skills needed in the labour market.

According to a participant: *'As a school, we are doing our best to make sure that the students fit into the issues of economic growth by engaging them in subjects that will help them and teach them the requisite skills to be better persons in future' (T5).* At the senior level, the guidance counsellors assist the students to choose the subjects to learn according to their area of strength and future career aspirations. Although this is contradictory to the views of Favara and Appasamy (2015) that the Nigerian labour market is in high demand for cognitive skills and the fact that skills needed presently may not be in demand in the next five decades (UNESCO et al., 2016); the schools and the guidance counsellors in this study can develop skills in the students for lifelong learning to be able to fit into any job role at any time even as entrants from different sectors.

The students go for excursions to have an experience of the business world. In the area of collaboration, the schools partner with other professional bodies by organising seminars and workshops to teach the students about life skills and socio-economic issues. As part of activities in the schools' timetable, a participant says: *'we have career day where the schools collaborate with and invite professionals from outside. The students are able to interact with these professionals'* (T5).

According to the survey data, 8 (11.1%) of the teachers and 5 (26.3%) of the managers said student placements are embedded in the schools' curriculum and extra-curricular activities. The schools collaborate with some private organisations to achieve this. Yet, this is still not sufficient to salvage the issue of unemployment in Nigeria. Figure 12 and Figure 13 show an illustration of this. Quality education will eliminate the huge cost of training and retraining incurred by companies because of skills mismatch and outsourcing of roles to employees from other countries.

6.9 Teaching and learning aids and activities

This theme discusses teaching and learning aids and activities in the schools used in this study. During the Covid-19 pandemic, teaching and learning activities were done remotely. *'While the children were at home when all schools were closed, we got across to parents and opened platforms by which we taught the children...most of them using their parent's phones and it was an interesting challenge for them and us'* (M1).

The study, however, revealed that the pandemic put a strain on the teachers and students because of the long stay at home. Students became easily distracted and were no longer eager to learn. According to a participant: *'...The truth is that technology cannot replace the teacher. So that one-to-one contact was not there for about six months. And at the end of the day when we had the*

children back, we noticed that gap in some areas and it's an effect we are still battling with...'

(M3). This challenge is because the pandemic was unexpected and teaching and learning activities have always been done in the classroom without any reason for E-learning. One way to be fully equipped for any occurrence of this nature is for the students and teachers to become familiar with digital tools, interact with others remotely, engage in more diverse settings, and apply their knowledge in new contexts (Ordu, 2021).

When the participants were asked in the focus group interview if the school has sufficient teaching and learning aids for education, they responded that the schools have sufficient teaching and learning aids. For example, a participant said *'yes, it is better than some other schools'* **(S5)**. When prompted to explain why this student felt this way, she revealed that her former school did not have sufficient equipment in the laboratories so they were split into different groups to use the laboratories. This slowed down her learning process because the time allocated to some subjects on the timetable was insufficient.

As seen in the schools' inventory list, the schools' assets are audited regularly and managed by the maintenance officers **(Inventory Records)**. The maintenance officers send reports of these facilities and their working conditions to the vice-principal (administration) termly. Even though the schools have these facilities and are equipped to modern standards according to ratings from inspectors; the owners and managers still feel that a lot more can be done to increase the facilities already available. *'There are dormitory facilities but in some of the schools, they are not enough. If you go to the girls' school, the facilities available for dormitory life have become grossly inadequate and we have started putting up a fresh one...'* **(E1)**.

Teachers who are responsible for transferring knowledge must be adequately trained on the methods of teaching and the use of teaching/learning aids (NESG, 2018). The survey revealed that 92% of the teachers are well trained in the methods of 21st century teaching (Figure 15).

The students have an allotted time in the timetable for practical classes where they learn in the laboratory, farm, or sports centre and have hands-on skills and knowledge of what has been taught in the classroom. During break periods, the boarding students take their lunch in the dining hall while day students buy their meals from the cafeteria (**School Timetable**).

It was observed that the students and their teachers engage in after-school lessons in the evenings for the boarding students and early in the morning for the day students when they arrive (**Observation**). This is like a tutorial or an informal interaction and recap of what has been taught in the classroom. These lessons are done most times voluntarily by the teachers usually before the examination period and are in ‘difficult’ subjects like mathematics. This way, the students have more time to ask questions, participate in class activities and discuss freely among themselves in a more relaxed form. Reports further reveal that an educational consultancy volunteered ‘...to carry out a 2-week remedial programme across the 3 schools aimed at improving the teaching and learning of Mathematics’ (**Minutes of meetings**).

Apart from examination, the schools encourage the teachers to grade students using talent hunt and character traits; participation in class; performance in some of the curriculum activities they engage in; projects and research work; and use of quizzes, oral presentations, and sometimes communication skills. This is necessary to improve the educational standard. ‘*Apart from examination, there is need for the schools to embark on what I call talent hunt... I think if we create an opportunity for the children to display what they have right inside of them, it will help them a lot...*’ (**T1**). ‘...*We also look around to see how a child participates in class...*’ (**T3**).

The survey gives a breakdown of different strategies the schools use in teaching and learning activities like CSR activities, student placements, entrepreneurship education, research clubs/projects, and debates. However, the survey data show that the participants have differing views on the schools' methods for teaching and learning. For example, Figure 12 and Figure 13 reveal that 25% of the teachers agree that the schools engage in research clubs and projects to grade the students while 26.3% of the management say the same. Also, 22.2% of the teachers say that the schools organise debates for the students where they discuss socio-economic issues with opposing and proposing teams, while 10.5% of the management agree with this.

These activities are embedded in the **Curriculum** and the schools' extra-curricular activities as seen in the **School Timetable** and are aimed at leading to better performances. *'Majorly we use examination, but we also employ things like quiz, practical performance, like music and sports, we use that to assess students and to grade them'* (T5).

According to Adedokun (2011), students who learn through experience understand the importance of being involved in collective efforts to equip them with the skills and competencies they do not have; promote their self-confidence; make useful decisions that affect them; encourage them to take responsibility for identifying and meeting their needs; and fully participate in school activities. This agrees with the findings of the study because students are usually exposed to other activities that align with the 21st century teaching and learning apart from examinations. Figure 10 indicates that 58% of the management in the survey say that examination is not the only criterion used to test the knowledge of the students.

6.10 Access to education

This theme discusses students' access to education as a way of tackling unemployment and ensuring sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. OECD (2018b) and UIS & GEMR team (2019)

have estimated that 125 million people globally are not acquiring basic literacy and numeracy skills even after spending years in school with 70% of them among working-age individuals. The schools try to bridge this gap by practicing inclusive education and admitting students irrespective of their background. The schools' record of the population showed a combined population of 879 students at all levels with a teachers population of 167 (**Schools' Reports**). This helps the students to tap into the rich diversity in the classroom and interact freely with each other (Anupriya and Salim, 2014). *'ACMGS admits the female students of any race, colour, ethnic origin, or religion that will abide by the school policies and procedures...ACMGS accepts prospective staff from all nationality, religions, and beliefs that align with our philosophy of Christian education'* (**School policy document**). Students who want to be admitted into any of the schools are mandated to write an entrance examination and have a minimum score of 70% before they are given admission into any of the schools (**School policy documents**). The examinations hold at the beginning of the academic year and are open to only those going into Junior Secondary (J.S.) 1 and 2 and Senior Secondary (S.S.) 1 and 2. Students seeking admission into the examination classes (J.S. 3 and S.S. 3) are not granted this or they are asked to go a class down if they insist on being admitted. This is to maintain quality and ensure that the incoming students are familiar with the school environment, other students, and teachers while they prepare for the examination class in the next academic year.

Every citizen has the right to quality and affordable education. Unfortunately, as a result of inconsistent government policies, many schools in Nigeria are now owned by private individuals or religious organisations. Even though some schools are funded by the government, most of the allocated funds for education are still diverted toward other corrupt purposes (Egbefo, 2012).

Education which is capital intensive has become far out of the reach for some citizens in society (Dogra, 2011). The schools' management did not consent to release financial records for this study because of privacy and confidentiality concerns. However, a look at the fees rate from the newsletters shows that the schools have their target market for the middle and low income class and strive to offer quality and value with very affordable fees rate. The owners emphasise adding value as opposed to only profit-making. Even with this, many parents can still not afford to put their children in the schools. To solve this challenge, as part of the schools' CSR duty, the schools offer scholarship opportunities to some children of staff or the host communities and discounts for parents with three or more children enrolled in the schools. Studies by Moneva et al. (2007), Tan et al. (2015), and Orlitzky et al. (2013) suggest that CSR activities affect corporate performance in the sense that the schools attract more capital from their improved reputation in the public and the business community. The old students' association of the schools and some private organisations also regularly offer scholarship funds for the student(s) with the highest grade in a particular subject.

'I cannot say that the government has given us any funding support in strict terms. But there was a time the government promised to provide buses for student shuttle services, which they did, and for us that has been one outstanding support we have received ever since' (E1).

'Some individuals, some organisations...like I said the old girls, have at some point given us some financial support which at the point of giving the support, they specified what they would want it done with. Either use it to provide this or that for the laboratories or classrooms. So they have been like donations. We don't need to pay back' (E1).

The schools receive gifts and donations from some private organisations as a way to improve quality. For example, in a stakeholders (owners) meeting report by the Board Chairman, the Niger

Delta Development Commission (NDDC) supported School 1 (ACMGS) to construct a ring road and drainage system within the school environment. Another individual single-handedly built a library and equipped it with books and furniture. Also, the Shell Development Petroleum Commission (SPDC) as part of its CSR activity constructed a ring road and football pitch within School 2 (BCMSS) (**Minutes of meetings**).

The schools have been able to achieve this to keep up with the interesting challenge of maintaining the standard of education for the students and also to retain the stakeholders (parents and children) as a business venture. This is a way to cushion the effect of the Nigerian government's failure in meeting up with the UN recommendation of a 26% budgetary allocation requirement for its expenditure (UNESCO, 2015; Manuel et al., 2019).

6.11 Problems facing human capital availability

This theme discusses the problems facing the availability of human capital in Nigeria. Education as a measure of human capital availability and quality is the only way to analyse the impact of human resources on economic growth (Benhabib and Spiegel, 1994). Nigerian schools produce close to two million graduates annually and there is no concrete plan by the government as to what to do with these graduates (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2015). This supports a participant's view: *'I will say that from the onset, again considering the prevailing challenges in our national life as a country whereby students who are qualified either from the secondary schools or universities, are not able to secure placements in companies or organisations...'* (**E1**). Many graduates lack the basic skills and competencies needed to be employable because these skills are not imbibed in the students in school. In support of this, a participant notes: *'...I have been in recruitment exercises where you interview people who are supposed to be graduates and you actually wonder what school they went to...'* (**E2**). Another participant noted:

'We made it clear to our teachers that our schools should not just seek to educate people but every teacher of any subject should explore the avenues whereby the children are equipped properly so that if they are not even able to go to universities after graduation and they choose to find themselves a job, they should be able to fit in. So these four criteria are taken into consideration and we emphasize them before our teachers so that we don't just produce people who have mere paper certificates but also can find their feet when they leave the schools' (E1).

Many students lag in academic activities and seem not to be responsible for their learning. The desire which should be in the students' minds to contribute to Nigeria's economic growth appears to be lacking. A participant in this study says the Covid-19 pandemic contributed a lot to this challenge because students were at home for about six months and all efforts made by the teachers to engage them seemed futile. *'...That one-to-one contact was not there for about six months. And at the end of the day when we had the children back, we noticed that gap in some areas and it's an effect we are still battling with...'* (M3).

The high rate of unemployment in Nigeria also contributes to the unavailability of human capital. The unemployment rate in Nigeria increased from 27.10% in the second quarter to 33.30% in the fourth quarter of 2020 (National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria).

Table 20 Overview of the Nigerian Labour Market

The table below shows Nigeria’s indicators and the number of people actively looking for a job as a percentage of the labour force³⁵:

	Last	Previous	Unit	Reference
Unemployment Rate	33.3	27.1	percent	Dec 2020
Population	206	200	Million	
Employed Persons	46488	58527	Thousand	Dec 2020
Employment Rate	66.7	72.9	percent	Dec 2020
Minimum Wages	30000	30000	NGN/Month	
Unemployed Persons	23187	21765	Thousand	Dec 2020
Youth Unemployment Rate	53.4	40.8	percent	
Employment Change	187226	155444	Jobs	Sep 2016

In support of this, a participant was of the view that: ‘...*Either due to challenges of leadership in the country; what to do with these graduates after they leave school is not taken or factored into the different plans government makes. And so it becomes difficult for people on graduation to easily find a place for themselves. That’s why some people who are actually not cut out for good education will tell you – those of them who have graduated, where are they? So they find some other means of self-survival...So I think the problem we have now is that, in as much as we are urging everybody to go to school, we’re also not making sufficient effort to provide...places where they can be employed to contribute to the economic life of the nation’ (E1).*

³⁵Source: Trading Economics provides data for 20 million economic indicators from 196 countries including actual values, consensus figures, forecasts, historical time series and news. Nigeria Indicators - was last updated on Saturday, June 18, 2022. Available at: <https://tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/indicators> (Accessed: 9 April 2022).

The poor incentives in the education sector compared to other professions have discouraged graduates from going into the teaching profession. However, (89%) of the respondents in this study said that they receive salaries and other remunerations and 96% of them confirmed that their salaries and other remunerations are paid on time (

Figure 16 and Figure 17).

Nigeria experiences brain drain because of the poor education system and high unemployment rate (Birabil and Ogeh, 2020; Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2015). A press release on 15/7/2021 by Catriona Laing, the British High Commissioner to Nigeria, goes thus: ‘...*The UK Government is introducing new Visa Routes for students and those looking to work in the UK. In July, we opened our New Graduate Route...If you’ve completed your education and you are looking to secure a job, you can also apply for our Skilled Worker Route. So we think these are great innovations and they are designed to attract the brightest and the best...So I hope you will believe me when I say we really are looking to attract the brightest and best Nigerian students to study in the UK and then indeed, to stay in and work with us, sharing their skills...*

’ (TGM Education TV, 2021).

In as much as this is a good effort by the UK government to offer quality education services to Nigerian students which the Nigerian government has failed to provide; as controversial as this might sound, Nigeria is yet going to suffer from the massive brain drain this new policy will cause.

6.12 Management policies

This theme discusses management policies that the schools use in ensuring values of standard, sustainability, stakeholders' management, teacher training, and funds management. The schools' core value is to maintain an academic standard by recruiting teachers with the right knowledge and skills. The teachers go through a rigorous recruitment process before being employed to work in the schools. As seen in the **Minutes of Meetings**, *'the Chairman of the HR Committee was directed to work out a template for getting good teachers that will serve the 3 schools'*. Table 12 shows that 100% of the teachers in the survey have the right knowledge and skills to work in the schools. They are trained specifically to exhibit excellence and fit the objectives of the schools. The schools recruit only graduates who have the minimum academic qualification in education to work as teachers. The minimum academic requirement for a job seeker in the Nigerian education sector is NCE (National Certificate in Education).

'There is policy when it comes to recruitment and training. When we are talking about recruitment, we are targeting to get the best teachers. The minimum education qualification we take is NCE. In terms of training, teachers go through the training that is needed. For instance, there is the type of training we give to newly recruited teachers like orientation, which will help them fit into the system' (M2).

Edema (2021) says that examination malpractice has eaten deep into the Nigerian education sector and devalued the certificates; and even some parents have contributed to this problem. As a management policy, the schools have zero tolerance for examination malpractice. The Code of Good Practice for Staff (**School policy documents**) for the schools states that any teacher involved in examination malpractice of any kind will be dismissed. Unfortunately, because of this stance, the schools have lost some students because parents who do not believe in these values have

withdrawn their children. During external examinations like WAEC, NECO, and JAMB; the schools insist on the moral background of the external examiners that are deployed to work in the schools during the examination period. This is to ensure that there is no infiltration of the schools and/or students.

The schools work very hard to ensure sustainability and meet stakeholders' needs by being the first choice for parents, teachers, and students. The schools experience low staff turnover because sufficient incentives are put in place by the employers and managers (**Newsletters**).

As a way of motivation, many of the teachers in this study have even acquired more academic qualifications up to the doctorate level. A participant supports this and noted that: '*...The school also permits teachers who have put in a few years of service who wish to acquire higher education to go. Because we understand that when that happens, when they come back they are better...*'

(M1). Teaching is a graduate profession in Nigeria. However, the schools encourage teachers to acquire further academic qualifications needed for their personal and career growth.

Another motivation strategy the schools' owner adopts is having regular informal gatherings with the teachers. As a routine, the schools' owner celebrates World Teachers' Day and 'Teacher of the Month award' (**Minutes of Meetings**) with them and this allows them to interact freely in a more relaxed manner. At this event, special monetary incentives are given to all the teachers as a way of acknowledging them for their work and support in the schools (**Observation**). '*...The teachers, I meet with them regularly. I celebrate World Teachers' Day with them during which time, I also give them tokens of appreciation...*' (E1). The school management meets with the parents at the beginning and end of each term to discuss the well-being of their children, hear their complaints, and discuss strategies to adopt for the benefit of the students, teachers, and management. On the

other hand, the owners meet with the parents annually to discuss operations and make decisions that affect the students and school in general for the next academic year.

'... We very regularly interact with the parents. At least once a year, I meet with the parents to just generally interact, appreciate them, encourage them and challenge them to continue to be there for their children and the schools... Each time I meet with parents, the teachers will always be there. So we interact generally... We are very much in touch with the many stakeholders... As the owners, each time we meet; issues of the three schools form part of the things we discuss...' (E1).

On the contrary, even though the schools make a lot of effort to maintain the standard, many parents still complain about different issues. A participant said the schools have not fully met stakeholders' needs. To solve this challenge, the schools need to have feedback boxes where parents, students, or teachers can anonymously drop their complaints or suggestions.

This participant narrated thus: *'...I will say yes and no. Yes, in the sense that we have got some satisfactory answers from the stakeholders... But you know human beings are insatiable. So there will be that craving to have more... We've done a lot and we are still working on doing better than what we've done so far'* (M3).

As a CSR strategy, the schools give employment opportunities to members of the host communities whilst insisting on excellence and teachers with the right knowledge and skills. *'... We are usually happy when people from the host communities seek employment and there are opportunities for them...'* (E1).

'... The vision of the education board is that our schools should be the first choice for parents, students, and staff. That way we must aspire for excellence in such a manner that people, parents will be queuing in to bring their children here, children will make sure that their parents bring them in, our teachers will like to come here and work' (E2).

The schools engage in regular staff training and re-training to ensure excellence. The schools also collaborate among themselves and with other organisations to organise regular staff training (**Training materials**). *'We have a minimum of two trainings per term...and about six in the year. We have internal training. We also collaborate a lot with external educational bodies'* (M1). This training is usually within and outside the state or country. The schools have collaborated with organisations like the Nigerian Association of Private Schools (NAPS), Association of Christian Schools International (ACSI), and the United Arab Emirates Ministry of Education, and sent teachers and management for training within Nigeria, South Africa, United States, and the United Arab Emirates. Documents review further showed that *'...The school sponsored some delegates to an Educational Conference in Finland...'* (**Minutes of Meetings, BCMSS Report**).

'...We do have like the ACSI, up to international level training for our staff. These trainings are more or less, training the trainers. When we come internally, we impact these trainings to see that there is a general upgrade of the staff' (M5).

As a former management staff in these schools, the researcher had the opportunity to attend several trainings with other colleagues within and outside Nigeria. On many occasions, the owners have also accompanied the teachers to attend these trainings. Through the trainings, the teachers can interact with the resource persons, other teachers, and even students. The owners and management also use the opportunity of these training programs to purchase some teaching aids which will be useful within the schools.

In the schools' organisation culture, the schools' management delegates staff according to their areas of strength and talent. Staff who display specific skills and talents are assigned to certain aspects of the schools' life. For example, staff who are athletic are assigned to be masters or mistresses of the sports teams.

The schools collaborate with HR servicing organisations to organise staff audits annually where their **KPIs** are reviewed according to the **schools' policies**. The schools do not believe in retrenchment except in extreme cases like examination malpractice or safeguarding concerns. Unfortunately, some staff were retrenched as the schools were downsizing as a result of the negative impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. *'...We had one last year and we needed to reduce the number of staff by reason of the pressure of Covid-19. We picked some staff who had not measured up'* (M1).

A memo sent out by the chairman of the Board to other members of the Board also shows the schools' commitment to ensuring staff performance: *'...I wish to re-emphasise our new performance ethics and request that we specifically assess the performance of the 3 new members of the ACMGS management team in 6 months' time'* (Staff job description).

The schools' management is prudent with the management of funds. *'Bank statements are availed to the finance committee to enable the committee to monitor the Board's financial activities'* (Report – Finance Committee). Before the start of any academic year, each of the school's finance officers submits a budget to the owners and this is reviewed and decisions are made. The Chief Finance Officer together with the finance team organise a financial audit annually to check the schools' financial records and books. 56% of the participants in this study agree that funds are allocated for infrastructural development (Figure 18).

Because the tuition fees are not outrageously high, the management has to properly manage the scarce funds and ensure that staff salaries and other remunerations are paid when due. *'...We are very prudent in the management of funds which we get...and because we know that the world will get even more digitalized, we have built a modern CBT centre and we are presently equipping with computers to ensure that whatever the world comes to, we are equal to the task...'* (M1).

6.13 Summary

Descriptive statistics was adopted to analyse the results from the quantitative data showing the spread of values and beliefs raised in the questionnaires using tables and graphs to give an understanding of the qualitative data. The coding template was developed into themes and provided an extensive discussion of the relationships across the data from participants – questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, observations, and documents. The interviews and focus groups are the strongest part of the data. However, for better analysis and interpretation, the survey data and documents were used to illustrate points within the themes and support some of the participants' perceptions.

CHAPTER SEVEN

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

7.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter presents an in-depth discussion of the research findings. The researcher goes on to develop an empirically based model to understand the data. This model is developed from the conceptual framework to give a better overview and link to the theory and literature. The structure of the literature review and the entire thesis is centred around the empirical model, therefore the researcher discusses this chapter based on the research findings. The justification for this chapter is to give a clearer understanding of the research context and make sense of the findings.

7.2 Introduction

The model shows a more detailed relationship between the research constructs. Based on the literature review, conceptual framework, and research findings; the empirical model has been developed by the researcher and is illustrated below:

Figure 21 Empirical model showing the link between education, human capital, and sustainable economic growth

Source: The Researcher

This model has been developed by the researcher based on the research questions and research findings and obtained while identifying the problem. It illustrates some factors which are instrumental to education as a tool for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The model shows bi-directional and interactive relationships between the SEG and each of the constructs and uses

indicators to further explain these relationships.. The interactions among the constructs are seen in the following indicators below:

INDICATORS				
Public/private investments	Employer-Educator synergy	Budgetary allocation	Entrepreneurship education	21 st century needs
More industries for job creation	Apprenticeships	Excursions	Stakeholders' needs	Futuristic curriculum
(Un)employment	Teaching/learning outcomes	Research institutes	Research groups	Exchange programmes
Better labour markets		Emphasis on university education		Qualified / skilled graduates and teachers

The indicators influence SEG and at the same time SEG influence these indicators. It therefore becomes a virtuous circle in the sense that as the indicators get better, SEG is improved and vice versa. The interactions among the constructs and their indicators are further discussed in this chapter.

7.3 Funding

Despite the challenges faced by the Nigerian education sector and the inability of the government to meet the budgetary allocation requirement of 26% (Education for All Coalition; UNESCO, 2015 and Blampied et al., 2018); the Nigerian President – Muhammadu Buhari has proposed to give the sector its lowest allocation in 10 years. Out of the 2021 national budget of N13.08 trillion, only

N742.5 billion has been allocated to education (Olufemi, 2020). This is just 5.6% of the budget – the lowest percentage allocation since 2011. In 2020, the education sector received N671.07 billion which was 6.7% of the national budget. The highest budgetary allocation the education sector has ever received is 10.7% in 2015 which was proposed by former President Goodluck Jonathan in 2014. Since then, none of the budgetary appropriation bills has surpassed this. The UBE which supervises education at the primary and secondary levels got N77.6 billion which is grossly insufficient to oversee these levels. Many government schools in Nigeria have dilapidated infrastructure with inadequate funds to upgrade them.

As seen in CHAPTER ONE of this study, Osunwusi (2020) describes the government's ideas and strategies as glamorous in terms of documentation rather than in practicability. This idea is not feasible because there is no way the government can achieve 100% education expenditure by 2025 far above the global benchmark of 26% when it has not even been able to achieve more than 10% for the past 10 years. This is ludicrous and shows the weakness of the leadership in Nigeria because the President has decided to pledge to the UK (and the world) on how education will be more funded subsequently without communicating with the citizens or showing a genuine commitment to improving the sector.

At the Global Education Summit which was held in London, the Nigerian President promised on 28/7/2021 to increase the budgetary allocation to the education sector by 50% over the next two years. In a document titled: Heads of States Call to Action on Education Financing Ahead of the Global Education Summit, the President stated:

'We commit to progressively increase our annual domestic education expenditure by 50 per cent over the next two years and up to 100% by 2025 beyond the 20 per cent global benchmark'.³⁶

This is a very beautiful idea by the President. However, as seen in Chapter 1 of this study, Osunwusi (2020) describes the government's ideas and strategies as glamorous in terms of documentation rather than in practicability. This idea is not feasible because there is no way the government can achieve 100% education expenditure by 2025 far above the global benchmark of 26% when it has not even been able to achieve more than 10% for the past 10 years. This is ludicrous and shows the weakness of the leadership in Nigeria because the President has decided to pledge to the UK (and the world) on how education will be more funded subsequently without communicating with the citizens or showing a genuine commitment to improving the sector.

The government has remained insensitive to the concerns of the education sector. A lecturer at Obafemi Awolowo University and Branch Chairman of ASUU in the school – Adeola Egbedokun says that the budgetary allocation to education is inadequate to make any useful change within the sector. He further says that:

'We have always stated from time to time that the budgetary allocation to education is meagre and inadequate compared to what is allocated to other sectors, especially what is allocated to somewhere like the National Assembly. A government that is keen on developing the nation will invest in education but we have an insensitive government that is not even thinking about

³⁶Agency Report (2021) 'Buhari pledges 50 per cent increase in education budget in two years', *Premium Times*. 29 July. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/476289-buhari-pledges-50-per-cent-increase-in-education-budget-in-two-years.html> (Accessed: 19 November 2021).

developing this nation at all. What they are concerned about is developing their pockets. That is not the way to go' (Olufemi, 2020 in Premium Times Newspaper, para.23-24).

Arguably, the Nigerian government feels that it is the responsibility of private organisations and individuals to fund private schools. However, this will not be the case if there is more government interest in providing quality education irrespective of whether the schools are publicly or privately owned. Therefore, it is a problem of the system and not the individuals.

7.4 Quality of Education

University education only teaches specific skills and course content in the sense that it focuses more on advancing theoretical knowledge at the cost of practical skills. However, many of the skills (especially the 4Cs of communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking) needed for the 21st century are gathered during secondary education (World Bank, 2007). The teachers develop these basic skills in the students so that they are open to learning more advanced skills in the future and identify and fit into different business opportunities.

Between 1960 and 1980, Nigeria's education system was a role model for other countries. The contemporary Nigerian literature was built on this strong foundation by Nigerian scholars like Chinua Achebe, Wole Soyinka, and J.P. Clark. However, the reverse is the case now as there has been slow progress in the growth of Nigerian literature and the education sector generally because of the drastic decline in Nigerian educational standards (Adeaga, 2012). To solve this challenge of poor education standards, the employers and management organise several stages of recruitment tests and interviews to select the best candidates. Chattaraj (2017) says that while quality education at all levels is crucial, ongoing training and education outside the formal classroom setting are becoming more essential. The emphasis is on the rapidly changing global economy, which places knowledge as the most valuable asset of the world.

In a statement by UNESCO (2014), education for sustainable economic growth is a lifelong learning process in which individuals acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to contribute to a sustainable society (Table 1 – cognitive learning objective for SDG 4). This statement corresponds with the outcome of the findings that the schools make effort to train the teachers to excel in their job roles. This has helped with student outcomes.

Scott (2015) says that the future education system aims to create a world for all and an opportunity to confront new challenges as they arise. The future of the education system is not clear but we can predict how it should be shaped. Curriculum and schools for future education should transform from an emphasis on teaching to an emphasis on learning.

Nigeria's education quality is affected and suffers three major setbacks because research is a neglected area of the education sector³⁷. First, the researchers work without sponsorship, especially in the core sciences. Resources are limited and operations are slow, selective, and sometimes politicised. Study findings are often abandoned on library shelves because of the government's lack of commitment to research-oriented development. Researchers do not have the resources to promote their work and research findings. Lastly, the research output in Nigeria is mediocre and repetitive because there are no innovative and effective measures to track research output nationwide.

As a way of promoting innovation and motivating the teachers, those who have worked in the schools for a long time are encouraged to engage in professional development activities. This is in line with the recommendation of Carlson and Gadio (2002) that because teachers are generally resistant to change, certain motivation strategies must be put in place to encourage them. The

³⁷ Ekundayo, O. (2019) *Education in Nigeria is in a mess from top to bottom. Five things can fix it*. Available at: <https://theconversation.com/education-in-nigeria-is-in-a-mess-from-top-to-bottom-five-things-can-fix-it-112894> (Accessed: 28 September 2021).

management has collaborated with an educational consulting firm to develop a plan of action for the improvement of the schools with highlights on the strategies (**Schools' Report**). The action plan includes the development of a more rigorous curriculum and instruction; improvement of the level of achievements of the students; building of a highly effective faculty; imbibing of higher-order thinking skills in the students; participation in international examinations; standard operating procedures in conducting both internal and external examinations; facilities upgrade; greater ICT application; greater networking of faculty with professional bodies and colleagues; and effective leadership.

7.5 Government Policies

Two notable government policies on education based on the curriculum are the 6-3-3-4 system of education and the UBE. The 6-3-3-4 was set up in 1983 to meet the educational needs of the citizens and equip the youths with sellable skills that will make them self-reliant. The 6-3-3-4 means six years in primary education, three years in junior secondary education, three years in senior secondary education, and four years in tertiary education. The policy focused on strengthening the educational institutions and creating innovative strategies to remodel the education sector. Although the 6-3-3-4 system was designed to inject functionality into the Nigerian education system by producing graduates to meet labour market needs (Omolewa, 1986); it has been faced with a lot of difficulties in the aspect of funding, sustainability, infrastructure, getting qualified teachers and motivating them (Yoloye, 2004).

The UBE was set up mainly to provide free, compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian child, eradicate poverty, and contribute to Nigeria's development. However, in reality, it has been observed that only a few have access to this free education. These policies have not produced any significant changes in the education sector mainly because of poor implementation

and insufficient availability of human and material resources (Okoroma, 2001; Babalola, 2018). The participants also believed the policies are rather fantastic on paper but improving the quality and sustaining them has remained an issue.

Another policy of the government on education is on the quality of schools being run which has been sustainable. An article by Edutainment (2021) reveals that private individuals and organisations that want to establish schools must go through certain procedures before being approved. These procedures include getting government licenses, an inspection of physical facilities to be used, teaching and statutory records, quality of teachers and the management structure, meetings/interviews with owners, safety facilities, health and sanitation measures, and beautification of the school compound. The schools board also organise inspection activities.

Economists have recognised that the development of human capital is the key prerequisite for a country's socio-economic and political transformation [Romer (1989b) and Lucas (1988)]. Education, as a measure of quantity, availability, and quality of the human capital is the sole method to analyse the impact of human resources on economic growth (Benhabib and Spiegel, 1994). Nigeria has recorded significant growth rates since the advent of civilian rule in 1999. The country has witnessed an average growth rate of about 6% in the last 10 years (UNDP, 2009). However, the nation's economic growth rate has declined because of unemployment and poverty prevalence. Research can be used to find out the extent to which professionals, skilled and semi-skilled workforce are available in various sectors of the nation's life. The more research efforts are encouraged, the more the country is better able to harness its human capital potential (Chikwe et al. 2015).

7.6 Labour Market Demand

The education sector has continued to deteriorate over the years due to inadequate funding. This has resulted in poor infrastructure, a lack of teaching and learning tools, an increase in the number of out-of-school children, and producing less competitive graduates.

The teachers reflect the 4Cs in teaching methodology. In terms of developing students' critical thinking skills, they sometimes allow the students to express their thoughts about concepts that have been taught in different ways. According to Saint et al. (2003), skills and competencies, in the struggle to meet the demand of the labour market, are mainly gathered in secondary schools. This is because the basic skills gathered at this level of education make possible a lifetime of learning. Furthermore, a study conducted by Kashefpakdel et al. (2018) in the UK shows that 90% of teachers believe that the top five skills and competencies cited by employers are developed in the secondary school. These skills and competencies are acquired through classwork and extra-curricular activities. Teachers believe that teamwork, confidence, communication, creativity, and problem-solving are the top five skills and competencies developed through extra-curricular activities.

Although this is contradictory to the views of Favara and Appasamy (2015) that the Nigerian labour market is in high demand for cognitive skills and the fact that skills needed presently may not be in demand in the next five decades (UNESCO et al., 2016); the schools and the guidance counsellors in this study can develop skills in the students for lifelong learning to be able to fit into any job role at any time even as entrants from different sectors.

Osagie (2014) says that the labour market can only be functional when education produces the needed workforce. It is for this purpose that UNESCO (2015) recommends that 26% of the government's annual budget should be channelled towards education. However, this assertion is

contrary to that of the findings of this study because the participants reveal that 95% of the funding is internally generated and not from the government.

Unlike some developed countries like France (Bonnal et al., 2002); apprenticeship experience, which is an actual driver for employment generation and poverty reduction at low investment cost, has not been adequately harnessed in tackling the unemployment surge in Nigeria (Fajobi, et al., 2017). To tackle the skills divide where people are not sufficiently qualified for jobs because they lack the required years of experience or specific skills; employers should collaborate with the education sector to shape a curriculum for employment. This can be done through student training or apprenticeship programmes (Favara and Appasamy, 2015).

Researchers insist that education as a measure of human capital availability and quality is the only way to analyse the impact of human resources on economic growth (Benhabib and Spiegel, 1994). But Nigeria is still far from achieving this because the government has failed to invest in human development through education. Every year, Nigerian schools produce close to two million graduates and there is no concrete plan by the government as to what to do with these graduates (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2015).

Before now, Nigerian employers were only concerned about graduates' certificates without testing for actual knowledge and skills. This has made graduates struggle just to get degrees and paper qualifications with no clue as to what to do with the certificates or with their lives. This supports the endogenous growth theory (discussed in Chapter 3) as to the link between education and productivity. However, in recent times, employers have cited that poor communication abilities and technical proficiency are the miseries of graduates seeking employment in Nigeria (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2015).

There is also a false sense of security people enjoy when they are equipped with several certificates. It is believed that the number of years enrolled in school is a measurement of human capital (Rjoub et al., 2016) in terms of high productivity and ability. The unemployment rate in Nigeria has also contributed to this because people feel the more certificates they acquire, the more chances they have to be employable.

The high rate of unemployment in Nigeria also contributes to the unavailability of human capital. Even though the government claims that the economy is growing, there is still massive unemployment in the country (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2015). Gone are the days when a graduate had job opportunities to choose from upon completion of his/her academic program whether at the secondary or university level. This is seen in the low percentage of people who are employed compared to those who cannot secure any job offer.

Many Nigerians see teaching as a non-lucrative occupation with little or no opportunities for professional development. They only resort to teaching when other options to find a job have failed. Teachers' incentives are very poor compared to those in other professions. This has discouraged graduates from going into the teaching profession. It is not a hidden fact that many schools in Nigeria do not pay salaries at the appropriate time (Adesina, 2020). This has resulted in teachers not putting their best to ensure quality. However, 96% of the teachers in this study confirmed that their salaries and other remunerations are paid on time.

Romer's (1989b) endogenous growth theory implies that countries with greater accumulation of human capital will have higher economic growth rates. This is prevalent in developed countries where there is an abundance of human capital and further research in acquiring new knowledge. However, the reverse is the case in Nigeria. The country faces a high level of brain drain because the available human capital is constantly taken out without being replenished. Because of the poor

education system, students who are sent abroad to study do not return to contribute their knowledge and skills to the nation's development. Also, the high unemployment rate has made the best brains in the country migrate to other countries for 'greener pastures'. Many Nigerians abroad excel in their professions because of the stable economic environment compared to if they were still in the country.

7.7 Teaching and learning aids and activities

Okebukola (2010) identifies the input factors in the teaching and learning process as the students, teachers, managers, curriculum, facilities, finance, instructional materials, and other general resources. The policy planners are engaged with the duty of certifying and verifying the availability of required facilities, curriculum content, and laboratories to accommodate students (Agabi, 2008). Some of these facilities in the schools are classrooms (a minimum of three classrooms and a maximum of five classrooms for each academic year group), maths, science, arts, music, garment, food, vocational, computer laboratories and equipment, playgrounds, farms, dormitories, libraries, hardcopy and eBooks, leisure centres, sick bays and medical equipment, sports centres, dining hall, staff lodges.

Teaching is aimed at grooming or developing the young. According to Abanador et al. (2014), the four common teaching methods are: participative or interactive, content-focused, learner-centred, and instructor or teacher-centred. In the teacher-centred approach, the teacher is the expert who masters the subject matter while the student is presumed to acquire the knowledge from the instructor. The student has little or no involvement in the teaching process (Ashman and Ongwae, 2001). In the content-focused teaching method, both the teacher and student have to fit into the content of the material that is taught in content-focused methods of teaching. The skills and information to be taught are very important and emphasis is laid on careful analyses and the clarity

of content (Ashman and Ongwae, 2001). Both the teacher and student are not important or cannot alter anything concerning the content. It is a programmed learning approach.

The learner-centred teaching approach concentrates on learning and the concern of the teacher is on what the student is doing. Learning by doing is an aspect of the psychomotor domain (Laguador and Dizon, 2013) and it encourages students' reflection on how and what they are learning. Petty (2004) shows research findings on the remembering rate of learning activities conducted by the national teaching laboratory US.

Figure 22 The learning pyramid: Research on the recall rate of different learning activities

Material redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Figure can be found: Petty, G. (2004) *Teaching today: A practical guide*. Nelson Thornes.

(Petty, 2004)

The figure above illustrates that students understand only 5% of the information by listening during lectures, students get 10% when they read the information on their own. The students remember 20% through audio-visual while 30% assimilate what the teacher taught with demonstration. In

teaching with group discussion during class the students get 50% of the information. Students who practice by doing get 75% of the information. Also, students that use the information immediately or teach others retained 90% of the information.

The interactive or participatory method of teaching is focused on factors that enhance the learning objective. This is the learner-centred method. Proper teaching and learning sustain a good standard of education, guarantees quality graduates who can compete favourably with their counterparts in other countries (Ushie and Ogbulezie, 2016).

7.8 Summary

The empirically-based model was used to make sense of and discuss the research findings. The chapter showed the links between the research constructs and the outcome – sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. A major thing to note in this chapter is that the growth of Nigeria's economy is dependent on the availability of human capital. Nigeria needs a transition from the old economy to the new economy – which is the new normal. Education and Nigeria's new economy will give rise to sustained economic growth.

CHAPTER EIGHT

CONTRIBUTIONS OF FINDINGS TO PRACTICE (RECOMMENDATIONS)

8.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the contributions of the research findings to practice in the Nigerian education system. The contributions to practice are seen using empirical and methodological viewpoints. The chapter explores the Finnish education system and lessons the education sector in Nigeria can learn from this. Recommendations to practice are also discussed based on the school as a business venture.

8.2 Empirical contributions of findings to practice in the Nigerian education sector

8.2.1 The Way Forward for Nigeria's Transition from the Old to the 'New Economy' through Education

The following will guide Nigeria to embrace the knowledge cum new economy when applied by the government and Nigeria's education stakeholders:

A serious commitment to innovation has to be shown compromising high quality in the education sector. There should be a comprehensive reform in the education industry through extensive research. Transforming education in the face of new technological change and innovation is essential (Ossai and Ajudeonu, 2019). Innovation and research in the education sector create an

adaptable approach, which enhances young people's lives within the school and their future employment.

As the largest and most populous economy in Africa, Nigeria needs a stable and prosperous economy for faster poverty reduction³⁸. Emphasis should be on the centrality of human capital investment in the new economy. It should be placed at the centre as what propels growth rather than labour and capital in the old economy. Investments in human capital through education pay off in the form of higher future earnings and poverty alleviation³⁹.

There must be a commitment to reversing brain drain by offering appropriate incentives to Nigerian professionals within the national economy and those in the diaspora will give Nigerians the zeal to be home and contribute to the Nigerian project. According to Omonijo et al (2011), offering individuals the necessary educational qualifications and higher wages in Nigeria and expanding a better education infrastructure will prevent emigrants who are seeking higher education or job opportunity abroad.

Emphasis on public and private investments in the education sector increases quality and contributes financially to the growth of the economy (Nwafor et al. 2015). The Nigerian government must show serious commitment to the education sector through adequate public sector financing and related innovative strategies (Hall, 2013). Funding the education sector is one of the major functions of the government. This is done by preparing the annual budget for meeting the needs of the various sectors of the economy. A supplementary budget must be prepared by the government to take care of financial inadequacies in the education sector (Nwafor et al. 2015).

³⁸ World Bank Group (2018) *Nigeria Biannual Economic Update: Investing in Human Capital for Nigeria's future*. Available at: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/373161558953247137/pdf/Investing-in-Human-Capital-for-Nigeria-s-Future-Nigeria-Biannual-Economic-Update.pdf> (Accessed: 18 June 2022).

³⁹ Deji-Folutile, O. (2021) 'Funding education: A case of no money or no interest?', *Premium Times*, 2 December. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/opinion/498563-funding-education-a-case-of-no-money-or-no-interest-by-olabisi-deji-folutile.html> (Accessed: 10 June 2021).

Continuous increase in the allocation to the education sector increases the amount of available funds for managing the school system. According to Jakarta (2010), the contribution of the private sector to the national economy is an untapped resource. The provision of financial support for secondary education is one of the areas through which private sectors can fulfil their corporate social responsibilities. This serves as an additional revenue channel for secondary schools in the country.

The Nigerian government must muster the political will to implement investments in education and employment opportunities to transit from an old economy to a new economy and improve the per capita income of the individuals. Nigeria has what it takes to do this if it shows sincerity, commitment, and patriotism to financing the education sector.

E-learning has competitive advantages and many secondary schools have implemented it to positively impact students' performances. Technology has now become a tool to remove geographical barriers for everyone to learn anytime and anywhere without the presence of a teacher. E-learning adds more value to the teaching and learning activities in schools. The ICT sector of the economy should be encouraged to grow by providing the critical infrastructure and building the necessary human capacity. School authorities should provide and utilize E-learning facilities to improve students' achievement (Akanbi, 2020).

8.2.2 Lessons from the Finnish education system

The Finnish education system is witnessing a change in student teaching and is seen as a model for the rest of the world (Klein, 2015). This is because students are taught the necessary skills for a more technological and global society. Although Nigeria is still struggling with the weight of inefficiency in almost every sector of the economy, especially the education sector; some good

practices can be applied in the Nigerian context from the Finnish education system. This is because a leap in the education sector will result in a bust of life in other sectors of the country. According to the Finnish National Board of Education, ‘the focus in education is on learning rather than testing. There are no national tests for Pupils in Basic Education...teachers are responsible for assessment...’⁴⁰ Children are not forced into starting school immediately until they are age seven when they are enrolled in grade school. Primary and secondary education is combined to avoid a disruption in transition.

Nigeria can learn from the fact that the Finnish education system is particular about the quality of teachers and professionals. Contrary to the Nigerian education system, the minimum academic requirement for teachers in Finland is a Master’s degree and so these teachers enjoy great respect (Sahlberg, 2010). The priority is on qualified manpower, low student-to-teacher ratio, helping people grow and acquire skills needed for life, and professional development. Nigeria can adopt this strategy by ensuring that teachers are adequately remunerated (Simola, 2005) and that they are recruited based on the sound assessment as done in Finland. Recruitment should be for those with the needed knowledge and skills for the education sector and not for those who have lost hope in other fields and make teaching the last option.

Pupils in Nigeria start school at age one compared to the Finnish education system where kids are not mandated to start school until age 6 or 7. Education is not forced down their throat, learning is not rushed, and students are not overburdened with assignments but they interact and participate more in school activities thereby building strong social relationships. Assessment is not the basis of education in Finland and students are not under the pressure of examination. Therefore, learning is easier, more collaborative, and interactive, and the learning process is not tested by the result

⁴⁰ <https://www.appleblossomltd.com/finland-educational-system/>

sheet (Aina and Langenhoven, 2015). If this strategy is adopted in Nigeria, students will not be under the pressure to pass examinations and there will be an increase in student learning outcomes thereby reducing the occurrence of examination malpractice.

The success of Finland is tied to strategic planning in its education system. However, the Nigerian education system lacks planning. The Ministry of Education in Nigeria needs to embrace planning for a more vibrant education system. Students are the future of the country so education should be seen as a priority. Finland's education system should be a model for the Nigerian education sector for more effectiveness in terms of funding, upgraded facilities, qualified teachers (Adeoti, 2012), well-paid teachers (Kola and Gbenga, 2015), and a more flexible curriculum that is relevant to the modern world⁴¹.

Drawing from the Finnish education system, emphasis must be on overhauling the Nigerian education system to promote character, personal development, resilience, and communication skills as opposed to forcing students to cram formulas, pushing undergraduates into the labour market through examinations who later become unemployable.

8.3 Methodological contributions of findings to practice in Nigerian secondary schools

8.3.1 Talent Management

Management policies must be in place to ensure that teachers have the minimum academic requirement and qualifications to work in the school. At recruitment exercises, the applicant must show evidence of his skills and subject mastery to assist in raising the educational standards in the

⁴¹ Olajide, M. (2017) 'What Nigeria can learn from Finland', *The Nation*, 30 March. Available at: <https://thenationonline.net/nigeria-can-learn-finland/> (Accessed: 14 November 2021).

school he or she is hoping to be recruited as a teacher. As a top priority, it is important to identify, recruit and retain teachers who understand and drive the success of the schools. Rather than the Board conducting recruitment exercises, the schools can collaborate with recruitment agencies who will bring in their expertise to ensure that candidates with the right knowledge and skills are hired. This is because some of the Board members do not have training or experience in human resources.

Apprenticeship experience is seen to be an actual driver for employment generation and poverty reduction (Fajob et al., 2017). As seen in Table 2, the cognitive learning objective for SDG 8 is that students should understand innovation, entrepreneurship, and job creation and how these skills can contribute to a decent job. The role of the school management, in this case, is to collaborate with organisations to create apprenticeship opportunities for the students. Through the experience from the apprenticeship programmes, the students gather relevant skills to be employable, use their initiative to create and identify business opportunities, and contribute to personal and economic development.

Key findings from the study show that management practices are seen in talent management techniques that attract qualified teachers to improve education quality in the schools and impact society for economic growth. School management should understand the career aspirations of each teacher by identifying experiences, tasks, and learning opportunities they need to help prepare them for possible higher roles. The school management is also expected to effectively manage the school by planning and ensuring that there are enough teachers to be assigned to classes, has a hold of the school timetable of activities, acquiring teaching materials, and retaining the teachers for the tasks ahead. Continuous training and development are important to ensure that the teachers are up-to-date with current trends in the education sector to enhance their job performance

(Mbagwu and Nwachukwu, 2010). Training and development are important for a successful talent management programme in the school (Omotunde and Alegbeleye, 2021). Therefore, it is the responsibility of the Governing Board to organise training activities for the management staff to build their management skills, professional knowledge, and practical experience and also to raise school performance, student outcomes, and quality assurance systems. Training sessions can include leadership and management skills, managing resources, teacher development, managing change, and teacher appraisal techniques.

Furthermore, the study reveals that a futuristic curriculum is important in which teachers must be trained to improve their skills and how they can apply these skills to teaching methodology. Regular training sessions as an important part of staff development need to be organised by the schools' management to ensure that the teachers are up-to-date with new methods of teaching. Nakpodia (2008) emphasises that on-the-job training enables the teachers to acquire more theoretical and practical knowledge, competencies, and skills in their teaching subjects and pedagogy to develop their competence in classroom instruction.

Teachers derive satisfaction and enjoyment from teaching because they can help educate students and shape the future of society. Teacher-student motivation is linked and teachers who enjoy their profession can trigger students' enthusiasm to learn. Some strategies which the school management can adopt for effective talent management are good management styles, clear career progression, reduced workload, more opportunities for personal development, recognition and reward for their work, and collective decision making (Omotunde and Alegbeleye, 2021). Talent management strategies adopted by the schools can enhance operational productivity in the competing business environment (Younas and Bari, 2020). Operational productivity ensures job security for the teachers as a way to alleviate poverty and drive economic growth.

8.3.2 Corporate Governance

Strategies must be in place to ensure the schools' sustainability as a business venture. Well-governed schools contribute more to economic growth, as these schools are stable, sustainable, and capable to provide regular profit to the owners, regular earnings to the teachers, and strengthening their reputation in accessing debt capital (Skare and Hasić, 2016). Although the schools should have a Board size of above 10 members as advocated for by Sanda et al. (2010); more stringent measures should be in place so that these Board members are mainly selected based on their expertise in education and business management to increase performance. The school management must develop, support, and equip staff with knowledge and skills that will make them better educators. They are to manage the changing role of the school as the training hub for sustainable economic growth to support the student's behavioural learning for the development of policies and ESD (Table 1 Learning Objectives for the SDG 4 'Quality Education'). Also, the mandates of the Ministry of Education are to be strategically managed to avoid conflict in school governance. Structures must be in place to ensure accountability. KPIs must be conducted at least bi-annually using a skills audit of the teachers and management, an understanding of each person's roles and responsibilities, performance outcomes of the teachers, a recap of the schools' vision, students' learning outcomes, and parental involvement. Research findings show that the schools collaborate with HR servicing firms to organise staff audits to measure teachers' responsibilities according to the schools' policies. A financial audit is also important to ensure that there is strict adherence to the school's budget (Amos et al., 2021). The main objective of a financial audit is for accountability, efficient and effective school administration in delegating resources appropriately. Schools' account officers must adequately explain, defend and manage the schools' budget so that there is clarity on the financial goals and objectives.

Zero tolerance for examination malpractice should be a core value for the schools. The research participants disclosed that the schools have a zero-tolerance policy for examination malpractice and defaulting teachers are withdrawn. Teachers must ensure that the students are sufficiently prepared for examinations by revising the term's curriculum, solving puzzles that are likely to be examination questions, and inculcating self-confidence and moral values in them to withstand the pressure of cheating in examinations. The Governing Board should pay 'surprise visits' on examination days to eliminate corruption and ensure that the teachers are adhering to the schools' values. The school management must project a positive standard for stakeholders such that they gain recognition from the Ministry of Education as schools that do not tolerate cheating in examinations.

Regular inspection and supervision of the schools are necessary to ensure quality and compliance. It is the responsibility of the supervisory committee of the schools' management board to regularly visit the schools, act as an intermediary between the Ministry of Education and the schools, and also act as a link between the schools – inciting them to exchange experiences and learn from each other (Table 1 – social-emotional learning objective). School inspection through continuous assessment and monitoring is important to raise educational standards, effectiveness of teachers, and ensure organisational change⁴². Evidence from the study shows that the inspection team of the schools' board regularly visits the schools to check facilities, teachers' lesson notes, and teaching methodology to ensure that the schools are in line with government regulations. Resources must be available to carry out these activities, offer feedback, and assist the school with preparing an improvement plan (Ajayi et al., 2002) for quality improvement. The supervisory committee has a

⁴²Ofsted Annual Report 2012/2013: Schools Report. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/386795/Ofsted_Annual_Report_201213_Schools.pdf (Accessed: 18 September, 2021).

responsibility to provide feedback to both the government and school stakeholders. Supervision should be done within the quality framework pointing out the strong and weak points based on school performance. Feedback from school inspectors is likely to be used if the teachers are involved in recommendations and if support is provided to the schools. Feedback from the inspection can also be achieved if there is a relationship between the school management (inspectors) and teachers, and if there are clear rewards and sanctions to build trust, teamwork, and motivate the schools to perform better (Ehren and Visscher, 2008).

8.3.3 School Facilities

Management's responsibility is to sustainably maintain the assets and other infrastructure of the school. Programmes and approaches must be in place to provide a well-planned infrastructure that meets the needs of students and contributes to better teaching and learning. Where the condition of school facilities is improved and upgraded to modern standards, educational goals and objectives are achieved. The focus of school management should be on developing long-term partnerships with communities, non-governmental organisations, individuals, religious organisations, and the private sector to provide adequate facilities. A strong focus should be on capacity building, developing quality control and management systems, and schools' participation in the process. The management and maintenance of school facilities is an important function of the school management and must ensure maximum utilisation. Since education is dynamic in its method and content, the school management must ensure that facilities are constantly evaluated and modified to meet modern educational needs and the evolving economic environment (Lawanson and Gede, 2011). Issues to be addressed when considering school facilities are:

- Value for money;
- Targeting investments to where it is needed the most;

- Modest design standards that are safe, durable, child-friendly, and emphasise quality;
- Ensuring that there is an accurate provision and balance between new construction, renovation, and maintenance;
- Maintenance unit with well-trained staff and sources of revenue to meet maintenance costs.

Facilities should be put in place as well as training for remote learning. Teaching and learning can now be done from anywhere. Therefore, teachers should be trained in IT skills to form high-quality interactions with students even remotely and proffer solutions to the challenges of technology. Infrastructure development promotes growth and equity, and through both channels, helps to reduce the poor quality of students. Investment in infrastructure also contributes to sustainable economic growth by enhancing human capital through improved access to schools (Eturoma and Edame, 2014).

8.3.4 Funding and financial management

Although school fees are the major source of finance to offset administrative costs; the schools can engage in alternative activities to tackle the challenge of funding. For example, students can be encouraged to engage in income-yielding ventures for the schools such as simple handcraft, art, and farm products which can be sold at school events; alumni support, and PTA contributions (Nwafor et al., 2015). Engaging the students in crafts is a way to build their creative and team-building abilities.

In the endogenous growth theory discussed in Chapter 3, investments in knowledge capital require initial expenditure and in some cases, the capital market is used if the person making the investments does not have sufficient liquid funds. However, in Nigeria and other developed countries where labour laws are prevalent, the lender (in this case, the school owner) cannot seize the borrower (student) and/or their education (certificates) (World Bank, 2019). Therefore, other

ways to tackle funding challenges are by instituting corporate governance strategies that ensure fees are paid promptly by sending frequent reminder messages to parents; more options for instalment plans; making sure parents pay a large percentage of the school fees before the students can be allowed into the school on resumption days; making available enough school fees paying platforms; and choosing a fee collection system that is convenient for the parent.

Appropriate financial management techniques are important to control the inflow and outflow of cash in the school. Budgeting is necessary for the school management to plan the income expected and expenditure to be incurred for the financial year. Prudent utilisation of school funds is through publishing the school accounting records for public analysis (Nwafor et al., 2015). In this case, annual accounting records can be published to the stakeholders (owners) and financial institutions to get access to more credit facilities. Accounting records of the school ensure accountability and expenditure monitoring, and provides an opportunity to be aware of the financial needs. Another financial management technique the school management can adopt is adequate records of capital and recurrent expenditure control to avoid waste.

If the government abides by the UNESCO's (2015) recommendation of 26% budgetary allocation to the education sector and also makes a conscious effort to fund private schools; this will encourage the school management to place more focus on providing necessary facilities and an enabling environment for students as against only sourcing for funds.

8.3.5 Teaching and Learning Methodology

Apart from establishing the school as a business venture, the main essence of the school is to provide value to society by educating people who will drive economic growth (Table 1 and Table 2). School management must ensure strict adherence to policy implementation, especially the one that exposes students to skills and competencies rather than a focus on only certificates. Low skills

perpetuate poverty and inequality (World Bank, 2021). Developing students' skills can reduce unemployment and underemployment, increase productivity and improve their standards of living. Global trends are changing, therefore developing these skills in the schools will create a virtuous cycle and contribute to Nigeria's economic growth by enhancing the students' employability and labour productivity (Table 2 – cognitive learning objective).

Although many students find group work challenging; teaching and learning activities should involve more group work and projects to ensure student learning is achieved. Student participation in group work is an important learning outcome for secondary education and the workplace because it helps students to have healthy competition, apply their knowledge, gain a better understanding of themselves, remember group discussions and projects better, and employers want individuals who have developed their teamwork skills (Elgort et al., 2008 and Barkley et al., 2005). The school management has a role in involving employers in the curriculum. This curriculum must be futuristic with an emphasis on developing the knowledge, skills, and experience of students. With this, students will become responsible global citizens and entrepreneurial-minded to increase individual earnings, distribute income and contribute to a quality human capital for economic growth (Hanushek and Woessmann, 2007). Activities can begin to establish links with organisations like the schools' alumni and some professional bodies through apprenticeships, mentoring relationships, entrepreneurship opportunities, and employability modules. These activities must produce a win-win relationship for the business owner, school, and students. Students who have graduated the schools to the university could still benefit from these activities. Proper investments in the Nigerian education system is necessary for the students and teachers to become familiar with digital tools, interact with others remotely, engage in more diverse settings, and apply their knowledge in new contexts for the 21st century and beyond (Ordu, 2021).

Table 21 Examples of win-win relationships

Activity	Benefit for the school	Benefit for the business owner
Employers provide real problems for students to work on	Students are motivated by challenging real-life tasks.	Range of new ideas
Employers provide work placements	Students gain valuable experience and pay	Potential employees and future applicants
Employers provide staff to deliver mentorship programs and skills training	The curriculum is enriched and students have access to role models and support.	Opportunities for staff development

8.4 Summary

Based on the empirical model discussed in Chapter 7, this chapter outlines the contributions of the findings to practice in schools and the education sector in Nigeria. A major highlight of this chapter is adopting lessons from the Finnish education system. Based on the education system in Finland, education in Nigeria must be centred around competent teachers who will work to promote character and personal development in students for innovation, employability, and sustainable economic growth.

CHAPTER NINE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

'We have lots of studies about what's wrong with our education system. We need to accept responsibility, be bold, find solutions and move forward to make education a centrepiece of our economic development' (Christine Gregoire)

9.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter reflects the entire research study. It summarises the contents of the six chapters already discussed. The study originates from the four research questions that explain the interaction between the research constructs of education and sustainable economic growth. This chapter furthermore gives a summary of the findings from the primary data based on the research objectives, discusses limitations encountered during the study, directions for further research, and explains how the study contributes to knowledge and practice in Nigerian schools.

9.2 Introduction

This thesis explored education as a major pathway to sustainable economic growth in Nigeria and answered the predominant question: How well do education providers in Nigeria align provision with the SDG of quality and access to education? Research constructs were developed to answer the holistic question and were further broken down into the following sub-questions:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?

3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing students to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?

The research adopted the pragmatic, mixed method design to give an understanding of the participants' opinions based on the research problem and used an exploratory research design to discuss the relationship between the constructs. The three schools used for this study are all under one ownership but have separate management structures; therefore, they were not compared against each other. While working through the findings, an interesting part of the study showed contradicting but interesting views of the employers and teachers, and how the document analysis linked to the interviews and focus groups.

9.3 Key Findings

This section will discuss some key findings from the study about the research objectives. The overall objective of the research was to explore the relationship between education and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

Objective 1: To explore how middle/low income private secondary schools in Nigeria obtain and use funding to influence SEG.

The study reveals that a greater accumulation of human capital in Nigeria will impact the economic growth rate. Education systems must encourage entrepreneurship and problem solving, and the government must provide incentives such as tax breaks to young people who choose to be job creators (Table 2). An accumulation of human capital is only possible by adequately funding the schools. Nigeria can improve the quality of the education sector if the government meets up with

the minimum budgetary allocation of 26% (UNESCO, 2015). The schools have a responsibility to adequately manage funds to ensure quality and infrastructural development. Notable in this research is that a proper mission and vision regarding funding and financial management have strong impacts on the school's sustainability as a business venture which in turn provides job opportunities for people and leads to sustained economic growth in Nigeria (Bilkisu, 2018).

Objective 2: To explore and examine how management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools in Nigeria influence labour market demand.

The study reveals that the low quality of education in Nigeria has produced unemployable graduates who are unable to meet labour market needs because the education is mainly theory-based. Students either study outdated courses not relevant for the 21st century or are not sufficiently equipped with the needed skills to get jobs (Cox, 2016). The 21st century teaching and learning requires the effort of the Nigerian government and educational stakeholders to provide the needed infrastructure to make it attainable for students, especially to prepare them to meet the demands of the labour market. The study also shows that the curriculum, which is not industry-based, produces graduates who still have to undergo training before gaining employment in companies. To solve the unemployment challenge in Nigeria, the responsibility of the school is to ensure infrastructure, apprenticeship opportunities, sufficient quality, and quantity of the human capital, that graduates are employable and entrepreneurial enough to create opportunities for themselves. Lastly, the study shows that a shift is necessary from an emphasis on certificates to an emphasis on actual learning outcomes. This is evident in the survey data that apart from written examinations; the schools use different methods such as talent hunts, debates, research groups, projects, classroom quizzes, and seminars to examine students' academic performance, relevant skills, and practical knowledge.

Objective 3: To explore how school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria.

The study shows that corporate governance strategies are important to ensure that the joint schools' Governing Board is comprised of members who have an experience in educational management to develop policies that are tailored to the schools' needs to ensure quality outcomes. Teachers' incentives are not equal to those in other professions and this has demotivated the teachers from putting in their best to work and discouraged graduates from going into the teaching profession. The study further reveals that school management practices are seen in resources management, leadership styles, talent management, and teaching methodology that improve the quality of education and prepare students to impact society for economic growth. For the quality of education to be feasible, it requires effective corporate governance strategies in schools and teachers who have the right knowledge and skills and can undergo relevant training in line with the schools' objective to meet up with the standards of education.

Objective 4: To outline ways in which teaching and learning aids and methods can prepare learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria.

Traditional educational and career pathways that have existed in Nigeria are no longer designed to develop skills for the fast-changing labour market requirements. Therefore, the study reveals that a futuristic curriculum is important to prepare students for jobs that are not in existence presently (Table 2– learning objectives for SDG 8). School policies can ensure that students' skills are developed in their areas of interest apart from their career choices. The study further shows that if proper investments in the Nigerian education system are made; the schools can enhance students' employability and labour productivity by involving employers in the curriculum planning,

encouraging research and development, building infrastructure, ensuring holistic teaching and learning, and preparing students with artificial intelligence skills for the technology-driven world. Students must be exposed to activities and facilities relevant to 21st century education to compete with their counterparts globally. Attempts should be made to discourage memorization while participatory learning should be encouraged (Aboluwodi and Owolewa, 2018). The quality dimension in education implies that the students are sufficiently equipped for future opportunities. It also implies that the needs of individual students are considered and addressed in both content and methods to be used in schools (UNESCO, 2012).

9.4 Limitations of the Research

This exploratory research has been conducted in three middle/low income private secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. A very interesting fact about this study is that the schools are privately owned and run by the same management, but each of the schools has its independent management board and reports to the overall board. The research also revealed the schools' strategies for business continuity and student outcomes for job creation and other potential opportunities to enhance Nigeria's sustainable economic growth. Noteworthy again is that more students can access quality education in the middle/low income private secondary schools in Nigeria at very affordable rates if these schools receive more government sponsorships and recognitions. However, some challenges were experienced during the data collection phase of the research study and are discussed below:

The pandemic was a major challenge during the data collection process and this made travelling to Nigeria impossible. On the other hand, a 'Plan B' option as stated in the UWS Ethics Form was to conduct the interviews and focus groups remotely. Questionnaires were emailed to the

Principals and the completed copies were returned. Most of the research participants were unavailable at the time of data collection because of the isolation order by the government thereby delaying the process. The data collection process was put on hold till the students and staff returned to school. However, final examinations were ongoing at the time of data collection, so many of the students were still unavailable. Some of the teachers were assigned to invigilate the examinations and were unavailable to take part in the interviews and focus groups. Many of the schools board members were also unavailable at the time of data collection because of other personal commitments.

Although the researcher has the knowledge and previous work experience within the Nigerian education sector and personal relationship with some of the research participants; reflecting on the researcher's role in this study, the 'inquiry from the outside' approach was applied as recommended by Evered and Louis (2001). The researcher's familiarity with the phenomenon and research context, investigative skills to ask accurate questions and prompt for more answers, and theoretical knowledge and research skills gave valuable insight and allowed a richer analysis of the data (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Many of the research participants who have a range of professions and work experiences brought different perspectives and opinions to the data gathering process. This gave a mixed but interesting analysis and interpretation of the findings to ensure credibility and trustworthiness (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). However, it was not easy to understand the mind (and body language) of some of the participants because the interviews and focus group sessions were conducted online. The focus group interviews were conducted via Zoom, and WhatsApp video call was used to conduct the semi-structured interviews. Some of the participants were sceptical about the E-interview process and this was evident in internet glitches, long silence, pitch and quality of voice, and their facial expressions. As a result, the interviews were conducted

again to ensure that these participants were more relaxed and able to interact freely. Salmons (2012) gives a framework of online data collection methods that should align with the overall purpose of the study. These are the researcher's roles, choosing E-interviews for the study, informing participants before the data collection phase, determining E-interview style(s), selecting the ICT package, ethical consideration, and aligning the purpose and design of the study.

It was also impossible to collect the financial records of the schools. However, the Principals were willing to give an estimate of the annual tuition fees. Collecting financial data from the Ministry of Education would have yielded more accurate results as it will highlight government spending on each account head rather than estimates. However, these financial records are not available for research purposes.

Additionally, estimates of validity and reliability are obtained for a large set of surveys (Scherpenzeel and Saris, 1997). However, the validity and reliability of research in this context were inappropriate because the survey data was only used to understand the research context and not to generalise to a wider population. Therefore descriptive statistics were used using tables and graphs to present the questions and results. This was done to support the findings from the interviews and focus groups using thematic analysis.

9.5 Directions for Further Research

This study builds on previous research studies by Adedeji and Bamidele (2003), UNESCO (2018), Ahmed (2015), and Chattataj (2017) where they discussed education for sustainable economic growth in higher education and other developed countries. However, the research findings focused on education for sustainable economic growth in middle/low income private secondary education arguing that education at this level provides the basis for lifelong learning. This study, therefore, suggests future research on how the research concept can be conducted in public-owned secondary

schools and within the Ministry of Education. Research of this type can be carried out by the Research and Development department of the Ministry of Education using quantitative method and the findings can be compared with the outcome of this study. Some future research ideas to look out for are as follows:

Research Idea 1: ‘Government support and financial management in Nigerian public-owned secondary schools’. Discussing the research problem in chapter one, the Nigerian government provides no funding for private schools. Therefore, further research will be needed to explore funding and financial management strategies in public-owned schools to achieve quality education.

Research Idea 2: ‘A study of the secrets of other developed countries for Nigerian schools’ – using EdTech and teachers’ skills for hybrid learning⁴³ and the World Management Survey (WMS) for schools (Yue-Yi Hwa, 2021) as case studies. For example, conducting a comparative study of the Nigerian education system and the Finnish education system. According to OECD (2015), the Finnish education system is said to be the best in the world because there is a high emphasis on the academic qualification of the teachers. Teachers are required to have a master’s degree that includes research and practice-based studies. As a result, the teaching profession is valued in Finnish society because it enjoys respect, trust, and an attractive career choice (Finnish National Agency for Education, 2018a). The National Education and Research Development Plan which outlines the education policies is reviewed every four years and guides the government when preparing and implementing education policies. Also, the government expenditure on education as a percentage of GDP is 5.3%, which is higher than the OECD average of 5.0% (OECD, 2018a).

⁴³ World Bank (2021) *Digital Technologies in Education*. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/edutech#1> (Accessed: 13 September 2021).

Lastly, high education performance is supported by systems that encourage quality, assessment, and evaluation of teachers and administrators to improve student outcomes, and high supply to meet labour market needs.

Research Idea 3: Research of this context has not been preliminary conducted. Therefore, the study adopted the exploratory design, and a conceptual model was developed by the researcher based on the analysis to understand the research problem in depth. This conceptual model can be quantitatively tested as an avenue for future research using a descriptive investigation and an explanatory design to study the subject in a wider range of schools, derive conclusions from the research, and make recommendations to practice.

9.6 Conclusion

A sustainable economy is resilient and provides a good education and quality of living for its citizens. This is because quality education will enable other sectors of national development to experience sustainable economic growth. The level of development of education is said to determine the level of development of a nation's economy (Obanya, 2004). It is the responsibility of the Nigerian government and stakeholders to make education a topmost priority. Nigeria's economy can become more robust and productive when there is an increase in the proportion of educated people. This is because these people can effortlessly carry out tasks that require literacy and critical thinking. A workforce where every person is poorly educated limits the nation's progress. Workers are those who drive the economic system in Nigeria; therefore, if the government turns a blind eye to funding education, the schools will lack sufficient resources and continue to produce unemployable graduates. Skilling and reskilling the students and human capital for future jobs means a total overhaul of the entire Nigerian education system and society.

Education for sustainable economic growth should be the goal of the schools – which is to train citizens who will be equipped to drive the economic advancement of Nigeria. Therefore, the teaching and learning process in schools should seek to empower students with the right knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes to make informed decisions and responsible actions for a just and economically viable Nigerian society. The schools must strive to contribute to Nigeria’s economic growth through their engagement in excellence, effective management policies, and high-level teaching and learning. What the schools do now, determines the future of the nation.

Figure 23 Link between the present and future of a nation

Source: The Researcher

If education in developing countries fails to align with the demands of the 21st century, meet the challenges of the workforce, and ensure the well-being of the workers; then such education cannot promote sustainable economic growth. Bokova (2017, p.7), The Director-General, UNESCO states that ‘a fundamental change is needed in the way we think about education’s role in global development...education has a responsibility to be geared with 21st century challenges and aspirations, and foster the right types of values and skills that will lead to sustainable and inclusive growth...’ It is a great opportunity, therefore the choices and decisions of educators will shape the

fate of many Nigerians in the next few years. It is the responsibility of the educators both at the government and private levels to redesign the education systems and models in Nigeria in line with future jobs and opportunities for the students. To make sure that young people play their role effectively in achieving the SDGs, each of them must have an education that empowers and gives them a voice of their own to create a more sustainable, equitable, and peaceful world (Table 1).

‘...with good education, I can achieve anything I wish to.’ (S1).

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: Research Participation Invitation Letter to the School

Doctoral College,
Research – School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Research Participation Invitation Letter

Name of School: -----

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu, I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration. I am currently conducting a research as part of the fulfilment of the award of Doctorate degree at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

I am writing this letter to invite your school to kindly participate in the research study which I am conducting. The research is on the topic: Assessing the role of education as a tool for Nigeria's sustainable economic growth.

Please be assured that your school's participation is completely voluntary and the management can decide at any stage of the study to either participate in the research process or not. All responses will be kept strictly confidential and contact details of your management, staff and students will remain strictly anonymous and will not be considered for any use apart from this research thesis. Even though direct reward might not be attached to participating in this study, your school's

**APPENDIX II: Research Participation Invitation Letter to the Governing Board
(Employers)**

Doctoral College,
Research – School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Research Participation Invitation Letter

Dear Board member,

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu, I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration. I am currently conducting a research as part of the fulfilment of the award of Doctorate degree at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

I am writing this letter to invite you to kindly participate in the research study which I am conducting. The research is on the topic: Assessing the role of education as a tool for Nigeria's sustainable economic growth.

Please be assured that your participation is completely voluntary and you can decide at any stage of the study to either participate in the research process or not. All responses will be kept strictly confidential and all your details will remain anonymous and it will not be considered for any use apart from this research thesis. Even though direct reward might not be attached to your participation in this study, your contribution and views would help to obtain better understanding to the concept of this research.

APPENDIX III: Research Participation Invitation Letter to the Management Staff

Doctoral College,
Research – School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Research Participation Invitation Letter

Dear Management Staff,

Name of School -----

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu, I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration. I am currently conducting a research as part of the fulfilment of the award of Doctorate degree at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

I am writing this letter to invite you to kindly participate in the research study which I am conducting. The research is on the topic: Assessing the role of education as a tool for Nigeria's sustainable economic growth.

Please be assured that your participation is completely voluntary and you can decide at any stage of the study to either participate in the research process or not. All responses will be kept strictly confidential and all your details will remain anonymous and it will not be considered for any use apart from this research thesis. Even though direct reward might not be attached to your participation in this study, your contribution and views would help have better understanding to the concept of this research.

APPENDIX IV: Research Participation Invitation Letter to Teachers

Doctoral College,
Research – School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Research Participation Invitation Letter

Dear Teacher,

Name of School -----

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu, I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration. I am currently conducting a research as part of the fulfilment of the award of Doctorate degree at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

I am writing this letter to invite you to kindly participate in the research study which I am conducting. The research is on the topic: Assessing the role of education as a tool for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth.

Please be assured that your participation is completely voluntary and you can decide at any stage of the study to either participate in the research process or not. All responses will be kept strictly confidential and all your details will remain anonymous and it will not be considered for any use apart from this research thesis. Even though direct reward might not be attached to your participation in this study, your contribution and views would help have better understanding to the concept of this research.

This study has been scrutinized by the UWS research ethics committee and asserted to conform with the specified principles of conducting ethical research. For more information or clarification regarding this study, kindly contact me through my email address [REDACTED]. You could also contact my supervisor – Dr Karen Maher via her email address: [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

I look forward to you accepting to share your knowledge and experience with me.

Yours sincerely,

Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu

Doctoral researcher, UWS London campus

APPENDIX V: Research Participation Invitation Letter to Students

Doctoral College,
Research – School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Research Participation Invitation Letter

Dear Student,

Name of School -----

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu, I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration. I am currently conducting a research as part of the fulfilment of the award of Doctorate degree at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

I am writing this letter to invite you to kindly participate in the research study which I am conducting. The research is on the topic: Assessing the role of education as a tool for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth.

Please be assured that your participation is completely voluntary and you can decide at any stage of the study to either participate in the research process or not. All responses will be kept strictly confidential and all your details will remain anonymous and it will not be considered for any use apart from this research thesis. Even though direct reward might not be attached to your participation in this study, your contribution and views would help have better understanding to the concept of this research.

APPENDIX VI: Summary and Purpose of the Research Study

The only reliable way to sustainably develop any people or nation is through education. It has been said by scholars (Aristotle and Plato) that ‘As is the state, so is the school’, ‘what you want in the state, you must put into the school’. The skills that are acquired in individuals through education must be applied to support the both the present and the future generations in their daily lives. This guarantees development and sustenance of the society. Education, which is an important component of human capital formation is seen as vital in increasing the productive and mental capacity of people. Education does not only supply the needed human capital which is germane for sustainable economic growth, but it is also a key to poverty reduction and a major determinant for ensuring equity, fairness and social justice. Teachers are the main stay of the education system. They promote the teaching-learning process by acting as instructor, model, leader, confidant, adviser, counsellor, tutor and so on. These multiple roles mean that teachers’ professional education requires careful planning and execution. Sustainable economic growth is channelled towards nation building. Nation building is derived from the accumulation of human capital and it entails higher income, better education, less poverty, freedom and more equitable opportunities. Human development focuses on creating an environment in which people can develop their full potentials, lead productive and creative lives, and become the real wealth of nations. The quality and quantity of human capital is mainly achieved through education to build the skills and competencies needed for the workforce. Education is an investment against poverty. Human capacity can only be developed when the school curriculum is functional and responsive. My research is based on formal education as I will be using teachers, students, programme/content, school environment. This research thesis will seek to answer the five questions below:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?

APPENDIX VII: Consent Form (Questionnaire)

RESEARCH TOPIC: Accessing The Role Of Education As A Tool For Nigeria's Sustainable Economic Growth

CONSENT TO TAKE PART IN RESEARCH (QUESTIONNAIRE)

- I, voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequence of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my questionnaire within two weeks after the data collection process, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose of and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that participation involves filling out research questionnaires.
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research, my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by using codes and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of the people I speak about.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my questionnaire may be quoted in the data interpretation stage of this research thesis.

- I understand that the signed consent form and filled-out questionnaires will be retained securely in electronic copies and that only the researcher has access to these data until the University's exam board confirms the results of the thesis.
- I understand that under freedom of information legislation, I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Signature of research participant

Date

Signature of researcher

Date

Link Referencing:

<https://www.tcd.ie/swsp/assets/pdf/Participant%20consent%20form%20template.pdf>

APPENDIX VIII: Consent Form (Interview)

RESEARCH TOPIC: Accessing The Role Of Education As A Tool For Nigeria's Sustainable Economic Growth

CONSENT TO TAKE PART IN RESEARCH (INTERVIEW)

- I, voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequence of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my interview or focus group interview within two weeks after the data collection process, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose of and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that participation involves partaking in interview and focus group interview sessions.
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I agree to my interview/focus group interview being audio-recorded.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research, my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by using codes and disguising any details of my interview or focus group session which may reveal my identity or the identity of the people I speak about.

- I understand that disguised extracts from my interview or focus group interview may be quoted in the data interpretation stage of this research thesis.
- I understand that the signed consent form and original audio recordings will be retained securely in electronic copies and that only the researcher has access to these data until the University's exam board confirms the results of the thesis.
- I understand that under freedom of information legislation, I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Signature of research participant

Date

Signature of researcher

Date

Link Referencing:

<https://www.tcd.ie/swsp/assets/pdf/Participant%20consent%20form%20template.pdf>

APPENDIX IX: Consent Form (Documents/Observation)

RESEARCH TOPIC: Accessing The Role Of Education As A Tool For Nigeria's Sustainable Economic Growth

CONSENT TO TAKE PART IN RESEARCH (DOCUMENTS/OBSERVATION)

- I, voluntarily agree to permit observation of relevant items and release school documents needed for this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to observation and release these documents now, I can withdraw them at any time without any consequence of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw these documents and pictures/videos within two weeks after the data collection process.
- I understand that participation involves releasing relevant school documents needed.
- I understand that the school will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I understand that all information gotten from school documents and pictures/videos will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my these documents may be quoted in the data interpretation stage of this research thesis.
- I understand that the signed consent form, school documents and pictures/videos will be retained securely in electronic copies and that only the researcher has access to these data until the University's exam board confirms the results of the thesis.
- I understand that under freedom of information legislation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.

- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Signature of research participant
(On behalf of the school)

Date

Signature of researcher

Date

Link Referencing:

<https://www.tcd.ie/swsp/assets/pdf/Participant%20consent%20form%20template.pdf>

APPENDIX X: Participant Information Sheet for Governing Board (Employers)

Thank you for consenting to take part in this study – your time is much appreciated.

The current study aims to understand the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Using interviews, questionnaires, observation methods, and relevant school documents; the results from the current study aims to bridge the gap of knowledge with respect to key questions such as:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?

If you have questions or would like to know more about the current research, you can email the researcher (Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu) at [REDACTED]

If you ever wish to withdraw your data from the study, you need to email this address with your participant code number within two weeks of study participation. You do not need to state a reason and there will be no repercussions. If you have any complaints regarding your experience of participating in this study, you may contact Daniel Turner (Deputy Dean) on [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

You can refer to the following references to get more information regarding the existing literature:

Laurie, R, Nonyama-Tarumi, Y, Mckeon, R. and Hopkins, C. (2016) ‘Contributions of education for sustainable development (ESD) to quality education: A synthesis of research’, *Journal of Education for Sustainable Development*, 10(2), pp.226-242.

Manuel, M., Coppard, D., Dodd, A., Desai, H., Watts, R., Christensen, Z. and Manea, S. (2019) *Subnational investment in human capital. ODI Research Associate.*

Okoroma, N. (2006) ‘Educational policies and problems of implementation in Nigeria’, *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 46(2), pp. 244-263.

APPENDIX XI: Participant Information Sheet for Management Staff

Thank you for consenting to take part in this study – your time is much appreciated.

The current study aims to understand the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Using interviews, questionnaires, observation methods, and relevant school documents; the results from the current study aims to bridge the gap of knowledge with respect to key questions such as:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?

If you have questions or would like to know more about the current research, you can email the researcher (Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu) at [REDACTED]

If you ever wish to withdraw your data from the study, you need to email this address with your participant code number within two weeks of study participation. You do not need to state a reason and there will be no repercussions. If you have any complaints regarding your experience of participating in this study, you may contact Daniel Turner (Deputy Dean) on [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

You can refer to the following references to get more information regarding the existing literature:

Laurie, R, Nonyama-Tarumi, Y, Mckeon, R. and Hopkins, C. (2016) ‘Contributions of education for sustainable development (ESD) to quality education: A synthesis of research’, *Journal of Education for Sustainable Development*, 10(2), pp.226-242.

Manuel, M., Coppard, D., Dodd, A., Desai, H., Watts, R., Christensen, Z. and Manea, S. (2019) *Subnational investment in human capital. ODI Research Associate.*

Okoroma, N. (2006) ‘Educational policies and problems of implementation in Nigeria’, *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 46(2), pp.244-263.

APPENDIX XII: Participant Information Sheet for Teachers

Thank you for consenting to take part in this study – your time is much appreciated.

The current study aims to understand the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Using interviews, questionnaires, observation methods, and relevant school documents; the results from the current study aims to bridge the gap of knowledge with respect to key questions such as:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?

If you have questions or would like to know more about the current research, you can email the researcher (Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu) at [REDACTED]

If you ever wish to withdraw your data from the study, you need to email this address with your participant code number within two weeks of study participation. You do not need to state a reason and there will be no repercussions. If you have any complaints regarding your experience of participating in this study, you may contact Daniel Turner (Deputy Dean) on [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

You can refer to the following references to get more information regarding the existing literature:

Laurie, R, Nonyama-Tarumi, Y, Mckeon, R. and Hopkins, C. (2016) ‘Contributions of education for sustainable development (ESD) to quality education: A synthesis of research’, *Journal of Education for Sustainable Development*, 10(2), pp.226-242.

Manuel, M., Coppard, D., Dodd, A., Desai, H., Watts, R., Christensen, Z. and Manea, S. (2019) *Subnational investment in human capital. ODI Research Associate.*

Okoroma, N. (2006) ‘Educational policies and problems of implementation in Nigeria’, *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 46(2), pp.244-263.

APPENDIX XIII: Participant Information Sheet for Students

Thank you for consenting to take part in this study – your time is much appreciated.

The current study aims to understand the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Using interviews, questionnaires, observation methods, and relevant school documents; the results from the current study aims to bridge the gap of knowledge with respect to key questions such as:

1. How does funding in middle/low income private secondary schools influence SEG in Nigeria?
2. How does management practices within middle/low income private secondary schools influence labour market demand in Nigeria?
3. In what way does school management practices influence education quality and SEG in Nigeria?
4. How are the teaching and learning aids and methods preparing learners to be drivers of SEG in Nigeria?

If you have questions or would like to know more about the current research, you can email the researcher (Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu) at [REDACTED]

If you ever wish to withdraw your data from the study, you need to email this address with your participant code number within two weeks of study participation. You do not need to state a reason and there will be no repercussions. If you have any complaints regarding your experience of participating in this study, you may contact Daniel Turner (Deputy Dean) on [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

You can refer to the following references to get more information regarding the existing literature:

Laurie, R, Nonyama-Tarumi, Y, Mckeon, R. and Hopkins, C. (2016) ‘Contributions of education for sustainable development (ESD) to quality education: A synthesis of research’, *Journal of Education for Sustainable Development*, 10(2), pp.226-242.

Manuel, M., Coppard, D., Dodd, A., Desai, H., Watts, R., Christensen, Z. and Manea, S. (2019) *Subnational investment in human capital. ODI Research Associate.*

Okoroma, N. (2006) ‘Educational policies and problems of implementation in Nigeria’, *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 46(2), pp.244-263.

APPENDIX XIV: Focus Group Interview for Students

Name of School: -----

Hello everyone and welcome to our focus group session. My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu and I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. Thank you for taking the time to join me to talk about the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This session will take about 60minutes. This session will be semi-formal so please feel relaxed so that we can all share our thoughts and ideas.

This session is being recorded because I don't want to miss any of your comments. People often say very helpful things in these discussions and I may not be fast enough to write them all down.

We will be using participant codes to identify ourselves just to ensure that all levels of privacy and confidentiality are maintained. I have placed codes in front of you to help us remember each other's codes. Our discussions here will only be used for the purpose of this research and the tape recording will be destroyed after completion of the research.

There are no right or wrong answers but rather differing points of view. Please feel free to share your point of view even if it differs from what others have said. Keep in mind that your positive or negative comments will be very helpful in this research. It is important to please give each person opportunity to talk without interrupting.

QUESTIONS

What do you think about education for economic growth in Nigeria?

Quality of education:

1. What activities does your school have to ensure good education? Eg. excursions, research activities, student placements.
2. What criteria does your school use to test your academic ability and knowledge? Eg. examinations, projects, quizzes

Labour market demand:

3. Do you think the teaching and learning process is a holistic development of the student or for the labour market, or both?
4. Are you taught the required skills for the labour market in terms of the 4Cs?

Funding:

5. Are funds sufficiently allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development?
6. What challenge does your school face in providing quality education?

Teaching and learning aids and methods:

7. Does your school have sufficient teaching and learning aids for education?
8. Do you think your teachers are well trained on the methods of 21st century teaching?

The aim of this research will be to understand the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Of all the issues we have discussed, what is the most important to you and why?

Thank you for taking time to participate in this focus group interview.

APPENDIX XV: Focus Group Interview for Teachers

Name of School: -----

Hello everyone and welcome to our focus group session. My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu and I am a Doctoral student of Business Administration at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. Thank you for taking the time to join me to talk about the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This session will take about 60minutes. This session will be semi-formal so please feel relaxed so that we can all share our thoughts and ideas.

This session is being recorded because I don't want to miss any of your comments. People often say very helpful things in these discussions and I may not be fast enough to write them all down.

We will be using participant codes to identify ourselves just to ensure that all levels of privacy and confidentiality are maintained. I have placed codes in front of you to help us remember each other's codes. Our discussions here will only be used for the purpose of this research and the tape recording will be destroyed after completion of the research.

There are no right or wrong answers but rather differing points of view. Please feel free to share your point of view even if it differs from what others have said. Keep in mind that your positive or negative comments will be very helpful in this research. It is important to please give each person opportunity to talk without interrupting.

QUESTIONS

In general, what do you think about education for economic growth in Nigeria?

1. What challenge does your school face in providing quality education?
2. In your opinion, are the Nigerian government policies feasible and sustainable?

3. How are the 4Cs reflected in the education of the learner? Collaboration, Critical thinking, Communication, Creativity
4. Does your school encourage student placement in private organisations, research activities and excursions to give them hands-on experience within the academic environment and labour market?
5. Which of the following issues related to economic growth are embedded in the curriculum or extra-curricular activities? Eg. CSR activities, student placement, entrepreneurship education, research clubs, debates, STEAM, etc Select all that apply
6. What criteria does your school use to test your academic ability and knowledge? Eg. examinations, projects, quizzes

The aim of this research will be to understand the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Of all the issues we have discussed, what is the most important to you and why?

Thank you for taking time to participate in this focus group interview.

APPENDIX XVI: Semi-Structured Interview Session for Teachers

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu. I am a Doctoral student of University of the West of Scotland. Thank you for taking the time to join me to talk about the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This session will take about 60minutes. This session will be semi-formal so please feel relaxed so that we can share our thoughts and ideas. Even though you have opted to take part in this interview session, please be reassured that this interview is completely voluntary and you can decide to withdraw from participating at any time if you wish.

Purpose: The information gathered through this interview will be used as a part of mixed research into the role of education as a tool for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth. The research is conducted as partial fulfilment for the completion of doctoral research for the award of Doctorate in Business Administration.

Confidentiality: Please note that this interview session will be recorded and the responses you provide are completely anonymous and confidential. The research outcome and report will not include reference to any individual. The researcher has sole ownership of the interview records and these will be destroyed after completion of the research.

May I turn on the digital recorder?

Name of School: -----

Before we begin, it would be nice if you could tell me a little bit about yourself. You don’t need to mention your name or job role.

Prompt: How long have you been working in this school?

1. Quality of education

How does your school's curriculum relate to the issues of economic growth?

Prompt: For example, considering issues like entrepreneurship education, research clubs, debates, student placement.

Prompt: Are these issues embedded in the curriculum?

In terms of educational activities, does your school collaborate with other organisations for student placement, research activities and excursions to give them hands-on experience within the academic environment and labour market?

Prompt: Are these organisations private or public owned?

Prompt: How was this collaboration useful to you, the students, and the school?

Can you tell me if your school faces any challenge in providing quality education.

Prompt: Do you think this challenge (if any) is in the area of funding, the management, or infrastructural facilities?

Prompt: How do you think this challenge can be solved?

2. Labour market demand

How would you describe the way the students are taught skills for the 21st century?

Prompt: Do you think the 4Cs of Collaboration, Creativity, Communication and Critical thinking are reflected in the teaching?

Prompt: In what ways do you reflect the 4Cs in teaching?

3. Government policies

What will you say about the Nigerian government policies on education?

Prompt: Can you think of any government policy and how it has helped the education sector?

Prompt: Do you think these policies are feasible and sustainable?

4. Teaching and learning aids and methods

Does your school use only examination to test the academic ability and knowledge of the student?

Prompt: How will you rate the use of examination? Has it really helped boost the learning process of the student?

Prompt: Apart from examination, what other option do you think the school can use to grade the student?

APPENDIX XVII: Semi-Structured Interview Session for Management

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu. I am a Doctoral student of University of the West of Scotland. Thank you for taking the time to join me to talk about the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This session will take about 60minutes. This session will be semi-formal so please feel relaxed so that we can share our thoughts and ideas. Even though you have opted to take part in this interview session, please be reassured that your participation is completely voluntary and you can decide to withdraw from participating at any time if you wish.

Purpose: The information gathered through this interview will be used as a part of mixed research into the role of education as a tool for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth. The research is conducted as partial fulfilment for the completion of doctoral research for the award of Doctorate in Business Administration.

Confidentiality: Please note that this interview session will be recorded and the responses you provide are completely anonymous and confidential. The research outcome and report will not include reference to any individual. The researcher has sole ownership of the interview records and these will be destroyed after completion of the research.

May I turn on the digital recorder?

Name of School: -----

Before we begin, it would be nice if you could tell me a little bit about yourself. You don’t need to mention your name or job role.

Prompt: How long have you been working in this school?

Prompt: Can you tell me what you think about education for economic growth in Nigeria.

1. Labour market demand

How would you describe the way the students are taught skills for the 21st century?

Prompt: Do you think the 4Cs of Collaboration, Creativity, Communication and Critical thinking are reflected in the teaching?

Prompt: In what ways do you reflect the 4Cs in teaching?

In what way is the education functional to solve the problem of youth unemployment in Nigeria?

2. Quality of education

How does your school's curriculum relate to the issues of economic growth?

Prompt: For example, considering issues like entrepreneurship education, research clubs, debates, student placement.

Prompt: Are these issues embedded in the curriculum?

In terms of educational activities, does your school collaborate with other organisations for student placement, research activities and excursions to give them hands-on experience within the academic environment and labour market?

Prompt: Are these organisations private or public owned?

Prompt: How was this collaboration useful to you, the students, and the school?

Can you tell me if your school faces any challenge in providing quality education.

Prompt: Do you think this challenge (if any) is in the area of funding, the teachers, parents, or infrastructural facilities?

Prompt: How do you think this challenge can be solved?

3. Funding

How is your school funded?

Prompt: Are funds raised internally or from fees, donations, government, loans or other means?

Prompt: Are fees paid on time by parents? If not, does this affect the school in any way?

Does your school partner with other organisations to tackle any funding issues if they arise?

Prompt: In what way has this helped the school?

Prompt: Are these funds paid back? Within what time range are you required to pay back?

4. Teaching and learning aids and methods

Does your school use only examination to test the academic ability and knowledge of the student?

Prompt: How will you rate the use of examination? Has it really helped boost the learning process of the student?

Prompt: Apart from examination, what other option do you think the school can use to grade the student?

5. Government policies

What will you say about the Nigerian government policies on education?

Prompt: Can you think of any government policy and how it has helped the education sector?

Prompt: do you think these policies are feasible and sustainable?

6. Management policies

What management policies does your school have to reflect both teachers and learners motivation, national economic growth and corporate social responsibility?

Prompt: For example, incentives for the best student or even the least performing student, learning opportunities for students in the host community?

What is the school's policy on talent management for staff?

Prompt: In terms of recruiting, training/re-training, retrenching

Prompt: How often do you train your teachers? Are trainings done internally or do you collaborate with other organisations to achieve this?

In what way has the global pandemic of Covid-19 affected your school?

Prompt: Were teaching and learning activities done remotely?

Prompt: How was this achieved?

Are there opportunities to interact with your school's stakeholders?

Prompt: How do you achieve this?

APPENDIX XVIII: Semi-Structured Interview Session for Employers

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu. I am a Doctoral student of University of the West of Scotland. Thank you for taking the time to join me to talk about the need for and impact of education for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This session will take about 60minutes. This session will be semi-formal so please feel relaxed so that we can share our thoughts and ideas. Even though you have opted to take part in this interview session, please be reassured that your participation is completely voluntary and you can decide to withdraw from participating at any time if you wish.

Purpose: The information gathered through this interview will be used as a part of mixed research into the role of education as a tool for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth. The research is conducted as partial fulfilment for the completion of doctoral research for the award of Doctorate in Business Administration.

Confidentiality: Please note that this interview session will be recorded and the responses you provide are completely anonymous and confidential. The research outcome and report will not include reference to any individual. The researcher has sole ownership of the interview records and these will be destroyed after completion of the research.

Name of School: -----

Before we begin, it would be nice if you could tell me a little bit about yourself. You don’t need to mention your name or job role.

Prompt: In your opinion, what you think about education for economic growth in Nigeria.

Prompt: Do you think education the only determinant for economic growth in Nigeria? Why?

1. Government policies

What will you say about the Nigerian government policies on education?

Prompt: Can you think of any government policy and how it has helped the education sector?

Prompt: Do you think these policies are feasible and sustainable?

2. Quality of education

Is the process of education for holistic development or the labour market, or both?

Prompt: What areas of a person show that he/she had good quality of education?

How well do education providers in Nigeria align provision with the Sustainable Development Goal of quality and access to education?

Do your teachers show that there is a growth or decline in the quality of education in Nigeria?

Prompt: Can you remember any recruitment exercise you conducted that portrayed this growth or decline?

3. Management policy

What is your school's policy on talent management for staff?

Prompt: In terms of recruiting, training/re-training, retrenching

Prompt: How often do you train your teachers? Are trainings done internally or do you collaborate with other organisations to achieve this?

In what way has the global pandemic of Covid-19 affected your school?

Prompt: Were teaching and learning activities done remotely?

Prompt: How was this achieved?

What strategies do you have to ensure the school's sustainability?

Prompt: Is the school able to meet the needs/requirements of the stakeholders?

APPENDIX XIX: Questionnaire for Teachers

Doctoral College,
School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Target respondents: The teachers,

Request for response to Research Questionnaire

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu. I am a Doctoral student of University of the West of Scotland.

Purpose: The information gathered through this questionnaire will be used as a part of mixed research into the role of education as a tool for Nigeria's sustainable economic growth. The research is conducted as partial fulfilment for the completion of doctoral research for the award of Doctorate in Business Administration.

Confidentiality: Please note that the responses you provide are completely anonymous and confidential. The research outcome and report will not include reference to any individual. The researcher has sole ownership of completed questionnaires and these will be destroyed after completion of the research.

Yours sincerely,

Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu

Name of school: -----

Instruction: Please indicate by ticking (√) in the column provided as appropriate to you.

Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Indecisive (I), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

S/No.	Teaching and learning aids and methods	SA	A	I	D	SD
1.	There are sufficient teaching and learning aids for education					
2.	Teachers are well trained on the methods of 21 st century teaching					
3.	Examination is the only criterion used to test the academic ability and knowledge of the learner.					
	Quality of education					
4.	I have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector					
5.	The school management provides opportunities for my training and development					
	Funding					
6.	Funds are sufficiently allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development.					
	Labour market demand					
7.	Learners are taught the required skills for the labour market					
8.	The curriculum is relevant to meet the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement.					

Quality of education:

9. Which of the following issues related to economic growth are embedded in the curriculum or extra-curricular activities? Select all that apply

- a. CSR activities
- b. Student placement
- c. Entrepreneurship education
- d. Research clubs/projects
- e. Debates

10. Is the curriculum relevant to meet the pressing need of Nigeria's economic advancement?

RELEVANT	IRRELEVANT
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Funding:

Underline the appropriate answer.

11. Do you receive salaries and other remunerations?

YES	NO
-----	----

a. Are they paid on time?

YES	NO
-----	----

APPENDIX XX: Questionnaire for Management

Doctoral College,
School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of the West of Scotland.

Target respondents: The management,

Request for response to Research Questionnaire

My name is Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu. I am a Doctoral student of University of the West of Scotland.

Purpose: The information gathered through this questionnaire will be used as a part of mixed research into the role of education as a tool for Nigeria’s sustainable economic growth. The research is conducted as partial fulfilment for the completion of doctoral research for the award of Doctorate in Business Administration.

Confidentiality: Please note that the responses you provide are completely anonymous and confidential. The research outcome and report will not include reference to any individual. The researcher has sole ownership of completed questionnaires and these will be destroyed after completion of the research.

Yours sincerely,

Uchechi Bel-Ann Ordu

Name of school: -----

Instruction: Please indicate by ticking (√) in the column provided as appropriate to you.

Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Indecisive (I), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

S/No.	Labour market demand	SA	A	I	D	SD
1.	Learners are taught the required skills for the labour market					
2.	Education is the only determinant for economic growth in Nigeria					
	Funding					
3.	Funds are sufficiently allocated to other elements of education for infrastructural development?					
	Quality of education					
4.	I have the required knowledge and skill to be in the education sector?					
	Teaching and learning aids and methods					
5.	Is examination the only criterion to test the academic ability and knowledge of the learner?					

Funding:

6 Who funds the education sector in Nigeria? Select all that apply

- a. Private sector (financial institutions, individuals, organisations, NGOs)
- b. Public sector (government)
- c. Foreign aids

i. Is your school internally funded or funded by the government?

- a. Internally funded

- b. Government funded
- Both

Quality of education:

- ii. Teachers are well trained on the methods of 21st century teaching?

TRUE	FALSE
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- iii. Which of the following issues related to economic growth are embedded in the curriculum or extra-curricular activities? Select all that apply

- a. CSR activities
- b. Student placement
- c. Entrepreneurship education
- d. Research clubs/projects
- e. Debates

APPENDIX XXI: Observation Guide

1. Observing teaching and learning activity in the classroom.
2. Observing teaching and learning activities in laboratories taking note of teaching/learning aids
3. Observing recruitment activities and methods
4. Observing schools' extra curricula activities

APPENDIX XXII: STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

TEACHERS' RESPONSE ON TEACHING AND LEARNING AIDS AND METHODS

Statistics

		Q1	Q2	Q3
N	Valid	72	72	72
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		3.5833	3.7222	2.6667
Std. Deviation		1.14756	1.09058	1.43399
Variance		1.317	1.189	2.056

Question 1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Disagree	14	19.4	19.4	23.6
	Indecisive	8	11.1	11.1	34.7
	Agree	32	44.4	44.4	79.2
	Strongly Agree	15	20.8	20.8	100.0
Total		72	100.0	100.0	

Question 2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	16	22.2	22.2	22.2
	Indecisive	7	9.7	9.7	31.9
	Agree	30	41.7	41.7	73.6
	Strongly Agree	19	26.4	26.4	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Question 3

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	17	23.6	23.6	23.6
	Disagree	26	36.1	36.1	59.7
	Indecisive	5	6.9	6.9	66.7
	Agree	12	16.7	16.7	83.3
	Strongly Agree	12	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

TEACHERS' RESPONSE ON QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Statistics

		Q4	Q5
N	Valid	72	72
	Missing	0	0
Mean		4.6389	4.3194
Std. Deviation		.48369	.70863
Variance		.234	.502

Question 4

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	26	36.1	36.1	36.1
	Strongly Agree	46	63.9	63.9	100.0
Total		72	100.0	100.0	

Question 5

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	2	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Indecisive	4	5.6	5.6	8.3
	Agree	35	48.6	48.6	56.9
	Strongly Agree	31	43.1	43.1	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

TEACHERS' RESPONSE ON FUNDING

Question 6

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Disagree	15	20.8	20.8	25.0
	Indecisive	14	19.4	19.4	44.4
	Agree	28	38.9	38.9	83.3
	Strongly Agree	12	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

TEACHERS' RESPONSE ON LABOUR MARKET DEMAND

Statistics

		Q7	Q8
N	Valid	72	72
	Missing	0	0
Mean		3.5833	3.3611
Std. Deviation		.96049	1.14210
Variance		.923	1.304

Question 7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	1.4	1.4	1.4
Disagree	11	15.3	15.3	16.7
Indecisive	15	20.8	20.8	37.5
Agree	35	48.6	48.6	86.1
Strongly Agree	10	13.9	13.9	100.0
Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Question 8

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	6	8.3	8.3	8.3
Disagree	11	15.3	15.3	23.6
Indecisive	15	20.8	20.8	44.4
Agree	31	43.1	43.1	87.5
Strongly Agree	9	12.5	12.5	100.0
Total	72	100.0	100.0	

TEACHERS' RESPONSE ON QUALITY OF EDUCATION (EXTRA CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES)

Question 1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	CSR Activities	9	12.5	12.5	12.5
	Student Placement	8	11.1	11.1	23.6
	Entrepreneurship Education	21	29.2	29.2	52.8
	Research Clubs/Projects	18	25.0	25.0	77.8
	Debates	16	22.2	22.2	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Question 2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Relevant	47	65.3	65.3	65.3
	Irrelevant	25	34.7	34.7	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Bar Chart Distribution of Respondents on Quality of Education

TEACHERS' RESPONSE ON FUNDING (SALARIES/PAYMENT)

Findings 3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	64	88.9	88.9	88.9
No	8	11.1	11.1	100.0
Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Findings 4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	69	95.8	95.8	95.8
No	3	4.2	4.2	100.0
Total	72	100.0	100.0	

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON LABOUR MARKET DEMAND

Statistics

	Q1	Q2
N Valid	19	19
Missing	0	0
Mean	4.0000	3.2105
Std. Deviation	.81650	1.13426
Variance	.667	1.287

Question 1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	2	10.5	10.5	10.5
Agree	13	68.4	68.4	78.9
Strongly Agree	4	21.1	21.1	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Question 2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	7	36.8	36.8	36.8
Indecisive	4	21.1	21.1	57.9
Agree	5	26.3	26.3	84.2
Strongly Agree	3	15.8	15.8	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON FUNDING

Statistics (Question 3)

N	Valid	19
	Missing	0
Mean		2.4737
Std. Deviation		1.02026
Variance		1.041

Question 3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
Disagree	13	68.4	68.4	73.7
Indecisive	1	5.3	5.3	78.9
Agree	3	15.8	15.8	94.7
Strongly Agree	1	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Bar Chart on Distribution of Respondents on Funding

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Statistics (Question 4)

N	Valid	19
	Missing	0
Mean		4.4211
Std. Deviation		.76853
Variance		.591

Question 4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
Agree	8	42.1	42.1	47.4
Strongly Agree	10	52.6	52.6	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON TEACHING AND LEARNING AIDS AND METHODS

Statistics (Question 5)

N	Valid	19
	Missing	0
Mean		2.6316
Std. Deviation		1.11607
Variance		1.246

Question 5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	2	10.5	10.5	10.5
Disagree	9	47.4	47.4	57.9
Indecisive	3	15.8	15.8	73.7
Agree	4	21.1	21.1	94.7
Strongly Agree	1	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Bar Chart of Respondents on Teaching & Learning Aids

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON EDUCATION SECTOR FUNDING

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Private Sector	3	15.8	15.8	15.8
Public Sector	5	26.3	26.3	42.1
Foreign Aids	1	5.3	5.3	47.4
Private and Public Sector	9	47.4	47.4	94.7
Public Sector and Foreign Aids	1	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Bar Chart Distribution of Respondents on Education Sector Funding

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON SCHOOL FUNDING

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid True	12	63.2	63.2	63.2
False	7	36.8	36.8	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

MANAGEMENTS' RESPONSE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid CSR Activities	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
Student Placement	5	26.3	26.3	31.6
Entrepreneurship Education	6	31.6	31.6	63.2
Research Clubs/Projects	5	26.3	26.3	89.5
Debates	2	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

APPENDIX XXIII: SHORT TRANSCRIPT OF INTERVIEW EXTRACT (WITH CODES)

Researcher: Apart from examination, what other option do you think the school can use to grade the students?

T2: *'The school, in my own suggestion, should use character traits and also creativity not just the head knowledge, and if we use this, we discover that children are gifted differently. Some are unique and gifted in the area of creativity, their hands. While some have high IQ. So if a child is talented through psychomotor you cannot say that child is a dullard. So if we apply these and use it, we will be able to achieve proper teaching.'*

T1: *'Well apart from examination, I think there is a need for the school to embark on what I call talent hunt. You really need to seek deep beyond what you see in the physical because every human being is embedded with one talent or the other but it is an opportunity for the child to display this that matters. So I think when we create an opportunity where the children will come up to really display what they have right inside of them, it will help them to a large extent. So I think talent hunt should also be included apart from examinations.'*

Researcher: In terms of educational activities, does your school collaborate with other organisations for student placement, research club, research activities ...?

T3: *'Research activities, yes. Debate, yes. Even student placements. We collaborate with other organisations.'*

T5: *'We have career day where the schools collaborate with and invite professionals from outside. The students are able to interact with these professionals.'*

Researcher: How was this collaboration useful to you, the students, and the school?

T2: *'For the pupils, I will say that it really broadened their horizon due to the exposure they had during the excursions. Most of them acquired new knowledge and skills. And also some of the things done in the classroom, they saw it practically, especially in the media and communication which they were exposed to during the excursion.'*

Researcher: What is your school's policy on talent management of staff?

M3: *'I will say that we don't have a written policy on that rather we have unwritten policy. Because in policy making, we have both written and unwritten. So we have unwritten policy and we believe in the areas of strength where you can perform better we move you there. For instance, here you won't see somebody that read Geography teaching Mathematics. And you won't see somebody that read Igbo language teaching Biology. So it's in the area where the teacher is talented, educated, or well equipped, we channel your resources to.'*

Researcher: How often do you train your teachers?

M1: *'We have a minimum of two trainings per term...and about six in the year. We have internal training. We also collaborate a lot with external educational bodies.'*

Researcher: What will you say about the Nigerian government policies on education?

T1: *'Nigerian policies on education, if I'm to say something, is next to zero. It is one thing to come up with a policy, it is another thing to implement the policy. You will agree with me that, to a large extent, some of the policies being put in place by Nigerian government has not really been implemented as it should be.'*

T2: *I will say it fluctuates in the sense that these policies are made depending on the passion of the leadership on policies on education. For instance, you see leaders that have interest in education, you see them make policies that are favourable and can enhance education.'*

Researcher: What areas of a person show that he or she has good quality of education?

M3: *I will say... there are actually different tools to measure. But for me, the greatest tool is character development. You pass through a school, we see it in you that yes, you passed through a school and the school passed through you. You see an alumnus of ... there are things you can mention or some social vices that shouldn't come near the person. But you discover that today, that's not where we are. You see a graduate of ... and you know the person is a true representation of the school. But today, it's not like that.'*

E2: *'...It is your thought process, mannerism, your way of interfacing with people, the way of addressing issues and problems, these are the things that structured education teaches you. It enables you to fit in as a good member of society.'*

Researcher: Do you think that these challenges are in the area of funding, management, infrastructural facilities?

T3: *'Infrastructural facilities has been taken care of partially. We still need to upgrade. Then funding is a major challenge. You know it's a private organisation and err it's not a government school per se so our boss is doing everything possible to help the school grow. So he needs encouragement and help from the government.'*

E1: *'Fees are not paid on time by parents. It's actually a battle for parents to commit themselves to regular payment of fees. Some parents are too smart to the extent that you see them trying to*

dribble the schools as it were even up to the point of their children graduating. And that continues to affect the funding or income generation of the schools.'

APPENDIX XXIV: ETHICS APPROVAL LETTER

19/01/2021

Dear Uchechi Ordu,

Your application 13322 ACCESSING THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AS A TOOL FOR NIGERIA'S SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH, submission 12178, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner